

SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE XXI CENTURY: CURRENT ISSUES, DISCOVERIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS - II

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NO	Author	Article Title	Page
1.	B.K. Narmurotov	FEATURES OF THE STATE OF RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BLOOD IN COMBINED INJURIES OF THE MAXILLO-FASCIAL AREA	1-6
2.	Begzod Zokirov	DEVELOPMENT OF OPTIMAL SEPARATION CONDITIONS INULINASE FROM HELIANTHUS TUBEROSUS	7-10
3.	Moncorgé	LATE IMPROVEMENT IN EMPIRICAL METHODS FOR CALCULATING TWO PULSES SIMULTANEOUSLY	11-13
4.	Marufjon Yuldashev, Muyassar Toxtaboeva	BOTU'S VIEWS ON THE ALPHABET	14-18
5.	Nargis Kurbanazarova	INTERPRETATION OF SOME ETHNOGRAPHIES REPRESENTING WEDDING CEREMONIES AS LINGVOKULTUREMA (RELATED TO WHITE)	19-22
6.	Wilson GD	THE PHILOSOPHY ADMINISTRATOR AUTHORITY FOR ASTROTRACKER OF 1 MW HFPV DEMO PLANT: STUDY CASE	23-25
7.	Marufjon Yuldashev, Dilrabo Andaniyazova	THE AESTHETIC FUNCTION OF LITERARY TEXT	26-31
8.	Utkir Normuminov	THE MAIN ASPECTS OF USING ABBREVIATIONS WHEN WORKING ON THE INTERNET AND COMPUTER	32-35
9.	Penny packer	REGULATING PLANT DISORDER TO BOOST FEED SCOPE; UTILIZATION OF BACILLUS SUBTILIS	36-39
10.	Gulirano Pulatova, Feruza Hayetmatova	PEDAGOGICAL LOAD CONTROL OF SPECIAL ENDURANCE TRAINING IN LONG DISTANCE RUNNING	40-44
11.	Zahro Urunova	THE PROBLEM OF INTERPRETATION OF THE TERMS "DEFECTOLOGICAL" IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE	45-48
12.	Ad. Levanony	THE CULTIVATION IN AUSTRIA; ELEVATION OF SULFUR AS AN PREREQUISITE ALIMENTARY ELEMENT	49-51
13.	L.L. Saviozzi	ASSESSMENT OF FERTILIZERS IN SPRINKLED GRAIN: IMPACT ON CEREAL YIELD AT VARIOUS FERTILIZER RATES	52-55
14.	Muslima Yuldasheva	PRINCIPLES OF LINGVOKULTUROLOGICAL PROPERTIES IN TRANSLATION OF IMAGES	56-59
15.	Dilora Jarqinova	DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIFRUSTRATION SKILLS IN FUTURE SPECIFIC TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM	60-62
16.	Davron Jarkinov	WAYS TO DEVELOP INDIVIDUAL CREATIVITY THROUGH VERTIC INTEGRATION OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATION	63-65
17.	Bohrmann G	AN INVESTIGATIVE EXPLANATION OF PARADIGMATIC MODEL OF BOUSSINQ'S COMPARISON IN COMPARABLE POROUS MEDIA DURING INFILTRATION OF GROUNDWATER FLOW	66-68
18.	Nematullo Usmanov	TECHNOLOGY OF FORMATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE OF SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF INTEGRATIVE APPROACH	69-72
19.	Hilolaxon Saidova	INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES - AS A FACTOR OF QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES	73-76

20.	Muzayyan Kholmatova	FACTORS FOR FORMATION OF HYGIENIC CULTURE OF THE MODERN ISLAMIC FAMILY IN STUDENTS	77-79
21.	Shailesh Shukla, Abhimanyu Singh	ABSORPTION OF DISPOSITION IN ARCHAIC INDIAN CRAFT AND ITS COMMUNAL PURPOSE	80-82
22.	Shyam Pathak	PROBABILITY OF SPIRITUALITY: A SITUATION OF INDIAN AGNOSTICISM	83-85
23.	Jaxongir Yunusaliev	SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL NECESSARY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC WORLD-VIEW IN STUDENTS	86-88
24.	Mexriniso Alimjonova	THE IMPACT OF THE ORIGINATING GLOBAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT ON TENDENCIES IN EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT	89-90
25.	Sarvinoz Abdirahmonova	THE MAIN FEATURES OF LEARNING ENGLISH IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	91-94
26.	Crunkhorn KM	ANTAGONIST: PHARMACOLOGY AND PHARMACOKINETIC ENHANCER	95-97
27.	A.H.Piterson	ACCEPTING PHARMACY ONLINE LEARNING: MODELS OF BENEFIT	98-100
28.	A'zamjon Dusmatov, Olimjon Sarimsaqov	TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF FIBER ON THE NATURAL PROPERTIES IN THE PROCESS OF APPLYING THE TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARATION OF COTTON FOR STORAGE	101-108
29.	Khakima Davlatova, Ozodbek Nematov	TAJIKS OF JIZZAKH OASIS: TRADITIONAL WAY OF LIFE, CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS AND RITUALS	109-113
30.	Guljakhon Madrakhimova	INTERNATIONAL LABOR STANDARDS AND THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING VACATION LEGISLATION	114-117
31.	Sabohat Abdudayeva	A BEGINNER'S GUIDE TO ART HISTORY	118-121
32.	A.M.Harsvardhana	HANDLING OF INTERPERSE AND CHANGED FONTS IN WORD RECOGNITION BY NATIVE AND NON-NATIVE SPEAKERS OF ENGLISH	122-124
33.	M.Rangrej Parwez	STUDY ON THE FEELING ANTAGONISM TYPES OF ALLIANCE FOR AS WELL AND VERY	125-127
34.	Alisher Abdullayev, Shaxlo Djumakulova, Ma'rufjon Qodirov	TRIANGULAR IRREGULAR NETWORKS FOR MODELING OF GEOMETRICAL STRUCTURE	128-132
35.	Ugulshod Mingniyozova, Behruz Muxtorov, Muhridin Jovliyev	RIEMANN-DARBOUX SUMS	133-136
36.	William D. Berry	SELF-EFFACING IN COMMUNITY SERVICE: EVOLUTION AND BASIC ACCEPTANCE OF THE SELF-EFFACING SCOPE FOR COMMUNITY SERVICEERS	137-139
37.	D. C. Montgomery	COLLABORATIONS IN CONCLUDE CRAMPED DUPLICATE: LOGICAL AFFAIR AND AN APPLICATION TO PERSONAL VOTE-EARNING ATTRIBUTES	140-142
38.	M.S.Togaymurodov	FARMERS' SCHOOL IS THE FIRST PROJECT IN UZBEKISTAN!	143-146
39.	Nilufar Utkirovna Mamatkulova	CLASSIFICATION OF MODERN TOURIST SERVICES BY TYPE OF ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN	147-150

40.	Shakhnoza Akhmedova, Alisher Akhunov	THE IMPORTANCE OF 3D PRINTER IN SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT	151-153
41.	Soyibnazarov Abbasjon Ikromjonovich	VIRTUAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT - AS THE FUTURE OF EDUCATION	154-157
42.	Lutfullah Lutfi	THE ROLE OF LOCALIZATION IN INCREASING THE SOCIO- ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY	158-161
43.	Bek Mohammad Naiem	IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH	162-166
44.	Wameq Said Ismail	WAYS TO IMPROVE THE SYSTEM OF REMUNERATION OF LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES	167-171
45.	Hashimzada Diana	SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES OF WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT IN RURAL AREAS AND WAYS TO INCREASE IT	172-176
46.	Bahaduri Abdul Shahim	THE ROLE OF INDIRECT TAXES IN INCREASING STATE BUDGET REVENUES	177-181
47.	Farqiy Sher Ahmad	ENHANCING THE ROLE OF ANTI-CORRUPTION IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT (AFGHANISTAN)	182-186
48.	N.K. Kayumova, J.A. Nazarova	TUNNEL NEUROPATHIES IN PRIMARY HYPOTHYROIDISM	187-191
49.	L.Kh. Mamadinova, J.A. Nazarova	THE SEVERITY OF PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS, DEPENDING ON THE BODY MASS INDEX	192-195
50.	Aliyeva Muslima	THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE	196-198

FEATURES OF THE STATE OF RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF BLOOD IN COMBINED INJURIES OF THE MAXILLO-FASCIAL AREA

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ABSTRACT: The hemostasis system is one of the main life-supporting systems, which is designed to preserve the liquid state of circulating blood and counteract its loss through the coagulation mechanism. This duality of functions predetermines the complexity and multistage not only of the blood coagulation process, but also of the mechanisms that limit it. It is known that microcirculation disorders can lead to insufficient blood supply, tissue hypoxia and tissue dystrophy. The fact that in the pathogenesis of the inflammatory process of great importance is the violation of the rheological properties of blood, single works are devoted, however, they do not trace the relationship between the aggregation and deformability of erythrocytes and the antithrombogenic activity of the vascular wall.

KEYWORDS: Blood, coagulation mechanism, hypoxia, inflammatory.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this work is to study the state of the rheological properties of blood in patients with concomitant facial injuries.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In accordance with the purpose of the study and to fulfill the assigned tasks, clinical studies were carried out in 40 patients with concomitant facial injuries who were hospitalized in the ENT department of the TMA multidisciplinary clinic in 2018-2021. All patients underwent a comprehensive examination, including the collection of complaints, clinical examination of patients, laboratory and instrumental research and X-ray studies.

RESULTS

In patients with combined fractures of the facial skeleton, there is a decrease in the antithrombogenic activity of the vascular wall against the background of latent coagulopathy of consumption, compared with other fractures of the face, high functional activity of platelets.

There were no significant changes in the fibrinolysis system and blood anticoagulant activity. An increase in blood viscosity, an increase in the aggregation of erythrocytes, and a decrease in the deformability of erythrocytes were noted.

Partial recovery after the traditional course of treatment of the antithrombogenic activity of the vascular wall, platelet aggregation capacity in patients with uncomplicated course of combined fractures of the facial skeleton, coinciding in time with the stabilization of the clinical picture of the disease, indicate an incomplete recovery of the function and structure of endothelial cells and platelets in this category of patients. There is also no complete recovery of indicators of the procoagulant hemostasis and rheological properties of blood.

In patients with combined fractures of the facial skeleton, in the process of traditional treatment, it is not possible to fully restore the fibrinolytic activity of the vascular wall endothelium and bring it to the parameters of practically healthy people. This indicates a reduced ability of vascular endothelial cells to secrete tissue plasminogen activators, converting inactive plasminogen to plasmin

Patients with combined fractures of the facial skeleton are characterized by a syndrome of increased blood viscosity, increased aggregation of erythrocytes, and a decrease in erythrocyte deformability. In the process of treating patients, there is no complete recovery of indicators characterizing the rheological properties of blood.

In patients with combined fractures of the facial skeleton, there is a decrease in the antithrombogenic activity of the vascular wall against the background of latent coagulopathy of consumption, compared with other fractures of the face, high functional activity of platelets. There were no significant changes in the fibrinolysis system and blood anticoagulant activity. An increase in blood viscosity, an increase in the aggregation of erythrocytes, and a decrease in the deformability of erythrocytes were noted.

Partial recovery after the traditional course of treatment of the antithrombogenic activity of the vascular wall, the aggregation ability of platelets in patients with combined fractures of the facial skeleton, which coincides in time with the stabilization of the clinical picture of the disease, indicates an incomplete recovery of the function and structure of endothelial cells and platelets in this category of patients. There is also no complete recovery of indicators of the procoagulant hemostasis and rheological properties of blood.

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DEVELOPMENT OF OPTIMAL SEPARATION CONDITIONS INULINASE FROM HELIANTHUS TUBEROSUS

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ABSTRACT: The results of studies on the development of optimal conditions for the release of inulinase from Jerusalem artichoke tubers (*Helianthus tuberosus*) are presented. The most effective extractant, which promotes the maximum transfer of proteins into solution, has been identified, and the extract of soluble protein has been concentrated with complete preservation of its enzymatic activity. Three inulinase isoenzymes with different degrees of purification have been isolated, hydrolyzing inulin with activity $I_1 = 0.0175 \text{ U / mg}$, $I_2 = 0.0083 \text{ U / mg}$, $I_3 = 0.00450 \text{ U / mg}$.

KEYWORDS: *Helianthus tuberosus* I, inulinase, Jerusalem artichoke tubers.

INTRODUCTION

Inulinases (2,1- β -D-fructan fructanohydrolases) are the most important class of enzymes for the production of fructose, glucose and inulo-oligosaccharides, which are intensively used in the pharmaceutical and food industries. Three types of inulinases have been described, including endo-inulinases, exo-inulinases and fructofuranosidases (invertases), which are not common catabolic carbohydratases. The main enzymatic reaction involves mainly two enzymes that catalyze the hydrolysis of inulin and they are divided into two groups according to the type of action on inulin. Exo-inulinases (EC 3.2.1.80) cleave the terminal fructose fragment from the inulin molecule; endo-inulinase (EC 3.2.1.7), as a result of hydrolysis of the internal bond in the inulin molecule form various oligosaccharides, which are soluble dietary fibers and functional sweeteners [1, 2]. Inulinases are widespread among higher plants and microorganisms. The process of obtaining inulinases from fungi, yeasts, and bacteria is well studied and widely presented in the literature [3]. Currently, there are highly active enzyme preparations of inulinases that promote the conversion of inulin-containing raw materials into fructosides of

various degrees of polymerization. Plant inulinases are less studied and the results of their study are presented only in two early works [4]. At present, the physiological role of plant inulinases is still not fully understood. It is assumed that the change in the carbohydrate composition of tubers during winter storage occurs not without the participation of hydrolytic enzymes - inulinases.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Preparation of a coarse enzyme extract. Jerusalem artichoke tubers were thoroughly cleaned, washed under running water and cut into small pieces using a knife. The crushed pieces were poured with an extracting solution in a ratio of 1: 3 and homogenized in a stationary blender (Ufesa, Spain). Then the homogenate was incubated on a thermostated circular shaker with a rotation speed of 180 rpm for 2 h at a temperature of 37°C, after which it was filtered through 6 layers of gauze. The filtrate was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 40 min (K-26 centrifuge, Germany), and the resulting supernatant was passed through an acetate filter on a porcelain funnel under vacuum to obtain a transparent extract. The obtained extract was concentrated by passing it through an AR-02m separating ultrafiltration apparatus with hollow fibers (Russia) of periodic action. The working mixture circulated in a closed loop, washing the outer surface of the fiber, and the filtrate was removed through its inner channel. Each portion of the filtrate was analyzed for protein and sugar content. As a result of filtration, the most concentrated protein extract was obtained. All further work on the isolation and purification of Jerusalem artichoke inulinase was carried out at a temperature of 4°C. Isolation and purification of inulinase from Jerusalem artichoke tubers (*H. tuberosus*). To the resulting solution of concentrated protein extract was added crystals of ammonium sulfate to 90% saturation and left in the refrigerator for an hour. The precipitate that formed was centrifuged for 25 min at 10,000 rpm (K-24 centrifuge, Germany), dissolved in buffer I (20 mM K, Na-phosphate buffer pH 7.0, containing 5 mM mercaptoethanol) and dialyzed against 10 volumes of buffer II (2 mM K, Na-phosphate buffer pH 7.0, containing 5 mM mercaptoethanol) during the day, changing the buffer solution twice. The dialysate was planted and inulinase was isolated.

Ion exchange chromatography. The column (25x310 mm) contained DEAE cellulose equilibrated with buffer I. Elution was performed with a linear concentration gradient of sodium chloride (0–1 M) in buffer I. Active fractions were collected in 8–10 ml by an Isko automatic collector (USA).

Measurement of inulinase activity. To determine the inulinase activity, 0.1 ml of the test enzyme solution was added to 0.9 ml of a 1% inulin solution (0.2 M Na-acetate buffer, pH 5.0), stirred and incubated at 37° C for 10 h. The amount of the formed reducing sugars was determined by the modified Shomody-Nelson method. The unit of inulinase activity was defined as the amount of the enzyme catalyzing the formation of 1 µmol of fructose per minute.

Determination of protein concentration. The protein concentration was determined by the Bradford method by the absorption of complexes of the enzyme Coomassie brilliant blue at a wavelength of 595 nm [1] using bovine serum albumin as a standard. The protein yield was monitored by sequential measurement of the optical density of the column eluates at 280 nm [5].

In the process of isolating and purifying inulinase, we combined extraction methods (transferring proteins to a dissolved state with a 0.9% sodium chloride solution, which, along with dissolution, stabilizes the protein); methods of fugation, filtration and ultrafiltration through hollow fibers (to obtain a concentrated protein extract), salting out and centrifugation methods (sediment formation at 90% saturation of the concentrated extract of Jerusalem artichoke tubers with ammonium sulfate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, dissolving the resulting sediment (in 20 mM K, Na -phosphate buffer pH 7.0 with 5 mM mercaptoethanol), dialysis (against 10 volumes of 2 mM K, Na-phosphate buffer pH = 7.0 with 5 mM mercaptoethanol).

CONCLUSION

The results of native electrophoresis in 7.7% polyacrylamide gel of samples of combined fractions of each peak with the determination of inulinase activity in pieces of cut gel showed that we have three inulinase isoenzymes with different degrees of purification, electrophoretically heterogeneous, hydrolyzing inulin with activity $I_1 = 0.0175 \text{ U / mg}$, $I_2 = 0.0083 \text{ U / mg}$, $I_3 = 0.00450 \text{ U / mg}$ and differing from each other in electrical mobility (data not shown), which need further purification for use in experiments to study their physicochemical properties ... Fractions of each peak of inulin ase activity were pooled, concentrated by precipitation at 80% saturation with ammonium sulfate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, dialyzed and further purified separately.

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LATE IMPROVEMENT IN EMPIRICAL METHODS FOR CALCULATING TWO PULSES SIMULTANEOUSLY

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ABSTRACT: As some focused energy ultrafast-optical estimations include more than one heartbeat—ordinarily one to energize a medium under examination and another to test it—a strategy for estimating two heartbeats at the same time is profoundly attractive. In twenty years, two-beat estimation methods have progressed from equivocalness loaded to an as of late created procedure that can quantify a heartbeat pair with subjective focal frequencies, intricacies and transmission capacities. Here, we survey late endeavors to at the same time measure two ultrashort laser beats utilizing a solitary gadget.

KEYWORDS: Ultrashort beats; ultrafast estimation; FROG

INTRODUCTION

Since their presentation a very long while prior, ultrashort laser beats have permitted analysts to make the most transiently exact and precise estimations at any point made. Nonetheless, such estimations rely intensely upon the capacity to gauge the beats in question, and heartbeat estimation methods have customarily falled well behind beat age strategies. This is on the grounds that the estimation of an occasion has commonly required the utilization of a more limited one, and ultrashort laser beats are the most brief occasions at any point produced. Indeed, even a self-referred to method, that is, one that uses the occasion to gauge itself—all that that could expect to be accomplished—seemed lacking, as the beat is just pretty much as short as itself, not more limited. Twenty years prior, the single-beat estimation issue was tackled by the presentation of recurrence settled optical gating (FROG), a self-referred to strategy that totally measures the power and period of one subjective ultrashort laser beat . FROG and its improved on variant, GRENOUILLE , are generally utilized as self-referred to beat estimation methods today. Notwithstanding the FROG family, different methods, including multiphoton

intrapulse impedance stage examine (MIIPS) and ghostly stage interferometry for direct electric-field remaking (SPIDER), have additionally accomplished normal use.

METHODS

The two-shading estimation was made with a couple of heartbeats with focus frequencies of 400 nm and 800 nm (blue and red). The deliberate and recovered follows are appeared in . An all around isolated twofold heartbeat in red was created by a Michelson interferometer, while the blue heartbeat was a basic heartbeat. The G-mistakes were 0.8% and 0.5% for the blue heartbeat and red heartbeat, separately. The spectra of both red and blue heartbeats were estimated freely and plotted in dark ran lines.

CONCLUSION

Rundown Several ultrashort beat estimation strategies have endeavored to take care of the two-beat estimation issue. The soonest endeavor, Blind FROG, discovered restricted application in portraying fs-beats, because of the presence of nontrivial ambiguities. The trial device and recovery calculation produced for Blind FROG, in any case, propelled other estimation procedures that can take care of the two-beat estimation issue. In light of Blind FROG, CRAB has performed concurrent attosecond and femtosecond beat recovery. No nontrivial ambiguities are known in CRAB remaking, on the grounds that the sign field age component takes an unexpected structure in comparison to that of the initially proposed whole recurrence age Blind FROG. The summed up projections recreation calculation is hearty and requires no additional data for the beats to meet.

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BOTU'S VIEWS ON THE ALPHABET

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ABSTRACT: Botu was one of the initiators of the conversion of the Uzbek-Arabic alphabet to the alphabet based on Latin script. Author of a number of articles on linguistics and literature. Botu was unjustly convicted in 1930, imprisoned, and a victim of repression. One of the streets in Tashkent and the school are named after Botu. Botu was one of the pioneers of modern Uzbek literature, a talented poet and public figure. Botu was also known to the people as a public figure and translator. In particular, it is known that he has been active in the development of school education and higher education, science and culture in our country. However, Botu was yes in some erroneous and contradictory way without mute to the politics of his time. The article discusses Botu's way of life and linguistic activities.

KEYWORDS: Botu, Mahmud Hodiev, linguistics, literature, jadid period, jadidism.

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of materials on the development of Uzbek writing over the past century shows that during this period there were many enlightened people who correctly understood the role of writing in our socio-enlightenment life, and therefore enthusiastically promoted the idea of democratization and nationalization of writing. For example, in the period up to the 30s of the XX century Ashurali Zohiri, Fitrat, Elbek, Sodiqov, M.Shermuhammad, Toshmat, Shokirjon Rahim, Rahim Inomov, M.Usmon, S.Uygur, Ghazi Olim, Otajon Hashim, Mannon Ramz, A.Yuldosh , Yakub Omon, Ibrahim Tohiri, S. Ibrahim oglu, Arif Olimjanov, Botu (Mahmud Hodiev), M. Rasuli, Bekjon Rahmon oglu, Shokir Sulaymon, Qayyum Ramazan, a number of our intellectuals took an active part in the work of alphabet and spelling reforms. Between the 1930s

and 1940s, this work was continued by a number of other linguists and organizing leaders. (Jamolkhonov, Umarov, 2017: 5.)

In the early twentieth century, with the opening of new types of schools by the Jadids and the introduction of new methods of teaching, there was a need for new textbooks that would enable children to read and write more quickly. The “method of savtiya” successfully used by Ismailbey Gaspirali to ensure the rapid literacy of children in the kindergarten was also approved by the Central Asian Jadids. In this region, the traditional method of hijab has been replaced by the "method of savtiya" in new schools. The advantage of this method was quickly felt in practice, and it began to gain more and more prestige among the masses. Based on this method, a number of alphabets devoted to questioning began to appear. Saidrasul Saidazizov and Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov (1878-1931) were the first in Turkestan to carry out this work, which was considered a revolutionary reform for its time. Saidrasul Saidazizov published the book "Ustodi avval" in 1902, and Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov in 1907 published the book "Adabi avval" in Tashkent. According to Yuldash Abdullayev, an associate professor of the history of teaching literacy in Central Asian schools, both manuscripts were originally written at the same time. Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhonov's book was published later only for certain objective reasons. By 1917, more than a dozen books in the Uzbek alphabet were created. But among them, the above two works are considered the most perfect in terms of the internal structure of the alphabet and a number of other aspects. (Nurmonov, 2002: 123.)

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In February 1928, Botu wrote an article entitled A Few Words on Language and Spelling. It describes the author's views on the number of vowels in the Uzbek literary language. In this article, he emphasizes that the issue of language and spelling is the most important and significant for his time, that it has been debated for several years, but has not yet been resolved, and that the "literacy" in this area has not been resolved. emphasizes the difficult task of improving literacy. He then turns his attention to the question of the amount of flours that caused the various controversies at the time. At that time, the process of developing norms and rules of the new Uzbek literary language, determining the number of vowels in the new alphabet was underway. The intellectuals of the time had different views on the issue of determining the amount of vocal sounds. One group of intellectuals demanded that the Uzbek literary language be nine-voiced (like Fitrat), while another group demanded that it be six-voiced. According to Botu, the fact that there are nine flours creates certain "weights" and

"difficulties" in the work of literacy of the people. "Several years of experience have shown that the current nine stretches will have a significant impact on the public at a later date," he writes. In doing so, he refutes the views of intellectuals who argue that the features of the Uzbek language, the sound system should be continued and preserved. (Sayidov, 2008: 64)

It should be noted that the state of language processes at the beginning of the century, the relationship between the language of living speech and the language of printed works, issues related to the formation and development of written literary language are much more complex. Abdurauf Fitrat, who constantly fought for the purity and simplicity of the Uzbek language with objective scientific logic, in his speech at the Language and Spelling Congress in 1928, revealed the roots of this situation, the essence of the issue: "We read newspapers and books published by other Turkic peoples. We have also opened modern schools. We also published a newspaper earlier. We needed our language for school, for the newspaper. We began to care for him again, to understand him. Those who did this were our open-minded, intelligent people. They were few in number and busy. However, on the one hand, Tatar newspapers, the language of which was more or less corrected, also had written books. In such a ridiculous state, our former intellectuals came to the ridiculous view that "our language is not a scientific, literary language." That is why our schools and writings were under Ottoman influence. Most of the hours devoted to native language classes at open courses in Tashkent were given to the Ottomans. All this was an insult to our language, a disrespect to our language. All this was due to a lack of knowledge of our language and literature. A young man and a young woman came together in 18 years to fight against all this, to rebel, to fight against all this. " This "young and young force" was established under the leadership of Fitrat with the great goal of developing the Uzbek language, spelling, literature, art and culture on a national basis. It was the Chigatay Gurungi society, which united the leading intellectuals of the time. (Yuldashev, 2002: 25.)

In his article A Few Words on the Problem of Language and Spelling (1929), Botu argues that changing the alphabet does not solve everything. "The real issue is that it starts after that: we have to look at what we have done with a critical eye and correct our shortcomings," he said. That is, with the success of the alphabet, our work will not end. Now the important issue of our people is language and spelling. This has not been the case for many years, although it has been debated. It is great that we strive to resolve this, even if not one hundred percent. As important as it is to educate our workers, it is no less important to solve the problems of our

language and spelling. ” (Botu, 2004: 123.) Indeed, the problem cannot be solved if the spelling of the alphabet is not the same as in the pamphlet. It was necessary to quickly develop new spelling rules based on the new alphabet. It was not possible to develop complete spelling rules, as the issue of vowels had not yet been debated. In this article, Botu also expressed his serious conceptual views on the acquisition of nine vowels in the alphabet: “We have adopted a common alphabet; we got nine syllables (a vowel sound), but the quarrel was not completely resolved. Just as there are those who claim that the nine syllables are few for our language, there are also those who prove that there are many of them. Of course, this issue does not have to be resolved from the point of view of "no deviation from the common alphabet." Azerbaijan has also refused to adopt the common alphabet in its entirety. The peculiarity of the Uzbek language is that its development requires the addition of a number of innovations in the new Uzbek alphabet. Since we say that the new alphabet - the Uzbek alphabet, first of all, serves to quickly eliminate the illiteracy of workers, and it should be so, we must go in this direction in practice. Our years of experience have shown that the current nine stretches bring the next degree of weight to the masses. Of course, for an educated, enlightened class, this is not so difficult. But we are not saying that language and spelling are the monopoly of this class, and then we will have to reckon with the public. ” (Botu, 2004: 123.) Language and spelling in 1921

CONCLUSION

The analysis of materials on the development of Uzbek writing, orthography and linguistics over the past century shows that during this period there were many enlightened compatriots who correctly understood the role of writing and orthography in our socio-enlightenment life. . Botu has a special place among such enlighteners as Ashurali Zahiri, Fitrat, Elbek, Shokirjon Rahim, Ghazi Olim, Otajon Hashim, Mannon Ramz, Shakir Suleiman, Qayyum Ramazan. Along with his poetry, Botu has made his name in the history of linguistics with his journalistic articles and scholarly articles on current issues of the alphabet and linguistics. This work was continued by many more linguists, enlightened poets and writers in the 30s and 40s.

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INTERPRETATION OF SOME ETHNOGRAPHIES REPRESENTING WEDDING CEREMONIES AS LINGVOKULTUREMA (RELATED TO WHITE)

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ABSTRACT: Language is not only the most significant means of communication and expression, but also the accumulation of knowledge related to culture [1]. Culture combines the material and spiritual values of people belonging to a particular community and embodies the concepts that make up a national socio-cultural fund of values of one national community that do not exist in another at all, or differ significantly from them[2].

KEYWORDS: Archetype vamifs, ethnographisms, paremiological, signs and symbols.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the object of the science of linguoculturology is an irreplaceable lexicon, which reflects the vivid expression of folk culture in the language: ethnographies, lacunae, exotisms and stylistic collections of language, mythical appearances of language units: archetype vamifs (myths and legends), rituals and customs reflected in the language, paremiological fund of the language, language standards, signs and symbols, analogies and metaphors in the language, as well as Uzbek speech habits and forms of speech etiquette. In this chapter, we have analyzed the ethnographisms related to lingvokulturemas - wedding ceremonies that are part of linguocultural units.

Linguistic units, such as words, phrases, and expressions that represent cultural characteristics, form lingvokulturema - linguocultural units. Linguoculturema is the basic unit of linguocultural analysis. The term was proposed by V.V. Vorobyov (Vorobyov, 1997) and is widely used in the literature in the field of linguistics, cultural studies and linguoculturology.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In the study of a particular culture, the content and form of expression of language units specific to that culture must also be considered. According to V.V. Vorobyov, a linguistic unit that differs from the word and its lexical-semantic meaning - lingvokulturema

includes and expresses not only the relevant features specific to the segments of the language (linguistic meaning), but also the segments of culture (non-linguistic cultural meaning). It is a dialectical unit with a linguistic and extralinguistic (conceptual and objective) content as a complex unit. This unit is deeper than the word in essence [3].

After V.V. Vorobyov, N.N. Kirillova and A.L. Afanasyeva also draws attention to this unity, believing that lingvokulturema is a lexical or phraseological unit that includes not only denotative - definite meanings, but also cultural semantics that represent certain cultural concepts[4].

According to A.A. Potebnya, the word has two different meanings, one is related to linguistics and the other is a name that is the subject of other sciences. This is the connotative (additional, new) meaning of the word [5].

Conceptual and subjective differences in linguocultures are especially evident when compared in different languages, which allows us to have an idea of the specific features of the language or folk culture we are learning. Conceptual and subjective differences in linguocultures are especially evident when compared in different languages, which allows us to have an idea of the specific features of the language or folk culture we are learning. Each nation has its own characteristics in social and labor practices, which are expressed in differences in the lexical-grammatical nomenclature of events and processes, in the harmony of certain meanings, in their etymology and in other aspects [6]. It is seen as a broader unit than the word, a unique form of linguistic thinking in linguistics that combines not only language but also a cultural environment. It can also be expressed in words, phrases, the whole text, as mentioned above.

Lingvokulturema - the specific meanings that are expressed may not exist in the mind of the receiver (listener), that is, they may be unfamiliar to him. Understands the meaning of these units when the meaning expressed is fully consistent with the living conditions of the recipient (consciously using these concepts) [7]. Therefore, these units of culture play an important role in translation studies in ensuring a better, deeper understanding of the content given in the text and the understanding of the values in this context to another cultural representative [8].

Linguocultural units in Uzbek language dictionaries are linguistic units consisting of a combination of linguistic sign and cultural content, in the semantics of which cultural information is clearly reflected. In particular, phraseology, standards, symbols, metaphors, constant analogies, speech etiquette, words related to customs and rituals, riddles, national

realities, archetypes, mythologies, lacunae, precedent units, etc [9]. can be defined as linguocultural units.

There are a number of names, words, terms related to wedding ceremonies taken as the object of our research, which, as mentioned in previous chapters, reflect many spiritual and cultural symbols.

Linguocultural units representing religious-ideological views related to color:

Whiteness (whiteness) - when a wedding is sent to a girl chosen for the bride, white cloth (whiteness) is sent to almost all regions of Surkhandarya along with clothes, fabrics and jewelry. While the main intention here is a wish for the bride and groom a clear and bright life, the second meaning is a symbol of trust in the bride and her family. The groom who marries a boy with good intentions is a sign that he believes in the virginity of the girl, that the groom wants his face to be bright in the house.

Chimmat is the first to enter the groom's house, holding the whiteness sent by the bridegroom to the bride's face. Here, the first meaning is a sign of the bride's culture and modesty, while the second meaning is a sign that the girl is a virgin. The next day of the wedding (wedding day for Turkmens living in Surkhandarya, Jarkurgan and Termez), the bride and groom use this whiteness on the first night. The groom's side (usually women) checks the girl's virginity. Ak surdi is the custom of sprinkling flour on the hair, face and eyebrows of the bridegroom as he enters the bridegroom's house and on the bride's side of the bridegroom's house. The main purpose of this is to ensure that whiteness is light, that the relationship that begins with goodness lasts. As mentioned above, looking at white as a sign of goodness is a characteristic of the oasis.

CONCLUSION

In short, there are also customs such as laying a white cloth on the floor for the bride and groom, adding a piece of Chimildiq white cloth, which also has a positive meaning - a bright and clear life, a bright future, a peaceful and serene life.

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THE PHILOSOPHY ADMINISTRATOR AUTHORITY FOR ASTROTRACKER OF 1 MW HFPV DEMO PLANT: STUDY CASE

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a rationale based chief regulator intended for trackers for a 1MW HFPV demo plant in Taiwan. A sun position sensor on the tracker is utilized to recognize the sun position, as the sensor is touchy to the force of daylight. The sign yield of the sensor is part of the way influenced by the cloud, which has a hard authority position with the conventional ESR control. Thusly we have utilized rationale based boss (RBB) authority which grants exchanging the ESR authority to sun direction under radiant or overcast conditions. To check the security of the proposed control, an examination was performed and the outcomes show that the proposed authority can effectively accomplish adjustment of the trackers of the 1MW HFPV demo plant.

KEYWORDS: High fixation photovoltaics (HFPV); rationale based boss (RBB); regulator; relative essential subsidiary regulator (ESR)

INTRODUCTION

As of late, the issues of lack of petroleum derivative sources and an Earth-wide temperature boost impacts have gotten increasingly extreme. Individuals have started to look for different potential answers for those issues. One of the potential choices is the utilization of sun energy, which gives an elective fuel source as well as improves ecological contamination. In this manner, high focus photovoltaics (HFPV) have drawn in much consideration lately, as a result of their high productivity. HFPV frameworks require a sun oriented tracker to produce power contrasted with regular non-focus photovoltaic frameworks. The sunlight based tracker is the critical part in the HFPV framework to empower precise and stable following.

The Institute of Nuclear Energy Research (INER) has fostered a HFPV high force age framework with III-V sun based cells, as an elective source to the utilization of sun oriented

photovoltaics (PV) and as a reliable fuel hotspot for humanity . And furthermore one MW HFPV exhibit power plant , which covers an establishment space of 2 hectares, introduced at Lujhu in December 2009, producing more than 1 million kWh each year, and lessening carbon dioxide outflows by around 660 tons every year. It is an achievement for Taiwan's administration to have put the strategy of energy saving and carbon decrease into training. In the writing, basic sun global positioning frameworks comprise of open-circle and shut circle types . The sun ephemeris gives the evident situation of the sun in the sky at a given second on schedule, at a given point on the earth. Working with recipe, position counters and authority strategies as indicated by the sun ephemeris, empower the sun powered tracker to focus on the sun. This is called open-circle authority . The other strategy for sun following is by utilizing the sun position sensor to distinguish and move the sun powered tracker. In any case, both open circle and close circle strategies have their individual issues of high following blunder, like the establishment mistake, and impact of mists on the sun position sensor.

METHODS

The sun following authority framework, , incorporates the sun position sensor and the instrument declined point agent, the tracker position encoder, the simple and computerized transformation module, the engine authority module, the microchip, the azimuth and the height engine. The sun position sensor is mounted evenly on the instrument declined point agent. The system declined point agent has four springs to change the declined point in the west/east and south/north course. It empowers the sun position sensor instrument to keep similar level point as the sunlight based modules. The tracker position encoder utilizes the reed change to identify the stroke length of the actuator in rise and the relocation of engine in azimuth to compute the sun based tracker position. The rise and azimuth point of the sun powered tracker are put away as heartbeats tally each moment. The simple and advanced change module is for changing over the sign of the sun position sensor to a computerized signal. The engine authority module gets the microchip order to begin or stop the azimuth and rise engine.

CONCLUSION

The proposed authority plot has been approved on an equipment model trial arrangement of the framework and for the trial climate as show in Figure 9. In the sun global

positioning framework, the RBB regulator empowers framework soundness and high effectiveness power creation. Under daylight conditions, the reference-following regulator gives following exactness to help HFPV power creation on a case by case basis. Under shady conditions, the way follow following regulator moves to follow the sun direction, which is put away in the memory. The sun direction table is looked for and determined by interjection when required any time with area between two focuses. By and by, some blunder is presented by computation and by insertion. Notwithstanding, the way follow following regulator is to empower stable following. The alternate way, a reference-following regulator is utilized.

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THE AESTHETIC FUNCTION OF LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT: A literary text is a very complex whole, expressing the content of a work of art, functionally complete, formed on the basis of the visual capabilities of the language, freely combining various stylistic forms in accordance with the artistic intent of the author, has the ability to deliver aesthetic pleasure to the listener or reader. In the literary text, as in other stylistic texts, the laws of strict logic, simplicity, intelligibility, normativity are not fully observed. Uses artistic means effectively. Sensitivity comes to the fore. Melodic, attractive elements are widely used. In the depicted reality, harmonious music, inner harmony is noticeable. It contains many possibilities, such as spiritual arousal of a person, crying, laughter, leading to the world of fantasy, meditation, the formation of aesthetic thinking, learning a deep and different outlook on events.

KEYWORDS: Text, literary text, linguo-poetic approach, aesthetic function of language, means of artistic depiction.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of the compiler is critical in the structure and shaping of the text. Depending on this purpose, the compiler chooses the appropriate language tools and language templates, the appropriate text type. First of all, it should be noted that the choice of literary or non-literary text type is based on the main purpose of the text compiler. In a literary text, the author's goal of aesthetic impact on the reader comes to the fore, while in scientific literature the author's main goal is to have a communicative impact on the reader. In other words, while the content and expression of certain information in a popular science text are primary, in a

literary text such information is not primary, but the idea that should be expressed in this medium - the aesthetically expressive expression of an idea - is primary, absolutely decisive.

The types of literary and non-literary texts differ from each other, first of all, in the weight of the aesthetic function of the language.

Here, first of all, it is necessary to dwell on the functions of the language. After all, there is no language without function, just as matter cannot exist without action, just as language cannot exist outside of function, function is a factor in the existence of language. [Avrorin, 1975, p. 34.] But in linguistics there is not a single idea of the number of linguistic functions. While most linguists recognize the polyfunctionality of a language, some scholars speak of a monofunctional language. For example, the Russian linguist R.V. Pazukhin argues that language has only a communicative function. [Firsova, 1981, p. 8-9.] But it is categorically impossible to agree with this idea.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

G.O. Vinokur, who devoted most of his scientific work to the study of the language of fiction, notes that the communicative and expressive functions of language began to differ from the old ones in linguistics, as evidenced by the German linguist G. von der Gabelentz gives the following point of view in his book, published in 1891: "Language is a fragmentary expression of thought, and thought is a combination of concepts. But human language wants to express not only related concepts and their logical relationships, but also the speaker's relationship to his own thought; I want to express not only what I say, but also myself, and in this way the psychological factor is added to the logical factor, saturating it in all respects". [Vinokur, 1991, p. 44.] In modern linguistic literature, four to five functions of language are mainly noted. For example, V.A. Avrorin emphasizes the need to distinguish between communicative (communication tool, means), expressive (expression of ideas), constructive (formation of ideas), accumulative (accumulation, storage of social experience and knowledge) functions of language. [Avrorin, 1975, 44-p.]

When studying the language of fiction, in addition to the term "expressive function" of language, terms such as "poetic function of language", "artistic function of language", "stylistic function of language", "rhetorical function of language", "aesthetic function of language" are used. The concept and term "poetic function" of language were first used in the work of the famous Russian-American philologist R. Jakobson "Linguistics and Poetics" and it is defined in terms of the thesis that in fiction it is important not that it is expressed, but that how it is

expressed ("Fiction is language in a poetic function"). [Budagov, 1988, p. 280.] The famous Russian philologist G.O. Vinokur, who lived at the beginning of the last century, used the term "poetic task", as well as the term "artistic task" (the term "poetic language" also refers to the language of the artistic function, for example, science, on the contrary, it can also mean a language that is artistic material"). [Vinokur, 1991, p. 51.]

R. Jakobson's views on the poetic function of language were supported by French linguists, but some, for example M. Riffater, prefer to use the term "stylistic function" instead. [Khovanskaya, 1980, p. 185-186.] In "General Rhetoric", written by a group of French linguists (from the Greek word for "metaphor")), they say that R. Jakobson's term "poetic task" can be replaced by the term "game task" in psychology, but the most appropriate term is "rhetorical the task". [Dubois J., Edeline F., Klinkenberg J.M. and others, 1986, p. 45.]

However, it should be noted that the term "aesthetic function of language" is relatively often used in philological literature. This is also natural, because the concept of an aesthetic task can generalize them, including a number of concepts such as expressiveness, artistry, poetics. In other words, the concept of aesthetic function is much broader than these concepts.

It should be noted that in the history of world linguistics, there are cases when some scientists overly absolutized the aesthetic function of language. For example, the Italian philosopher and politician Benedetto Croce, in his book *Aesthetics as a Science and Development as a General Linguistics*, published in 1902 and published in Russian in 1920, equated linguistics with aesthetics. German philologist Karl Vossler, who continued the ideas of Benedetto Croce, believed in the uniqueness of the aesthetic color of words and speech and in the fact that this same paint plays a leading role in language. [Kh.Abdurakhmonov, N.Makhmudov, 1981.] Of course, among the functions of language, it is incorrect to consider the aesthetic function as the main, leading task, that is, to interpret language as a purely aesthetic essence. But what led these scholars to such an absolute conclusion is that the aesthetic function of language also manifests itself at every stage, especially in a literary text. Regardless of how subjectivism prevailed in the views of these linguists, they were able to conduct a subtle and thoughtful analysis of the aesthetic function of language in literary texts of different genres belonging to different peoples. [Budagov, 1981, p. 40-44.]

The Swiss linguist Sh. Bally in his book "French stylistics" emphasizes the need to distinguish between the affective and aesthetic functions of language. In principle, states that the study of only the affective function is within the competence of the linguist and linguistics,

while the aesthetic function of language is the object of study in the fields of aesthetics and fiction. Russian philologist R.A. Budagov rightly pointed out that Sh. Bally's statement is incorrect, that "expression in a word, phrase or sentence has a conscious or unconscious aesthetic function," and therefore the affective function is also within the framework of the aesthetic function. [Budagov, 255-p.]

The concept of language differentiation according to its functions was developed by members of the Prague Linguistic Circle. For the first time in the Theses of the Prague Linguistic Circle, the rules for the relationship between linguistic functions and their forms of implementation are clearly defined. The authors of the thesis wrote: "Learning a language in each specific case requires strict consideration of the functions of the language and a variety of forms of implementation of these tasks. Otherwise, the description of any language, synchronous or diachronic, will inevitably be incorrect and to some extent false." This point of view was also reflected here: "Although speech activity plays a social role, it differs in relation to a non-linguistic being. In this case, speech activity either has the function of communication, that is, it is focused on expression, or it has a poetic function, that is, it is focused on the character himself". [Prague Linguistic Circle, 1967, p. 24, 25.]

Naturally, the language expresses each of its functions in its own form, therefore, as the authors of "Theses" emphasize, it is necessary to take into account these forms of implementation, expressions when describing the language. However, it would be wrong to say that this or that function of the language is completely separate and completely independent. Indeed, there is no need to prove that the communicative (communicative-intentional) task is the most central, leading task among the functions of language.

CONCLUSION

The language fulfills an aesthetic function in general, but the degree of its manifestation varies depending on the purpose of the compiler. For example, the goal of the author in a scientific and artistic text is completely different. While the main focus of the author is on informing, communicating, developing and summarizing appropriate rules, proving, proving and informing the listener or reader about certain laws, the goal of the creator of a fictional text is to influence the feelings of the listener or reader, to capture his spiritual world. Consequently, while a scientific text requires a logical, clear expression of thought and does not allow for two different interpretations, a figurative, ambiguous expression of thought comes to the fore in a literary text. In general, it would be less accurate to assess non-verbal text as an event with no

aesthetic value. Consequently, the aesthetic function of language, for all its originality and complexity, is, of course, based on the communicative task, manifesting itself directly in the literary text, transforming it and serving the interests of art. All units of the level in common parlance have more or less aesthetic value in a literary text.

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THE MAIN ASPECTS OF USING ABBREVIATIONS WHEN WORKING ON THE INTERNET AND COMPUTER

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ABSTRACT: The process of reforms in Uzbekistan in all spheres is becoming more and more widespread in the field of education. In particular, the choice of foreign languages along with physics as a priority for the development of science this year is noteworthy. It is well known that in the process of integration into the world community, at a time of bold and active entry into the world market, the need for knowledge of foreign languages and IT-technologies is growing. Therefore, today the criteria of comprehensive maturity of a specialist in the field requires knowledge of not one, but several foreign languages, as well as their native language. A video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on May 6 this year was dedicated to this topical issue. "It is time to introduce a new system of foreign language teaching in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. As long as we aim to build a competitive state, from now on, school, high school, college and university graduates must be fluent in at least 2 foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion of the activity of the head of each educational institution," said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

KEYWORDS: Multimedia, system, network, software, graphics, abbreviation, technology, computer, internet, radio, e-mail.

INTRODUCTION

The Internet is a global computer network that connects thousands of local and regional computer networks. The Internet is a complex system of self-formation and management, consisting mainly of 3 technical, software, information components, which include:

1. The technical component - consists of a set of different types of computers, communication channels, network hardware.

2. Software - programs that perform important functions such as communication of computers and network devices connected to the network on the basis of a single standard, processing of data at the level of transmission using an optional communication channel, retrieval and storage of information, as well as information security in the network is a set.
3. Information part - consists of various electronic documents, graphics, pictures, audio, video, etc. available on the Internet.

HTML (Hyper Text Markup Language) - is used to create documents for the WWW.

WWW - In the World Wide Web, information is obtained in the form of hypertext documents.

Hypertext - Text that guides other text documents.

The Site - is a logically whole volume of information in the form of hypermedia documents with graphic and multimedia elements.

Multimedia - is the ability to work with different types of information on a computer: color graphics, dynamic effects in text and graphics, sound output and synthesized music, animation, as well as full-length video clips, and even videos. To use the Internet, you must first connect to this information network. Here's how to connect to and use this network. There are several ways to connect to the Internet. The types of connections vary with each other and with the data transfer rate. Connectivity and speed determine the cost of using the Internet. As quality and speed increase, so does price. The types of connections can be listed in descending order as follows:

1. Direct connection- DC.
2. Connect using SLIP and RRR.
3. Call-based communication - CBC.
4. Connect using UUCP.

Let's get acquainted with the content of these methods. The direct connection method allows you to take full advantage of all the features of the network. In this case, a separate network is allocated for the user, which is provided by the provider. At first glance, the technical content of the Internet and the content of information seem to be similar. Because in both cases we are faced with the connection of objects organized in a "one-to-many" manner. Not really. From a technical point of view, any computer available on the Internet will be connected to many (millions) computers. Such a connection is called a network (Net). Thus,

when we talk about the network (Net), we mean a set of interconnected computers, and when we talk about the network (Web), we mean a set of electronic documents that form a single information environment. Network technology is a method of interconnection of computers in a network, a tool that defines the basics of data exchange. Network technology determines the way computers in a network exchange information, the maximum number of computers, the distance between them, the network cable, and the equipment. The main types of network technologies:

- Ethernet;
- Arc Net;
- Token Ring;
- Fast Ethernet;
- Gigabit Ethernet;
- FDDI;
- 100VG Any-LAN.

To connect the computer to the network, it must have a special device-network adapter. It can be included in the main board of the system block or installed in one of its empty slots. A special tool-network protocol has been developed for computers in the network to communicate and exchange information. The network protocol determines the order in which computers communicate and communicate, and computers that need to exchange information must use the same network protocol. There are the following main types of network protocols:

- NetBEUI;
- IPX/SPX;
- TCP/IP;
- POP3;
- SMTP.

In the global network - is the distance between computers is long, they use existing telephone networks, special network backbones, satellite communication for the exchange of information. The most popular and popular of the global networks is the Internet. The information component of the Internet consists of a set of information in the form of various electronic documents, graphics, audio recordings, video images, etc., available on the Internet. One of the important features of this component is that it can be distributed throughout the entire network. For example, the text of an e-textbook you are reading on your computer can

be obtained from one source, the pictures and sound from a second source, and the video and comments from a third source. Thus, it is possible to organize an electronic document in the network in the form of a set of several sources through mutually compatible "hyper-links".

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REGULATING PLANT DISORDER TO BOOST FEED SCOPE; UTILIZATION OF BACILLUS SUBTILIS

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ABSTRACT: Organic control of contagious plant microbes can boost worldwide feed accessibility, one of the three mainstays of feed security, by diminishing yield misfortunes, especially for low-pay ranchers. Be that as it may, the interrelationships of numerous natural factors can bring about different communications among the organic entities and their current circumstance, a few of which may add to powerful natural control. Here, we present a high level study of the nature and practice of organic control when it is utilized to control earthy colored decay in stone organic product. In particular, we portray the populace elements of *Penicillium frequentans* and *Epicoccum nigrum* and their viability as biocontrol specialists against earthy colored decay illness under field conditions. The size of *P. frequentans* populace after a use of a *P. frequentans* conidial definition during the harvest season is greater than that of *E. nigrum* following the use of an *E. nigrum* conidial detailing.

KEYWORDS: *Penicillium frequentans*; *Epicoccum nigrum*; earthy colored decay; stone organic product; populace elements; biocontrol.

INTRODUCTION

Acquaintance Plant infections need with be controlled to keep up worldwide feed accessibility, one of the three mainstays of feed security, and various methodologies can be utilized to forestall, alleviate, or control plant sicknesses. Notwithstanding great agronomic and agricultural practices, cultivators can apply substance manures and pesticides to their harvests, and such applications have contributed fundamentally to astounding upgrades in feed security. Discovering non-compound methodologies for regulating yield illnesses is of extensive interest due to ecological and wellbeing worries about the boundless utilization of engineered pesticides . These days, severe guidelines on substance pesticide use exist, and the political strain to eliminate the most risky synthetic compounds from the market is expanding. Hence, the

utilization of manufactured pesticides will likely be continuously decreased later on, and this decrease will be joined by an expanded dependence on the utilization of microorganisms as foes of plant microbes. In any case, regulating the wide range of microbes utilizing microorganisms actually stays an unfulfilled objective in business agribusiness. The primary deficiency of microbiological control is its absence of unwavering quality, and a few reasons can represent this limitation. Firstly, the populace elements of the organic opponent, the variety of the regular populace of the microorganism, and the common climatic conditions are considerably more factor than those that are utilized in the research center to examine the methods of activities of a natural control specialist (NCP). Furthermore, the climatic conditions that most blessing the advancement of the microorganism probably won't be equivalent to the conditions that are needed for the greatest articulation of a NCP's adversarial exercises. Along these lines, substantially more examination ought to be dedicated to recognizing the ecological conditions that are needed for the outflow of a NCP's gainful impacts under field conditions to make microbiological control more dependable.

METHODS

The elements of individual populaces inside the epiphytic local area are dictated by the paces of movement, displacement, development, and passing. Every one of these components is unequivocally impacted by the actual climate, substance therapy, mean air temperature (t_m), the relative mugginess (RM), the measure of wind and precipitation, and sun based radiation. Consequently, any climatic change, for example, an expansion in natural temperature or dry spell pressure, can possibly influence a NCP's exhibition and effect a feed security plan. Since new conidia without added substances are more defenceless to ecological pressure than dried conidial definitions, improving inoculum quality in such a way as to decrease its powerlessness to natural burdens is one approach to build the preharvest adequacy of NCPs. We tracked down that the spans of the two NCP populaces on the outside of peaches that were treated by either the FOR7 or FOR8 conidial plan are a lot higher than those on the surfaces of peaches that were treated with new conidia with no added substances. We likewise tracked down that the size of *E. nigrum* native populace was likewise lower than that of *P. frequentans*. Besides, utilization of both natural definitions consistently expanded the size of the native populace of the parasites

by 100-to 1000-crease on peach surfaces during the harvest season in completely tried plantations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Frequentans and *E. nigrum* are compelling *Bacillus Subtilis* in light of the fact that they can lessen the quantity of *Monilinia* spp. conidia on organic product surfaces. The quantity of *Monilinia* spp. conidia on peach and nectarine natural product surfaces that were treated with either an *E. nigrum* or *P. frequentans* conidial definition, as estimated by the space under the conidial number of *Monilinia* spp. progress bend (AUncMOPC) are fundamentally lower ($p=0.05$) than that found on untreated natural product surfaces. A positive connection between the conidial quantities of *Monilinia* spp. on peach surfaces and the occurrence of inert disease has been accounted for these idle contaminations are additionally identified with the frequency of postharvest earthy colored decay. The quantity of *Monilinia* spp. conidia on non-treated nectarine and peach surfaces increments from blossoming to reap. The quantities of *Monilinia* spp. conidia on natural product surfaces likewise increment quickly during the pit solidifying stage and during the month preceding harvest, and the levels can be just about as high as 103.4–104.5 conidia per organic product surface. The most significant levels of *Monilinia* spp. conidia on the natural product surface are generally found at collect. The littlest *Monilinia* spp. conidial populace was recorded on peach and nectarine natural product surfaces that were treated with a *P. frequentans* conidial definition, trailed by treatment with an *E. nigrum* conidial definition and a fungicide.

CONCLUSION

Organic control of earthy colored decay in stone natural product brought about by *Monilinia* spp. is subject to NCP thickness on the bloom or natural product surface and the RH. One approach to boost the presentation of a parasitic NCP is to create a strong conidial definition. The size of *P. frequentans* populace after a use of a *P. frequentans* conidial plan during the harvest season is greater than that of *E. nigrum* following the utilization of an *E. nigrum* conidial detailing. Additionally, uses of a *P. frequentans* conidial detailing during the harvest season additionally caused a more noteworthy decrease in the quantity of *Monilinia* spp.

conidia on the natural product surface than that found after uses of an *E. nigrum* formulation during the developing season. At long last, the strength of the *E. nigrum* conidial definition is equivalent to that of fungicide.

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PEDAGOGICAL LOAD CONTROL OF SPECIAL ENDURANCE TRAINING IN LONG DISTANCE RUNNING

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ABSTRACT: Muscles are the center of increasing fatigue in the course of distance running [5]. Accordingly, the strength and strength endurance of these muscles are the most important factors of performance in long-distance running [4, 5].

Summarizing the research materials on the physiology of long-distance running, we can conclude that special endurance depends on the maximum muscle strength, the degree of their capillarization and the functional capabilities (power, capacity, efficiency) of the alactate and aerobic systems of intramuscular energy supply [2].

Repeated and interval methods are used to train special endurance in long-distance running. It is known that strong and prolonged muscle acidosis has a negative effect on the tissue respiration system of muscles, and also contributes to a decrease in their maximum strength [3]. Thus, there is a need to control the degree of acidosis when training special endurance.

KEYWORDS: long distance running, special endurance, general endurance, repeated method, interval method, maximum strength measurement.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of the research is to develop a method for an approximate assessment of the degree of muscle acidosis, suitable for use in sports practice of running long distances.

Organization, tasks and research methods. It is known that a decrease in maximum muscle strength correlates positively with the concentration of lactic acid and ADP in the muscles. There is also a negative correlation with the concentration of creatine phosphate

concentration [3]. After the completion of the work, the recovery time of the concentration of creatine phosphate is about 5 minutes, while the main part is restored in the first 2.5 minutes. The utilization time of lactic acid is much longer: 0.5-1.5 hours [3]. Thus, if after 5 min. rest, there is a pronounced decrease in maximum strength, this can be regarded as a sign of muscle acidosis. These considerations formed the basis for the development of a new method for an approximate assessment of the degree of muscle acidosis.

The study was carried out in two stages, during which the following tasks were solved:

1. Develop a method for quantifying maximum strength that meets the specifics of long-distance running.
2. Develop specific recommendations regarding the assessment of the degree of muscle acidosis and appropriate adjustments to the training process.

Research methods. At the first stage, a stating experiment was carried out. The subjects were regularly trained qualified long-distance runners ($n = 20$).

The study participants were asked to undergo tests to measure the maximum load that they are able to perform over a long period of time. The study examined two common running methods in long-distance running: cruising (passive) and active pushing (active), maximum load, a heart rate monitor was used [1].

In this way, the functional state of each qualified long distance runner was measured.

The coefficient of repulsion force was calculated as the average value between the indicators of the right and left legs. Next, the coefficient of the relative repulsive force was calculated (the ratio of the absolute value to the participant's body mass). The final coefficient of the relative push-off force of both legs was calculated as the average value for the coefficients of active and passive running. Further, the correlation dependence (Spearman's correlation coefficient) between various values was determined.

The second stage of the study was based on auto experiment (Vlasenko P.S., MS). First, a series of tests was carried out to determine the maximum load recorded by the heart rate sensor in order to determine the variability of the results shown in the test. 5 measurements were taken for each distance per day. The number of testing days is 10. On the day proceeding the testing day, no training was conducted.

Then a series of tests was carried out - interval methods of running (1000m and 2000m as well as rest between segments) to failure, with an open grip, with a load of 70% and 80% of the maximum (the sum of loads recorded by the heart rate sensor). The maximum load

for each distance was measured before, after, after 2.5 minutes and after 5 minutes after the test. The test was carried out at the beginning, in the middle and at the end of a cycle aimed at training special endurance (cycle duration 6 weeks.).

Results. A high dependence was found between the coefficients of cruising and active, as well as the level of the functional state. The level of the functional state is most strongly correlated with the coefficient of relative strength of the two training methods $R = 0.973$. Correlation coefficient values for the interval method level and coefficients.

Table 1.

Decreased Maximum Strength After Testing

Load level		Work time	After	In 2,5 min.	In 5 min.
80%	Beginning of Cycle (low level of endurance)	42 s	5,7 %	0,7 %	0,9 %
	Middle of Cycle (middle level of endurance)	57 s	7,4 %	0,93 %	1 %
	End of Cycle (high level of endurance)	115 s	9,2 %	3,4 %	1,3 %
70%	Beginning of Cycle (low level of endurance)	108 s	8,18 %	2,8 %	0,81 %
	Middle of Cycle (middle level of endurance)	186 s	11,6 %	3,1 %	0,9 %
	End of Cycle (high level of endurance)	225 s	14,45 %	5,9 %	4,4 %

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The high degree of correlation between the coefficients of the relative running force and the level of the functional state indicates that the proposed test meets the specifics of long-distance running.

After performing the interval training method, a pronounced decrease in maximum strength is observed, which can be recorded using the above method, since significantly exceeds the level of variability of results. The decrease in maximum strength is less pronounced with a shorter duration of work. As endurance increases, there is a regular increase in the time of work at a given level of load, which is accompanied by a more pronounced decrease in maximum strength. If, after five minutes of rest, the indicators do not return to the initial level, this indicates muscle acidosis, and the need to adjust the parameters of the exercise by increasing the intensity in a series of runs (respectively, reducing the duration of work to failure). If there is a decrease in maximum strength at the 5th minute of rest after a series of approaches in the absence of a decrease after a single approach, the duration of the rest interval between approaches should be increased.

This method was used to select training parameters not only when performing interval loads, but also during repeated / interval running in different intensity zones during a long-term auto experiment.

CONCLUSION

1. The proposed method for measuring the maximum strength corresponds to the specifics of long-distance running.

1. Based on the data on the decrease in maximum strength, one can judge (at a qualitative level) the degree of acidosis and adjust the training process accordingly.

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THE PROBLEM OF INTERPRETATION OF THE TERMS “DEFECTOLOGICAL” IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT: In this paper studied interdisciplinary homonyms in defectology terms, analyzed the terms by antonymy and synonymy. There are a number of other terms in defectology, such as agglutination, convergence, divergence, accommodation, contamination, which are also actively used in linguistics, and hence they are using interdisciplinary.

KEYWORDS: Defectology, semantic relations, lexical level, synonym, homonymy, antonymy.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, textbooks and manuals published for higher philological education in Uzbekistan, along with these types of lexical-semantic relations, the concept of hyponymy is described in more detail. For example, in the textbook “Modern Uzbek literary language” by H. Jamolkhanov we read about this concept, in particular, the following concrete and well-founded ideas: The essence of such a relationship is that lexemes that express a narrower concept or meaning are in a relationship of type (hyponym) and gender (hyperonym) with lexemes that express a broader concept or meaning, such a connection is made through unifying (integral) semantics. In the terminological field of the Uzbek language “defectology” hyperonym of defectology combines 5 hyponyms, namely: deaf pedagogy, typhlopedagogy, oligophrenopedagogy, speech therapy, phonopedia, etc. are hyponyms of this hyperonym. Semantically, the semantics of “psychophysiological defect” and “correction of defect” in hyperonyms and “hearing loss” and “correction of hearing loss”, “correction of visual impairment” and “correction of visual impairment”, “mental retardation” and “mental retardation” in hyponyms. “Speech defect” and “speech defect correction”, “voice defect” and “voice defect correction” semaphores serve as unifying semaphores. Hyponyms – the semantics of the terms “hearing”, “sight”, “mental”, “speech” and “voice” in the semantics of the terms

“deaf pedagogy”, “typhlopedagogy”, “oligophreno pedagogy”, “speech therapy”, “phonopedics”.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

As noted, hyponymy occurs on the basis of a hierarchical, more precisely, hierarchical relationship between language units, in particular terms. V. Slozhenikina, who studied the terminology of defectology in Russian twenty years ago under the name “Correctional pedagogical terminology”, described the same hierarchical approach on the basis of concrete examples. He notes that in the terminology of defectology, the structure of the hierarchical relationship between the names of anomalous development (and the semantic paradigm of the names of speech disorders within this structure) is very common. In this case, the terms hyperonym anomalous development, dysontogeny – this is the first level of the classification. At the second level, according to the semaphore of “object of disorder”, the names of special cases of pathological development of the child's personality –ruhiy nuqsonlar, eshitish nuqsonlari, ko‘rish nuqsonlari, nutq nuqsonlari (mental disabilities, hearing impairments, visual impairments, speech defects) and other terms are distinguished. Speech disorders and also at the next level, lexical-semantic group structure distinguishes between oral speech disorders and written speech disorders. The fourth stage of classification involves distinguishing the names of specific cases of oral and written speech disorders, such as units denoting tempningbuzilishi, tembrningbuzilishi, ritmningbuzilishi (tempo disorder, timbre disorder, rhythm disorder) and other aspects of speech activity. In the fifth stage, according to the semantics of “localization of the defect” in the hyponyms of dyslalia, dysarthria, the names of disorders in the pronunciation of sounds are distinguished. The sixth stage is to distinguish the names of the types of dyslalia according to the specific distorted sounds in the child's speech – sigmatism, rotatism, gammatism, etc. In the seventh stage lexemes in the sense of type terms of defects in pronunciation are distinguished [4, p.12]. It should be noted that while the gender-genus hierarchical relationship between terms in the field of “defectology” is manifested, the meaning of the term at the highest level of the hierarchical relationship, i.e. hyperonym, gradually concretizes and complements the hyponymterms as the expression of the corresponding scientific concept falls to the lower level. This, of course, helps to improve the description of the scientific understanding of the terms, to express the essence of the scientific concept clearly and fully in a purposeful detail. Therefore, in the study of the terminological trend of “defectology” in the Uzbek language, special attention should be paid to the manifestation of a

hyponymic relationship. Another important but controversial issue in terminology is synonymy, which is considered a type of lexical-semantic relationship. It is well known that synonymy is usually a unique resource in the vocabulary of any language, a source that expands the expressive potential of the language, increasing its emotional-expressive and aesthetic impact. However, the attitude of researchers to synonymy within the terminological system is not the same. Linguist N. Mahmudov, studying in detail the problems related to the development and principles of terminology in the Uzbek language and the humanities pays special attention to the following aspects: “The issue of synonymy of terms is one of the most controversial issues in terminology. According to the traditional view, the presence of synonyms in the terminological system is assessed as a defect of the terminological system, i.e., a negative condition. But in recent times, the view that terminological synonymy is a positive phenomenon has also been stagnating in terminology. The emergence of synonymy in the terminological system is mainly interpreted as the deepening of existing scientific knowledge, the formation of new scientific paradigms and the serious development of science, interpreted as an integral feature of the terminological system as a phenomenon that expands the capabilities of special language in professional-communicative tasks”[3, p.10]. Researchers note that although the study of the problem of synonymy has been going on since the advent of philology, it has not yet been completed. Therefore, there are many different views on the application of this phenomenon to terminology. It is natural that in the case of the rapid development of science, there is a peculiar “explosion” of synonymy in terminology [5, p. 50]. A number of linguists (such as A.Koval, E.Tolikina) assess synonymy in terminology as a negative phenomenon, while others recognize that the synonymic relationship between terms is natural and appropriate [5, pp.51-53]. Well-known terminologists, for example, V.P.Danilenko, L.L.Kutina and others note that the phenomenon of synonymy in the field of scientific terminology is due to the fact that the existence of terminological systems is at an early stage, the term of their formation has not yet been chosen [1, p.106]. Russian terminologist V.M. Leichik tries to justify the existence of synonyms in any language terminology as a legitimate result of the development of science and the increase in the volume of knowledge about the object of study [2, p. 98-106].

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THE CULTIVATION IN AUSTRIA; ELEVATION OF SULFUR AS AN PREREQUISITE ALIMENTARY ELEMENT

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ABSTRACT: Total sulfur information of different horticultural and food things from the lab of the creator, have been aggregated to foster a comprehension of sulfur elevation and environmental cycling in Austria. As sulfur level is certainly not an included factor among the quality rules of soil and compost synthesis, the information base is fairly little. As a protein segment, sulfur is enhanced in frameworks of creature beginning, specifically in egg white. There is significant discharge from creatures and man by means of pee. Natural manures excrements, fertilizers may contribute altogether to the sulfur spending plan of soils, which is significant for natural cultivating of yields with high sulfur needs. For soils, waste is a primary course of loss of solvent sulphate, consequently pot analyses may yield ridiculous sulfur financial plans.

KEYWORDS: Sulfur; food; feed; grains; excrement; compost

INTRODUCTION

For the worldwide mainland hull, a mean outside worth of 261 mg/kg sulfur has been for the most part acknowledged. Absolute sulfur in soils at 10 test stations in the Czech Republic found the middle value of 221 mg/kg in 1981 territory 134–335 mg/kg, and marginally diminished to 205 mg/kg in 2008 territory 105–321 mg/kg, chiefly due to bring down climatic affidavit. There is no mean sulfur an incentive for soil in Austria, since sulfur has not been remembered for the overall soil stock. Just couple of qualities about water extractable sulfur exist, which are not agent, and rely upon the past wetting-drying conditions. Total sulfur substance isn't met among the quality rules for substances which ought to improve soil quality and soil supplement elevation, similar to compost, soil helps, garden molds and organo-mineral composts, just as for fertilizers and aging deposits. Along these lines, examination of all out sulfur resp. sulfur parts is normally not arranged for routine examples, and very little information are accessible. The information in Table 1 allude to groups every so often examined by the creator.

METHODS

The target of this investigation is to accumulate information of absolute sulfur substance of tests which have been processed with Mg-nitrate to get the all out selenium substance; different condensations may not be reasonable on account of sulfur misfortunes in the drying and ashing steps. The compost tests were submitted either by the specialists, or inside the edge of undertakings of the office of ranchers of the Province of Lower Austria Nö Landesland wirtschafts kammer, to have the degrees of supplements (NPK) and foreign substances decided, primarily in 2003 and 2008, and some in the middle. The metropolitan bio wastes were inspected to screen supplement impurities to acquire consent for reusing to rural zones. The cereal and food tests have been processed for the examination of selenium, and have been taken from an undertaking about selenium soil to plant move in 1999, just as from current food checking since 2008. At a new gathering, the creator understood that all agriculturalists are focussed on nitrogen and phosphorus cycling, and know barely anything about sulfur, like overabundance, speciation, issues of assurance, and so on This article ought to urge leaders to take more consideration about this fundamental component.

CONVERSATION

In readymade dinners for human utilization, sulfur elevation are higher in cheddar and meat-containing suppers. Typically sulfur elevation in food are higher than phosphorus . Factor investigations of all out groupings of non-metals in readymade suppers showed sulfur in a part inverse to boron, while selenium was along with phosphorus and iodine, and silicon was autonomous from the others. Boron fixations are normally fundamentally higher in green plants than in meat, dairy items and cereals, and for sulfur the contrary pattern is hence shown .

CONCLUSION

Contrary to numerous other minor components, sulfur consumption can't be expanded by changing from white bread to wholemeal bread. At the point when tests of 3 Austrian wheat assortments developed at two diverse exploratory locales were processed on a roller factory, sulfur focuses found in the grains and the mineral-improved flour part was not really higher, in spite of most different components researched. This is on the grounds that sulfur isn't contained in the mineral front of the grain, like selenium, boron and iodine . Nectar is for the

most part low in all minor components with the exception of boron. The examples were processed with nitric corrosive, and sulfur is mostly unstable; the given figures are in this way rather an assessment.

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ASSESSMENT OF FERTILIZERS IN SPRINKLED GRAIN: IMPACT ON CEREAL YIELD AT VARIOUS FERTILIZER RATES

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ABSTRACT: Fertilizers are getting progressively well known in numerous nations and for some harvests, however not very many investigations on their impact on cereal yield have been directed in grain. In this way, we assessed three diverse fertilizers in light of Azospirillum, Trichoderma, or unidentified rhizobacteria in the Philippines during four trimming seasons somewhere in the range of 2008 and 2012, utilizing four distinctive manure rates 100% of the suggested rate [SR], half RR, 25% RR, and no compost as Control . The examinations were led under completely flooded conditions in a normal swamp grain climate. Critical yield increments due to bio fertilizer use were seen in all trial seasons except for the 2009/08 DS. Notwithstanding, the impact on grain cereal yield shifted between bio fertilizers, seasons, and manure medicines. In relative terms, the occasional yield increment across compost medicines was somewhere in the range of 6% and 18% for the best bio fertilizer Azospirillum-based , however went up to 25% in singular medicines. Total cereal yield increments due to bio fertilizer were normally underneath $0.6 \text{ t} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1}$, comparing to an expected extra N take-up of under 7.6 kg N ha^{-1} . The bio fertilizer impact on yield didn't altogether connect with the inorganic manure rate utilized yet the best consequences for cereal yield were accomplished at low to medium compost rates.

KEYWORDS: Azospirillum; bio fertilizer; cereal yield; inorganic manure; PDAR; plant development advancing rhizobacteria; grain; Trichoderma.

INTRODUCTION

Fertilizers are getting progressively famous in numerous nations and for some yields. They are characterized as items containing dynamic or inactive strains of soil microorganisms, either microscopic organisms alone or in mix with green growth or parasites that increment the plant accessibility and take-up of mineral supplements . When all is said in done, they contain

free-living life forms related with root surfaces however they may likewise incorporate entophytes, microorganisms that can colonize the intercellular or even intracellular spaces of plant tissues without making clear harm the host plant. The idea of fertilizers was created dependent on the perception that these microorganisms can beneficially affect plant and harvest development . Subsequently, a scope of plant development advancing rhizobacteria (PDAR) has been distinguished and very much described. Direct advantageous impacts can happen when the microorganisms furnish the plants with valuable items. The most popular instance of this are microorganisms that can straightforwardly acquire N from the environment and convert this into natural structures usable by plants. Such natural nitrogen fixers (NNF) incorporate individuals from the class Rhizobium, Azospirillum, and blue green growth. Rhizobia are advantageously connected with vegetables and nitrogen obsession happens inside root or stem knobs where the bacterium lives . The class Azospirillum additionally has a few N-fixing animal varieties, which are rhizobacteria related with monocots and dicots like grasses, wheat, maize and Brassica chinensis L. .Azospirillum strains have been secluded from grain over and over again, and as of late the strain Azospirillum sp. B510 has been sequenced . Impressive N obsession by Azotobacter spp. furthermore, Azospirillum spp. in the grain crop rhizosphere was accounted for over and over , however others addressed such high measures of non-cooperative N obsession in farming.

METHODS

Site Description The analyses were directed during two dry seasons (DS) and two wet seasons (WS). In the 2008/09 DS and the 2009 WS, an exploratory site at the Central Experimental Station of the University of the Philippines at Los Baños CES-UPLB was utilized, though the test in the 2010 WS and the 2010/11 DS was led at the Experimental Station of the International rice Research Institute IRRr in Los Baños ES-IRRI. Both exploratory locales were situated in close area around 1 km separated in Laguna Province, Philippines 14°11' North, 121°15' East, 21 masl , in an average marsh grain creation territory with the predominant soil type "anthraquic Gleysols" . Definite soil attributes were broke down just for the field at ES-IRRI Table 1 yet the dirt at CES-UPLB was comparable. The dirt at the two destinations had a fine surface clayey topsoil and a high cation trade limit (CTL). Dirt pH esteems at CTL-UPLB in the 2009 DS and WS were 6.9 and 6.8, separately, while pH upsides of 6.9 2010 WS and 6.5 2012 DS were seen at the ES-IRRI site. The dirt natural carbon focuses at the two ranches were generally high,

going somewhere in the range of 1.5% and 1.9%. Identified with this, natural N fixations were additionally high at the two homesteads (0.15–0.27%). The high soil natural matter substance likewise caused high P accessibility as demonstrated by high Olsen P esteems, which were far over the basic low degree of 10–15 mg • kg⁻¹.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In each of the four seasons and across the bio fertilizer medicines, cereal yield expanded with expanding measures of applied manure. Notwithstanding, this increment was not in every case measurably huge and the yield increment changed extensively between seasons. By and large, the least cereal yields happened in the 2009 WS, going just from 1.9 to 2.7 t • ha⁻¹. For the most part, low yields in that season were because of a hurricane that caused impressive harm through flooding of the test field and housing of the harvest. Thus, the yield was collected rashly by around multi week, which further diminished achievable yields.

CONCLUSION

The examination was led to assess the impact of various fertilizers on the cereal yield of swamp grain, and research conceivable collaboration impacts with various inorganic compost sums. The outcomes showed critical yield increments for all items tried in certain seasons however the most predictable outcomes were accomplished by the Azospirillum-based bio fertilizer. As a rule, the noticed cereal yield increments were not gigantic (0.2 to 0.5 t • ha⁻¹) yet could turn out generous revenue acquires given the moderately low expenses of all fertilizers tried. The constructive outcome of the tried fertilizers was not restricted to low paces of inorganic manures and some impact was as yet seen at cereal yields up to 5 t • ha⁻¹. Notwithstanding, the patterns in our outcomes appear to demonstrate that the utilization of fertilizers may be generally useful in low-to medium-input frameworks. The outcomes accomplished would already be able to be utilized to foster better guidance for ranchers on bio fertilizer use in swamp grain, however a few significant inquiries remain. Specifically, fertilizers should be assessed under conditions with abiotic stresses average for generally low-to medium-input frameworks and with a scope of germplasm in light of the fact that their impact may rely likewise upon the assortment utilized. All the more upstream-arranged exploration would be expected to all the more likely comprehend the real instruments included, which thus could likewise add to utilizing fertilizers in grain-based frameworks.

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PRINCIPLES OF LINGVOKULTUROLOGICAL PROPERTIES IN TRANSLATION OF IMAGES

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ABSTRACT: In world linguistics, the scope of research on lingvoculturology, lingvopoetics and textology has been growing day by day in recent decades. It is known that the language of any nation, during its historical development, reflects the social process and changes in the life of that nation. In this sense, the study of the linguistic landscape of the world is a "comprehensive analysis of the living space, lifestyle, mental characteristics and national-cultural character of peoples, the principles of ethno-cultural ethics, social relations, interethnic dialogue, ethical and cultural norms of behavior." [1. 5] it also provides an opportunity to learn. In this respect, the emergence and development of works in the field of linguocultural studies is extremely important, but also provides very interesting linguistic materials for the theory of language. Sources related to linguoculturology mention lingvocultures as one of its main concepts.

KEYWORDS: Reality, paremeological unity, national-cultural, lacunae, linguoculturology, nosrang, moshrang.

INTRODUCTION

According to experts, the term was first used by V.V Vorobev in his works. "Linguoculture as a complex inter-level term reflects the dialectical integrity of linguistic and non-linguistic content. If a particular word is considered as a linguistic unit and is interpreted within the context of language, lingvokulturema manifests itself in the integral connection of a particular thing-event or action-situation with culture. Linguocultures, along with a purely linguistic understanding of a particular thing-event, incorporate linguistic units that reflect non-linguistic factors in constant motion, such as reality, paremeological unity, and national-cultural features such as lacunae. Existing research includes words, phraseological units, phrases, sentences, paremeological units, speech clichés, complex syntactic integrity, and text that reflect one or another aspect of culture. Thus, lingvokulturema is a unit that is specific to a

particular nation, encompasses linguistic and non-linguistic factors, expresses the interdependence of language and culture, and can be manifested by all means of language. It can consist of a single word (for example, wedding, soup), a compound word (for example, a teapot), a whole paragraph or a text.”[2. 10-11]

In world linguistics, the language of a work of art is studied in different aspects, and approaches take different forms accordingly. According to the sources: “study of lexical-methodological, linguocultural and lingvopoetic features of the language of the work of art; study of emotional-expressive lexicon of artistic speech; analysis of the peculiarities of the language of a particular folk art literature; to study the stylistic features of words typical of different speech styles found in works of art; determining the level of artistic means of artistic expression of visual means; revealing creative skills through linguopoetic analysis of literary texts ”[3. 6]. “In order to accurately and completely reflect linguocultures in translation, it is very important for native speakers to have a correct understanding of the linguistic understanding of the world. The uniqueness of each nation's style of linguistic understanding of the world is explained by the fact that it reflects the individual, public and national activities and experiences [2. 13].”

THE MAIN FINDING AND RESULTS

As the linguist N.Mahmudov noted, “Language reflects the way of thinking and national identity of the people, way of life and millennial traditions, in short, the inner and outer existence of the people. Therefore, it is natural that if a certain concept exists in one nation, it will not exist at all in another. In such cases, a concept that is specific to one people and can be expressed in one word can be expressed in another language, in a few words. ” The scientific study of those cases is now being conducted by linguoculturology, or linguistics, in a form adapted to our language. Comparative linguistics, a branch of linguistics, also plays an important role in comparative linguistics. The reason is related to the nature of science: “... if the linguistic landscape of the world contains universal historical experience, the national linguistic landscape of the world reflects the experience of a particular society, as well as the national and cultural peculiarities of the same people [4. 14].” As mentioned, words and phrases related to color are also perceived, along with the units that can be expressed by all means of language, expressing the interdependence of language and culture, covering linguistic and non-linguistic factors specific to a particular people. Because “language development is connected with the history, values and national culture of the people. In the linguistic landscape of the

world, along with reality, its signs are also reflected. Also, in a linguistic landscape, an event is represented by certain symbols. In the semantics of sign lexemes in different languages, along with the universal depiction of the world landscape, there is also a mental expression defined by national-cultural features. While universals are defined by universal parameters of understanding the world, mental characteristics are realized on the basis of ethnic characteristics, lifestyles, customs, traditions, national values of language speakers [5. 22].”

For example, the great poet, thinker, statesman, Yusuf Khos Hajib in the famous epic “Qutadg’u bilig” “Сўз бўз ерга яшил кўқдан тушди...” In the Turkish translation of this “Söz boz toprağa mavi gökten indi / The word descended from the blue sky to the gray ground” translated as. Because in Turkish linguoculture, the sky is blue, not green. Even in Kyrgyz, which is a close Turkish language “Сөз көк асмандан боз жерге түштү” translated as [6]. Because in almost all Turkic peoples the color blue is used as a standard for the color of the sky. In similar cases, each language appears to be unique, even though it belongs to the same family. In addition, the linguistic difference is also very evident in the color names. For example, when color names such as brown, nosrang, moshrang are translated into another language, the peculiarity of Uzbek linguoculture disappears. Because other nations perceive the name of color, which for us is associated with liver, nas, and mosh, with other associative units.

In this regard, trying to keep the visual aids in translation is one of the biggest problems.

Visual aids in Turkish TV series, such as "olive-eyed", "slap with the back of the hand", "a new habit in the old village", "find a pot with a lid", are easily used in the Uzbek translation. But this is wrong. Because ideograms, the literal translation of stereotyped units is detrimental to the development of the national language of translation as well as the incompetence of the translator. For the Turkish people, the blackness of the eye is represented by olive, while the Uzbeks express it clearly and effectively through the word charos. Uzbeks do not slap, slap, or use the Turkish phrase "push with their own hands." It is as if the old village and the new habit are Uzbek. However, the Uzbeks do not unite them in this way. Therefore, the content that is meant by the phrase is not fully understood. This phrase is in line with Uzbek linguoculture when it is used in terms of "inventing something on one's own" and "inventing something new." Rounding the lid on the pot is also not in line with the Uzbek imagination. This is also based on a specific situation in Turkish fairy tales and parables. In order for Uzbeks to understand that

proverb or phrase, they need to understand the leitmotif in it. That is, he must be aware of the tale or event on which that phrase is based.

CONCLUSION

Whether the simulation devices are devices, metaphors, metonymy, rhetoric, or other translations, the way in which the text-created language owners understand the world in the translation of each will need to be studied in depth. And at the same time it is necessary to have a good knowledge of the subtleties, logical and methodological bases of the translated language.

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DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIFRUSTRATION SKILLS IN FUTURE SPECIFIC TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the development of antifrustration skills of future science teachers through person-centered education as a pedagogical problem.

KEYWORDS: Antifrustration, character, methodology, national values, religious values.

INTRODUCTION

According to socio-historical and pedagogical and psychological analyzes, the development of antifrustration skills of future science teachers through person-centered education is a multifaceted and comprehensive concept that has come a long way in social development. The path, stages of development of human society, human life and activity can not be imagined without the character traits of the individual. Perhaps antifrustration or its properties in the early stages are inextricably linked with the appearance, formation, development, in other words, the influence of living conditions and the satisfaction of human spiritual needs. The increase in knowledge and experience in human beings has led to changes in lifestyles, the improvement of relationships, which in turn have led to the development and perfection of character traits. During the socio-historical development, the struggle of people for survival, the study of the being that surrounds man, the expansion of the types of production allow for the multifaceted formation and development of personality traits. In any natural, social environment, in all spheres of society, the positive features of human character continue to improve, develop and strengthen under the influence of repetition and repetition in people's daily lives, ending activities with positive results. The development of science, as well as the fact that all processes in existence are changing, has also led to the radical evolutionary reconstruction of future science teachers through the development of antifrustration skills

through person-centered education. Social, pedagogical relations in any system are constantly revealing new aspects of human character traits.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Regardless of the analysis of any field at the present time, its rise cannot be imagined without the formation of new aspects of the antifrustration character in humans. For the same reason, many branches of pedagogical science are engaged in the study of the formation of human character traits, development processes, laws and pedagogical mechanisms, and today this field has become their most important object of research. In particular, the development of antifrustration skills of future science teachers through person-centered education is becoming one of the most pressing issues today as a pedagogical problem. In this regard, in our article we have analyzed the future specific science teachers as a pedagogical-psychological problem of developing antifrustration skills through person-centered education. Commenting on the study of antifrustration skills in the science of foreign psychology, we see that educators often conduct research in two areas: those who interpret the term frustration and those who deny frustration and those who interpret the term personality. When we analyze the study of character in the pedagogy of the former Soviet Union, we see that educators pay special attention to methodological problems, especially the need for its formation, history, developmental laws, features, consequences, physiological basis. As a confirmation of our opinion, it can be said that several scientific studies have been conducted in the early stages of the study of the problem of frustration. Also in the psychology of the former Soviet Union, the areas of research on the scientific basis of the development of antifrustration skills through the person-centered education of future science teachers in the educational process will play a leading role.

CONCLUSION

The development of antifrustration skills of future science teachers of our country through person-centered education is always considered a priority of educational development. From a logical point of view, we consider it expedient to approach the solution of this problem in the following order: Uzbek folklore, unique sources reflecting our national and religious values, the formation of human character and its importance in Uzbek folk pedagogy and psychology. The solution of the problem of developing the positive qualities of human personality and character in the teachings of our great ancestors. The level of study of the problem of formation of character and its features in the pedagogy of our country, etc. Sources

related to the formation and development of human character in our country, their valuable advice, advice, vital analysis, conclusions and recommendations are still important in the field of its scientific composition, development and achievement of goals and objectives.

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WAYS TO DEVELOP INDIVIDUAL CREATIVITY THROUGH VERTICAL INTEGRATION OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER TECHNICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the ways of developing individual creativity through vertical integration of students of higher technical education through the organization of independent learning.

KEYWORDS: independent learning, creativity, ability, integration, theory, practice.

INTRODUCTION

The policy documents of the higher education system reform aim to ensure the training of competitive personnel. The new generation of young people must have the ability to ask and solve problems of the future, a high culture of thinking, the ability to find an independent path in political and social life. Changes and innovations in the system of technical higher education of the Republic, along with providing students of higher technical education with new knowledge, skills and abilities, change the attitude of our youth to themselves and other people, society, state, nature, inculcate patriotic ideas in the minds and hearts and develop creativity. implies This means that the activities of our higher technical education institutions should be aimed at the formation of our students in a democratic society as independent-minded, spiritually mature individuals with their own worldview. At present, new pedagogical technologies are widely used in the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in various disciplines taught in higher technical education. Special attention is paid to the active participation of students in the lessons, their understanding of the subject, the ability to apply their knowledge in practice and the development of independent and creative thinking skills. In order to develop the creative thinking skills of students of higher technical education, it is important for them to independently master some of the subjects assigned to them. This article recommends one of the ways to organize the student's independent work in the subjects taught to students of higher technical education. Let the subject of a practical study of Kirchhoff's laws for the

calculation of constant current circuits be given as a student's independent work. In this case, the student's independent work can be organized as follows:

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

For theoretical study of the topic of independent work the student is given a textbook, manual and a list of special literature. Using these references, the student learns the definition and mathematical expression of Kirchhoff's first and second laws, and discusses how the laws can be examined in a practical context. The student draws circuit diagrams to check that Kirchhoff's first and second laws are fulfilled. At the same time, the student makes the necessary changes to the circuit diagrams to use the necessary electrical measuring instruments and equipment in the laboratory. In other words, the student will have to draw up an electrical circuit diagram taking into account the technical capabilities of the laboratory room. The student shows the teacher the circuit diagrams he or she has drawn. The teacher gives her opinion on whether it is right or wrong. In this case, the student must be able to independently identify shortcomings in the scheme and eliminate them.

To verify Kirchhoff's first and second laws, the circuit diagrams found to be correct are assembled by the student in turn using laboratory equipment. These circuits are checked by the instructor before connecting to an uninterruptible power supply and are connected after being allowed to connect to the mains. Necessary measurements are made and measurement results are obtained.

CONCLUSION

Conclusions are made based on the measurement results. 6. A report on the work done by the student on the topic of independent work. The report describes the theoretical part of the topic of independent work and its accuracy is substantiated using the results of the measurements performed. The student's performance in independent work is monitored by the teacher. The teacher can help the student to work creatively, to direct him to independent thinking. Such organization of independent work of students meets the requirements of the regulations on independent education, enhances the student's ability to think independently, to understand the essence of the problem and to solve creatively.

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AN INVESTIGATIVE EXPLANATION OF PARADIGMATIC MODEL OF BOUSSINQ'S COMPARISON IN COMPARABLE POROUS MEDIA DURING INFILTRATION OF GROUNDWATER FLOW

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ABSTRACT: The current paper talks about with the issue of groundwater given by Boussinesq's condition invasion marvel in unsaturated permeable media. The administering nonlinear incomplete differential condition is addressed utilizing ideal homotopy investigation technique. The arrangement gives a stature of free surface of penetrated water table in unsaturated comparable permeable media (soil) by utilizing suitable starting conjecture worth of the arrangement. The mathematical just as graphical portrayal of the arrangement is given by Mathematic coding.

KEYWORDS: Boussinesq's condition; unsaturated permeable media; ideal homotopy examination strategy; intermingling control boundary; groundwater stream.

INTRODUCTION

The groundwater stream assumes a significant part in different fields like liquid elements, farming, ecological issues, synthetic designing, atomic garbage removal issues and bio science. The penetration marvel is valuable to farming reason, pollution of water and to control saltiness of water. Such kinds of issues are additionally helpful to gauge dampness substance of water in vertical one-dimensional ground water re-energize. A restricted spring is spring limited from a higher place and from underneath by impenetrable arrangements, while unconfined spring is limited above by water table. Penetration is measure in that groundwater travels through the pores of an unsaturated permeable medium (soil). It is represented by basically two powers, gravity and hair like activity. The current model was grown first by Boussinesq in 1903 and is identified with a unique inspiration of Darcy . The present numerical model arrangements with the filtration of an incompressible liquid normally water through a permeable layer, the primary issue in groundwater penetration.

METHODS

The current paper talks about the surmised logical arrangement of nonlinear fractional differential condition for a penetration wonder, to inspect the stature of the free surface of the water table in unsaturated comparable soil. The progressions in soaked permeable media and conveyance of pore pressing factors can be determined by utilizing the ideal homotopy investigation technique.

CONCLUSION

The condition addresses a stature of penetrated groundwater for any distance X and time $T > 0$. Utilizing ideal homotopy examination strategy, the ideal worth of assembly control boundary $c_0 = 0.01157372330371058$ is effectively gotten by limiting the square remaining blunder. Figure 3 addresses the tallness H for penetrated groundwater versus distance X and time T ; it shows that tallness of penetrated groundwater is diminishing as distance X expanding for fix time level T . From figure 3, it tends to be inferred that for invasion of groundwater is diminishing as distance X expanding and when time T expanding. Subsequently, the arrangement of one-dimensional Boussinq's condition by ideal homotopy investigation technique is graphically just as genuinely predictable. At long last, we can reasoned that the penetration pace of groundwater is diminishing with distance X , just as time T , builds utilizing ideal homotopy examination technique.

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TECHNOLOGY OF FORMATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE OF SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: On the basis of an integrative approach, the technology of formation of physical culture of students and the idea of strengthening health, improving physical fitness, reducing morbidity were discussed.

KEYWORDS: Integrative approach, activity, physiology, sports, exercise.

INTRODUCTION

Reforms in the education system and the development of the education system on the basis of modern requirements require an integrated approach. Further increase of physical activity in students, along with the development of physical culture, the use of various integrations of disciplines is one of the important technologies in the development of education and upbringing. Therefore, it is important to use an integrated approach to increase the effectiveness of physical education and labor lessons in schoolchildren. With the above in mind, increasing the integration of physical education and labor lessons with increasing student physical activity is one of the most pressing issues today.

One of the main tasks of physical education of school-age students is to strengthen their health, improve physical fitness, reduce morbidity. The need for movement is a necessary biological need and an important factor in the growth and development of the learner's body. Movement determines a student's functional capabilities and ability to do work.

Increasing motor activity helps to activate all the basic physiological functions of the body, increases the activity of the vascular and respiratory systems, increases metabolism. Promotes active muscle activity and the development of skeletal muscle and joint apparatus. Improves coordination of movements. Improves the functions of the central nervous system. Exercise, running, jumping, and working outdoors throughout the year are especially important

in increasing students' respiratory activity. Such trainings in many ways help to strengthen the health of the student's body, to realize the resistance to colds.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

According to the data obtained by O.Sinina, students engaged in physical training and cocktails in the open air suffered from colds 2-3 times less than their peers.

Hence, it is necessary to further improve labor lessons, physical education and sports. This should be based on a review of its purpose, content, and organization. Physical education of school-age students - taking advantage of health opportunities, should be applied in every school institution on the basis of physiologically correctly selected means, forms and methods of physical education, taking into account the age and sexual characteristics of students, physical education of students is not an easy task. In modern conditions, the vital need for movement in children and adolescents is not great. School-age students spend a lot of time in front of the TV and computer, as well as drawing, completing assignments, listening to different stories, and so on.

For a long time, movement games and playful exercises will remain the activities that students enjoy the most. This allows the training to take the form of fun and unusual games. It is known from our scientific research that well-chosen and properly structured play exercises aimed at developing physical qualities have a beneficial effect on the physical development of students. These include plot exercises such as Walking in the Garden, Runner and Jumper, All-Knowing, and similar playful exercises.

The future man must have laid the foundation of physical culture, and they include:

- Emotional-positive attitude of students to physical exercises and games, the impact of the forces of nature, the rules of personal hygiene, adherence to the agenda;
- elementary school of natural movements with general developmental characteristics, basics of musical-rhythmic knowledge, posture, ability to behave around, participation in group actions (games, dances, celebrations), demonstration of behavioral culture, independence, organization, discipline;
- ўз-ўзига хизмат кўрсатиш ва машғулотлар учун ускуна, мосламалардан фойдаланиш кўникмалари.

- In summary, the role and place of increasing physical activity in primary school students in the performance of the following basic tasks of physical education is extremely important:
- Strengthen health, help students develop and thrive properly.
- To provide students with specialized knowledge of physical culture and sports, to instill in them hygienic knowledge, skills and competencies.
- Forming and improving movement skills and competencies in students, teaching new types of movement and movement activities.
- Development of age-appropriate movement qualities (strength, speed, agility, endurance, etc.).
- Fostering courage, perseverance, discipline, teamwork, a sense of friendship, cultural behavioral skills, attitude to work.
- Develop the ability to hold the body correctly while standing and walking.
- Fostering a sustained interest and skills in regular physical education and sports.
- To inculcate organizational skills in students, to train public physical culture activists.

CONCLUSION

This work should be aimed at further intensifying the process of teaching students physical movements. Especially in the context of the regions of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take an integrated approach to the physical education of students - an unconventional approach that goes beyond the usual assumptions, a special approach to the formation of a healthy person from school age.

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INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES - AS A FACTOR OF QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the opportunities to increase the effectiveness of educational work, the scientific organization of activities and the widespread use of modern teaching technologies, the factors of achieving quality and effectiveness in education through pedagogical innovations.

KEYWORDS: Educational process, innovative technologies, educator, student, creative thinking, creativity, interactive methods, knowledge, skills and abilities.

INTRODUCTION

Integration and cooperation between the participants of the educational process will be ensured through open access to innovations and large-scale organization of innovative activities in educational institutions. Actions such as planning, design, programming, forecasting and evaluation should not be overlooked. Through pedagogical innovations, opportunities for quality and efficiency in education and upbringing are increased.

The winged phrase of the great German pedagogue Adolf Disterveg, who lived and worked in the 18th century, is still relevant today: "Noshud teacher simply tells the truth, and the best is to teach him how to find it." Learners should be approached not as information-receiving robots, but as objects of learning as free and creative thinkers, seekers, and innovators. Another well-known Russian pedagogue and storyteller, Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky, said: "Students are torches that must be lit, not containers that need to be filled." In the words of another great thinker, the author of the unique work "Shohnama" Abulqasim Firdavsi, "Whoever does not receive education from life, no teacher can teach him." Without discriminating against the services of teachers and tutors, it should be noted that the first

teacher and educator of the human child is his parents. Family upbringing is the cornerstone of perfection.

The concept of "innovative technology" includes ways to improve the acquisition of knowledge through the use of factors that increase the effectiveness of education, the design and implementation of various pedagogical processes. "Innovative technologies" means the management of the process of creating, adopting, evaluating, mastering and implementing various pedagogical innovations. The conditions and opportunities created in educational institutions in recent years, a creative and adaptive approach to the introduction of innovative models, effectively serve to strengthen the creative activity of teachers and students.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Today, the interest and attention to the use of innovative technologies in the system of continuing education is growing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that while so far the educational goals have been to teach students only ready-made knowledge, modern technology has taught them to be creative, to search for the knowledge they need, and even to draw their own conclusions.

The main form of organizing the teaching process is the lesson. At present, various non-traditional forms of teaching are being introduced. Such lessons serve to develop the student's creative ability, strengthen his mental capacity, broaden his scientific outlook, and develop his skills and abilities to be able to absorb every innovation quickly and fully. The use of innovative technologies in the classroom arouses students' interest in scientific research, develops creativity and ingenuity. As a result, the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are applied in practice, the quality of mastering increases. To do this, the teacher must be skilled and plan the lesson correctly depending on the content of the topics, to ensure that all students work actively and consciously during the lesson. After all, the teacher is the main executor of educational reform. At the same time, it is important to train every teacher to master, process and apply a large amount of information in a short period of time. In solving it, the teacher is assisted by the use of modern information technologies, including computers, along with traditional methods of teaching. The use of computers in the classroom allows for an interesting learning process, an individual approach to each student. At the same time, first of all, through the wide range of information and communication technologies, it will be possible to provide

students with a lot of knowledge, facts and information. Second, the full implementation of the teacher's innovative plan, ideas and thoughts is easy and effective.

Thus, innovative activity turns the student and the teacher into partners in the educational process. Ensures that the lesson is fun and productive. In determining the effectiveness of innovations, it is necessary to think based on the results of students' mastery of the basics of science. At present, information and communication tools are widely used in the acquisition of knowledge by students. In particular, working on a computer, searching for and mastering the necessary information from various networks is becoming an interesting activity for students. Only in this case, computer literacy is required to be perfect. It is also an innovative activity that requires students to acquire specific knowledge, skills and competencies.

Informatics and information technology are taught as a subject in all areas and specialties of educational institutions. These lessons have become the most interesting lessons for the students. In addition to teaching students computer skills and competencies, it would be good if they also developed a culture in this area. Some students are more interested in playing games, fighting, and enjoying "popular culture" than learning. Directing innovations in the computer network for quality and effective education should be the focus of the teaching staff.

Pedagogical innovations will be focused on serving to solve a certain number of tasks. If a student has solid knowledge and skills to apply it in practice, to be effective in experiments, to change the current situation for the better, to work on new ideas, to think of a solution to any problem, to think on a global scale, to innovate. will give a folated result. Similarly, pedagogical innovations solve the task of educating a comprehensively developed, harmoniously developed generation.

Usually students don't like being monotonous, being a passive listener, being obedient performer, being dependent on someone's opinion (even if it's helpful). Diversity in the educational process, independence, consciousness, activism, free and creative thinking, self-expression, awareness of innovations in science and the desire to create innovation are becoming a way of life for students. It has been found that the most effective way to solve these problems is through innovative technologies.

The achievements of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence are important social events. Extensive use of innovative educational technologies is required to understand their essence, to fully master them and to analyze them in an active life position. Innovative approaches are needed to fully reflect the social, political, spiritual, cultural,

enlightenment and economic changes taking place in society today, when traditional teaching methods are giving way to modern educational technologies. In order to bring success and problems in all areas to the attention of young people, educators must be able to analyze these issues at the level of modern requirements and live and work in step with all the changes in the social life of our country.

In a continuing education system, each course must have its own innovative goal. In order to achieve the innovative goal, the teacher himself must be sufficiently armed and ready to act in such a process.

CONCLUSION

We believe that one of the main tasks of ensuring continuity and continuity in the system of continuing education is not only to train students and trainees on the basis of innovative technologies, but also to teach them the successful use of innovative technologies in their future practice.

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FACTORS FOR FORMATION OF HYGIENIC CULTURE OF THE MODERN ISLAMIC FAMILY IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the factors that shape the hygienic culture of the modern Islamic family of students. Students discuss the development of a young family hygienic culture in the birth of a healthy offspring and the upbringing of a healthy generation.

KEYWORDS: Islamic family, Islamic religion, healthy living, hygienic culture, reproductive health.

INTRODUCTION

A responsible approach to the process of preparing students for family life is a requirement of today, and the work in this direction should be carried out systematically and consistently, including the Women's Committee, "Family" Research and Practice Center, "Mahalla" and "Healthy Generation", "Religious Affairs". It is necessary to strengthen cooperation between the Committee and other organizations. In order to prepare young people for family life in higher education institutions and increase the hygienic, Islamic rules, social and legal knowledge of young families, the establishment of "Young Family", modern Islamic family hygienic culture schools and regular monitoring of their activities give good results.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

It is expedient to study the economic situation of young families, to improve the system of financial support for low-income families, to attract sponsors to provide financial support for weddings of children from low-income families.

Also

- Formation of a modern healthy family based on Islamic traditions in the minds of students, development of measures to improve the reproductive health system based on Islamic practices.

- Promoting healthy lifestyles, the importance of premarital health check-ups, and Islamic and hadith-related hygiene awareness among student families to prevent infertility, birth defects, maternal or infant mortality;
- In-depth specialized medical examination and rehabilitation of high school students of academic lyceums, technical schools and vocational colleges to develop a hygienic culture of students, to form a healthy generation and a healthy family in the future, to pass the results of medical examinations to parents.
- In order to prevent the establishment of sharia marriages and paternity, the organization of mobile registration of marriages of young people once a month in the mahallas far from the bodies of the Civil Registry Office;

The Republican Center for Reproductive Health, together with all medical workers, the Republican Women's Committee, the Funds for Healthy Generation, Mahalla, the Committee for Religious Affairs and other public organizations should further improve their activities.

It is necessary to establish a social partnership between government agencies and the Committee on Religious Affairs in promoting the formation of a healthy family.

The role of the Kamolot youth social movement is also important in this regard. The movement faces the following goals in this regard. These are:

- Development and implementation of effective and acceptable methods of spiritual and educational work aimed at improving the legal, medical, physical, hygienic and spiritual culture of young families;
- Establishment of legal, medical, psychological, hygienic centers for young families;
- Carrying out explanatory and propaganda work aimed at increasing the responsibility of young families for the birth of a healthy offspring and the upbringing of a healthy generation;
- Organization of special training courses aimed at forming a culture of healthy living of young families;
- Preparation of methodological manuals and booklets, popular science brochures and explanatory work on the hygienic problems of the modern Islamic family and their solutions;

- Develop an implementation mechanism and procedure for the Action Systems to promote and encourage the formation of a healthy family among young people.
- Study the Qur'an, the hadiths that are the moral foundation of Islam;
- preparing children for marriage, sex education, husband and wife duties;
- acquisition of medical knowledge, observance of personal hygiene, attention to the sanitary condition of the house, household appliances, knowledge of first aid, study of folk medicine;
- education of the soul, the need to have a norm in everything: food, clothing, morality;

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ABSORPTION OF DISPOSITION IN ARCHAIC INDIAN CRAFT AND ITS COMMUNAL PURPOSE

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ABSTRACT: This article attempts to clarify the perspective as contained in the old Indian craftsmanship where disposition and human life are so weaved with one another that they become the fundamental piece of the other and this comprehensiveness gets back the point that they are not totally unrelated as is considered in present day times. Old Indian craftsmanship represents this coordinated methodology and one may discover the absorption of disposition in each structure considered and portrayed in that.

KEYWORDS: Prakṛti, pañca-tattva, disposition, Gaṅgā-Yamunā, Indian workmanship.

INTRODUCTION

Disposition for example Prakṛti is inescapable and supreme and, thus, Indian religion and reasoning from the Vedic occasions, discussed the disposition and its significance Agrawal, V.S. 1964: 1-29; Ray: 1975. The vegetation alongside water, fire, earth, sky and wind pañca tattva—five antiquated components involve a generous and incorporated sampṛkta place in the complete plenty of Indian Craft Coomaraswamy, A.K. 1996: 1-29 . Truth be told, Indian workmanship is by all accounts the incorporated visual appearance of human and non-human instinct structures. Our antiquated sacred writings are brimming with such references which show not just the significance of earth, tree, water, creature, plant for our endurance yet in addition make them holy objects of love. Their holiness and, along these lines, respect in the psyche and he craft of individuals, normally prevented them from making any harm the Disposition and furthermore supported them for its safeguarding for the endurance and food of the whole humankind

DISCUSSION

In an uncommon outside huge stone cut board at Mahābalipuram Tamilnadu , I could see both the sign of time and presence of disposition. This splendid Gaṅgāvataṛaṇa board of Pallava period is datable to seventh century CE Sivaramamurti, C. 1995: 24-28 . In the focal point of the bluff there is a hole showing nāga figures which are streaming lower to recommend plunge of Gaṅgā on the earth. On ground level, on its correct bank two figures are appeared of which one is conveying water-pitcher kalaśa having Gaṅgā jala while other one is crushing water from his long hair in the wake of scrubbing down in the Gaṅgā. Notwithstanding, two other male figures are appeared in two changed offers of Sūrya namaskāra. One is in namaskāra mudrā while the other one is having both the hands being raised over the head with open palms confronting sky and their fingers contacting one another. These figures unmistakably recommend that this Gaṅgāvataṛaṇa board addresses the typical strict exercises on the bank of Gaṅgā toward the beginning of the day hours. It has additionally normal renderings of the figures of elephants in bunch with infant elephants , deer and tiger to give sway befitting the event of retribution of Bhagīrath and plummet of Gaṅgā on the earth—Gaṅgāvataṛaṇa

CONCLUSION

Indian workmanship, along these lines, in the entirety of its size and indications has consistently been eco-accommodating assimilating the components of disposition verdure and fauna for giving explicit significance and personality to the structures in models/symbols. Additionally, disposition has consistently embellished the models and given important scenery. We may take a gander at the plenty of Indian Craft from the view point that it addresses the life and thought about the past to fill in as the ideal model for the present and, thusly, all such visual models become important for us all today. Indian workmanship totally gives lasting directive for us all today to live with disposition and become eco-accommodating to guarantee our own reality.

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PROBABILITY OF SPIRITUALITY: A SITUATION OF INDIAN AGNOSTICISM

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, I will investigate secularism, as it is utilized in the west and furthermore in India. In the west, agnosticism is found to have been started as a solid remedy against sacerdotal authoritative opinions, biases and hostile to social notion. Indian secularism, in contrast to the west, obviously, doesn't have confidence in supreme division among spirituality and State. Indian agnosticism rather keeps a principled distance of the State from strict foundations to get a satisfactory insignificant way of life and to turn away horrendous sufferings for the standard residents. However, the inquiry emerges: Why must spirituality be isolated from the State? Is detachment among spirituality and the State the solitary feasible arrangement? My conflict will be that there will not be supreme partition among spirituality and the State.

KEYWORDS: Spirituality, state, governmental issues, resistance, human qualities.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'secularism' has its starting point in Europe. It is first utilized toward the finish of the Thirty years' conflict in 1648, where there is an exchange of properties of the congregation to the rulers. References can likewise be found about the exchange of the congregation properties to the State during French upset. George Holyoke utilizes the term 'secularism' to allude to the pragmatist development of dissent in England Pantham 1997: 524 . The soul of Renaissance has obliterated the conviction of the middle age time frame, which has been heavily influenced by the strict confidence. The control of the Roman Catholic Church in all issue gets excruciating for the general population and they need a change. It is a period when spirituality is prevailing to the point that a lord can't conflict with the desire of the Church. The clerical set up of the archaic period goes under the assault of the Protestants who accepts that men are not for spirituality but rather spirituality is one fragment of human existence Kaintura

2011: 38 . The experience between the Church and the human qualities in the archaic Europe keeps on trying the meaning of secularism.

DISCUSSION

In this manner, the fundamental thought of secularism, as it wins in the west, is to isolate spirituality from the functionaries of the State. Indian secularism, in contrast to the west, is obviously, doesn't put stock in outright partition among spirituality and the State. The Indian vote based set up keeps 'equidistance' among spirituality and the State. Subsequently, it implies that the socio-political and different choices of the State ought to be liberated from the intercession of spirituality . It doesn't imply that the public authority will smother or rule all spiritualities and supports a solid down beating strategy for them.

CONCLUSION

All through my conversation on secularism, I emphasize my contention that there ought not be total detachment among spirituality and the State. I will be supportive of that type of secularism, which obliges both intercession and abstention of State foundations comparable to strict practices or keeps a principled distance of the State from strict organizations, which will get both opportunity of confidence and an honorable life for all. Along these lines, I have discovered that actually agnosticism for Gandhi, which Nehru additionally later endorsed, are most appropriate for this reason.

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SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL NECESSARY FOR DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC WORLD-VIEW IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the socio-pedagogical necessity of developing students' scientific world-view, the development of research work on the creation of new information and pedagogical technologies.

KEYWORDS: Interactive qualities, principles of integration, scientific world-view, innovation, continuing education.

INTRODUCTION

Today's education system does not allow the educational process to be conducted in an outdated style within the framework of new standards and programs. For this reason, pedagogical innovation is now considered as a whole complex dynamic process, and its interactive qualities, educational parts, functional characteristics and membership are being studied. In general, pedagogical innovation is a process of preparing future professionals to work in new conditions, which consists in the creation and introduction of new approaches and technologies that provide positive pedagogical results on the basis of previously acquired knowledge. Such pedagogical innovation means the purpose, content, characteristics, possibilities, tasks, stages of development, principles of pedagogical education, as well as the principles and mechanisms of integration in education and the creation of a system of methodological recommendations for selection, collection, application and use of innovative methods of integration in education. Through these, it is possible to understand the development of the scientific worldview, the achievement of high efficiency in this area. The results of our research in this area show that improving the results of work in the following areas will have a positive pedagogical effect in creating an innovative environment in education:

- Development of students' scientific world-view based on the rich spiritual and intellectual potential of our people and universal values;

- creation of effective organizational and pedagogical forms and sources based on rich national historical traditions, folk traditions and universal values in the development of scientific outlook in students;
- Development of information support of the educational process through the development and introduction of modern information technologies in order to find optimal options for the development of students' scientific world-view;
- Further increase the share of research work on the creation of new information and pedagogical technologies for the development of students' scientific world-view, strengthening the creation of tools and methods to increase the effectiveness of the integration of "science → education → practice" in the education system, etc.

Substantiation of classifications of pedagogical innovations provides an opportunity to make significant qualitative changes in the coverage of their content, in identifying ways to develop students' scientific outlook, achieving high efficiency at all stages of education. In addition, a convenient textbook on the assimilation of national spiritual values in history lessons has been created to use the rich heritage of Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Beruni and Al-Fargani, Mirzo Ulugbek, Ali Kushchi, as well as world-famous encyclopedic scholars. It contains information on the spiritual values relevant to each topic and is based on the fact that they have a positive pedagogical effect on the development of scientific outlook in students. Significant innovative approaches in the education system are achieved through the development of a scientific worldview in students and the implementation of the necessary sequence of development and implementation. As a result, the National Program of Personnel Training will train highly qualified, competitive specialists who meet the requirements of world education. Of course, large-scale research can be carried out to implement this necessary sequence, and they need to work together, involving experts in their fields. There are a number of pressing issues in this area that need to be addressed.

- creation and introduction of optimal options for informatization of the system of continuous education and development of scientific outlook in students at its level;
- Distinguish between generality and specificity of modern information and pedagogical technologies and create optimal options for their use;

- Development of systems of methodological recommendations for the relevance of innovative qualities formed in students to the practical activities of future professionals and their use;
- creation of organizational and methodological bases for the introduction of new information and pedagogical technologies in educational institutions;
- organization of centers for the development and implementation of pedagogical innovations;

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be noted that innovative approaches are an important process for the development of scientific outlook in students, in particular, the development of learning activities in students.

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THE IMPACT OF THE ORIGINATING GLOBAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT ON TENDENCIES IN EDUCATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the role of the formation of a global educational environment tendencies, knowledge as a reliable source of income and social protection.

KEYWORDS: Global education, human capital, science and technology, social protection, development index, social institution, secular education.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that currently global educational environment development tendencies is progressing in the world. Because nowadays all people have realized that the most demanded and justified investment is an investment is in “Human capital. The scientific and technological revolution happened in the 1950s of XX century turned economic competition between countries into emulation in science, engineering, and technology. In other words, we wouldn’t make a mistake if we say the competition is changed to between intellectual potential. The complexity of the global educational environment, development science technology and development of society are demanding on improving the quality. In turn the development of the global educational environment, the rapid application of discoveries, inventions, new ideas to real life leads to the rapid obsolescence of knowledge. The transition to a market economy, which is always accompanied by inaccuracy, leads to an increase in investment in knowledge as a reliable source of income and social protection, and new requirements for training. Consequently, the engine of providing progress, main factor of providing competitiveness depends on their knowledge, potential, rational use of available resources in the country, the ability to make the necessary decisions in a timely manner and rise to attention. Today it can be seen global educational atmosphere have been considered as human development index by UNO since 1990. Human development index is integral indicator that describes providing human perfection in society. It is obvious that expected long life, national income and the amount of

gross domestic product are linked to global educational atmosphere of citizens. The quality of education, literacy of citizens, expected life level are belong to depends on the national income created in the country, the size of GDP and the amount per capita. That's way the attention is being strengthening global education system to change completely. In many countries the attention is paying for education system globally.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Today, education as a social institution performs a civilizational (economic, humanitarian, cultural) function, and it must master the scientific knowledge, skills, abilities accumulated by mankind and cultivate a creative personality. If we explain it philosophically as society is renewed as a complex system, the main factor of the system that makes it up is that man must also be able to adapt to the new environment and perform its mandatory functions in order to meet its requirements. The literature distinguishes between mythological, scholastic, secular, and modern forms of education. The type of mythological education was based on fairy tales, myths and songs. Scholastic education involves the study of texts, rhetoric, grammar, understand of human nature. The secular type of education emerged in the early twentieth century. Modern education forms not only knowledge, but also quality knowledge, spiritual values. In the literature there are mythological, scholastic, secular and modern forms of education.

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THE MAIN FEATURES OF LEARNING ENGLISH IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: The planet, called the globe, continues to evolve to this day. We can see in history and today that man is in harmony with nature, that nature is becoming a key tool in the development of mankind. Man works continuously to meet his needs during his lifetime. Satisfies primary and secondary needs using naturally occurring minerals, water, land, and other similar resources. But given the limited resources, it forces them to be used productively. We can see that the geographical location of the countries of the world has a great impact on their economic development due to the presence or absence of available natural resources in them. At the same time, the country's potential in the field of science plays a high role.

KEYWORDS: English, business, world, development.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the world's population is 7 billion. States around the world have chosen a political and economic path to ensure the well-being of the people and the full satisfaction of their needs. Each country develops its own economic system in accordance with its political system.

If countries are economically developed, if the material well-being of their population is high, of course, their well-being will be ensured.

Uzbekistan is located in the Central Asian region of the Asian continent, its natural climate is favorable, rich in natural minerals, and the labor force is very different from neighboring countries.

The Republic of Uzbekistan gained its independence in 1991 and was recognized by all countries as a sovereign state. It has been accepted as an equal member of the United Nations as well as other international organizations.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

To date, it has been among the developing countries. Along with building a democratic state, it is confident in the transition to a market economy. One of the main requirements of a market economy is the development of entrepreneurship. It is important for entrepreneurs to provide production and services in the domestic market, as well as in foreign markets. At the United Nations, English, French, Japanese, Arabic, and Russian are accepted as international languages in the world.

The world's largest stock exchanges, financial markets and business centers are located in the UK, USA, Japan and China, and English is the medium of communication.

Today, English is seen as a means of global communication around the world. English is especially important for those working in this field. To develop an industry, you need to know the language of other countries, business. The role of English in business is very important. In business, mainly the means of communication play a big role.

Conferences and meetings are held mainly on business contacts and cooperation with foreign partners. So we need to learn and know English as our second mother tongue. There are so many words and phrases in English in business. I am convinced that when business partners exchange or communicate with each other, English words remove the barrier between them, they can quickly understand each other.

Here are a few examples of English phrases for business:

- Consumption
- To produce , to manufacture
- To operate
- The Board of Directors
- Asset management
- Sell goods
- Bring a product to market
- Payment in advance

In business, the business version of the English language is of great importance. In order to grow in business, it is necessary to know English at the "PRE-INTERMEDIATE" level in order to learn English effectively, avoid mistakes and pronounce phrases correctly.

I think it is necessary for a person entering a business to know English perfectly. When communicating at work, it is important to communicate in accordance with formal rules. Currently, we can see the level of learning English "IELTS", "CEFR".

In the field of primary education in our country, great importance is attached to the teaching of English as a second language to young people. There is almost no business literature in Uzbek. Researchers in the field are often forced to turn to English-language literature. For example, to solve the problem, the book of Philip Kotler, the most famous expert in the field, was translated.

When we analyze the development path of the world's largest and giant firms, companies and corporations, we can see that they have entered the international market as a result of operating and developing in their countries. For example, Coca-Cola, Samsung, Sony, BMW. These firms started their economic activities with a small circle of employees. Later, as a result of the development of technology, the volume and quality of production increased and entered the international market. High-level specialists have been recruited from abroad. This means that the company needs to use English to communicate.

Today we know the most economically developed countries - the United States, Great Britain, France, Italy, Japan, Canada. These countries have made a perfect transition to a market economy.

At the same time, we can take the example of developing countries in the world, such as China, Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Vietnam and Uzbekistan. They are also developing countries on the path to a market economy. There are also backward countries, such as Ethiopia and Afghanistan.

The independent Republic of Uzbekistan has been developing since 1991. The problem of budget deficit has been eliminated, the annual growth rate of the economy has reached 7-11%. As a result of the growth of exports, the republic received an increase in foreign exchange earnings.

CONCLUSION

Along with the development of the economy, special attention is paid to the training of personnel. One of them is that the state pays great attention to the teaching of foreign languages.

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ANTAGONIST: PHARMACOLOGY AND PHARMACOKINETIC ENHANCER

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ABSTRACT: Antagonist is that the hormone therapy of choice in pre-menopausal estrogen receptor positive carcinoma in women and sometimes in post-menopausal women. The environmental and genetic factors widely affect the pharmacokinetic parameters of a drug and this effect is understood as pharmgeonetics. The pharmacokinetic parameters that are what a body does with the drug, like bioavailability, half-life, distribution and excretion, has primary importance within the medication of a disease. The pharmacodynamics parameters which elaborate what a drug does with the body like side effects and positive symptoms are the pillars of therapeutic outcome. thorough knowledge of both parameters is important to urge maximum benefits from a medication plan during a disease for instance carcinoma .

KEYWORDS: Pharmgeonetics; Antagonist; Pharmacokinetic; Pharmacokinetic enhancer.

INTRODUCTION

Breast Cancer Breast cancer is that the second highly pervasive explanation for mortalities within the global . It doesn't cover only women but also men and food animals. Metastatic carcinoma is more drastic because the main causative agent isn't known. Although, multiple causes are known to be involved within the metastatic carcinoma , but still chemotherapy may be a question to completely treat this cancer . 1.3 million women suffer from carcinoma in us . Similarly 1 out of each 7 women had carcinoma . Not only humans but also animals become victim of carcinoma .Antagonist Among the chemotherapeutic anti-estrogens, antagonist is that the most essential as getting used for 40 years global wide. Yet there's no appropriate data for this medicine to support its entire kinetics and dynamics thanks to the environmental effects. Contrary to the previous decade when cervical cancer was the main explanation for death now carcinoma accounts for highest morbidity and death rate in females . The precise numbers of mortality and cancer cases in Pakistan areun known . Similar trend has

been observed for Australia. If we follow standard medication guidelines(SMG) proposed by WHO, the therapeutic outcome of a disease could also be altered significantly .

Mode of Action

Antagonist is being frequently prescribed as hormonal therapy of estrogen positive carcinoma within the clinics of Pakistan. there's a competitive binding of antagonist to estrogen receptors in cancer cells and other tissue targets, and this successively produces a nuclear complex that decreases DNA synthesis and inhibits estrogen action. it's a non-steroidal agent with potential anti estrogenic abilities which occupies estrogen binding sites in breast tissue and metabolized by the liver enzyme Cyp2D6 cytochrome P450, family 2, subfamily D, polypeptide 6 , rendering active metabolites of Antagonist includes N-desmethyl antagonist, endoxifen and 4 hydroxy antagonist .

BIOAVAILABILITY

Fuchs et al ,did work on the pharmacology of Antagonist plus bioavailability study depicts that further experiments should be performed on Antagonist thanks to its longer half – life. because the sampling time increases, pharmacokinetic parameters become more accurate and the other way around .

METABOLISM

According to a piece on urine samples of Antagonist detected through HPLC it had been observed that the metabolites are contained within the urine but not altogether samples. This thing clearly depicts that the metabolism of Antagonist varies in various individuals.

CONCLUSION

Antagonist is widely used anti carcinoma medicine prescribed in Australia and other country. The parameters of antagonist has been well experimented within the global including pharmacokinetic and Pharmacokinetic enhancer .parameters, whilst an extra study about its pharmgeonetic factor is required. Which is how various environmental factors affect the bioavailability and other pharmacological factors of antagonist. it's predicted that dosage regimen consistent with pharmgeonetic literature will increase the therapeutic results and wellbeing of a patient after using antagonist in carcinoma medication .

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ACCEPTING PHARMACY ONLINE LEARNING: MODELS OF BENEFIT

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ABSTRACT: Traditionally, instruction has spun around the possibility of a student being educated in an actual study hall setting. With late innovative turns of events and the "quick outcomes" world we now live in, elearning has gotten substantially more typical. Understudies and experts are presently ready to get to and secure talks, tests, confirmations and degrees on the web. The Purdue University College of Pharmacy's Center for Medication Safety Advancement has created three ervices to upgrade medicine wellbeing: The Veterans Affairs Yellow Belt Lean Certification Course, the Medication Safety Essentials Continuing Education Modules, and the Virtual Clean Room Simulation Certificate.

KEYWORDS: Elearning; o-portfolio; o-resources; intelligent professionals; assessment; without a moment to spare assets.

INTRODUCTION

Acquaintance Medication security proceeds with be a need in medical services. In clinics alone, more than 770,000 individuals are harmed or pass on every year from unfavorable medication occasions (UMO) . Drug store 2013, 1 44 \$5.6 million every year for each emergency clinic relying upon a clinic's size . This gauge does exclude costs related with re-confirmations, negligence and suit, or different wounds to patients as the consequence of ADEs. Further, this doesn't represent the effect UMO have locally setting where information is considerably more hard to evaluate. Consistently, clinics spend an expected \$1.56–\$5.6 billion to treat patients who endured because of UMO during hospitalization in the United States (US) alone . Despite the fact that examination on the expense and reasons for ADEs in the USA have been accounted for quite a long time in the writing, the issue was brought to the consideration of a bigger crowd in 2000 when the first of a progression of reports was delivered by the Institute of Medicine (IOM): "To Err is Human". The future reports "Intersection the Quality Chasm" and "Forestalling Medication Errors" were in this way delivered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three distinctive elearning openings have been portrayed that give instructive versatility, professional success, as well as expert advancement for drug specialists and other medical care experts. By acquiring and getting to information and abilities through elearning, students have more freedoms to build up the capabilities required in drug store and other medical services callings. The present students are innovation wise; students come into advanced education realizing the innovation just as commonly having utilized these stages in other instructive settings. Access to learning and getting proficient improvement turns out to be more available and adaptable for the present understudies and experts. Also, elearning has been discovered to be neither better nor mediocre than conventional methods of learning, as found by Cook et al. Numerous individuals favour web based usefulness and elearning gives access all day, every day in any area . It is presently simpler to refresh ranges of abilities, to obtain new information, and to show competency through elearning conditions. These three models—the Yellow Belt Lean Certificate, the Medication Safety Essentials Certificate, and the Virtual Pharmacy Cleanroom Simulation Certificate contributions—exhibit instructive modalities that ; help the student to stay informed concerning new information ; give a component to master and survey information and abilities, and ; make a strategy to normalize information and abilities to wellbeing experts like drug specialists.

CONCLUSION

Ongoing appraisal and examination is required as these mechanical advances and new academic methodologies are created to guarantee that new advances don't bargain the nature of instruction and clinical act of our medical care experts. Likewise with any program of guidance, assessment is an essential part of the web based instructing measure. It is essential to quantify the learning results and understudy accomplishment.

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TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF FIBER ON THE NATURAL PROPERTIES IN THE PROCESS OF APPLYING THE TECHNOLOGY OF PREPARATION OF COTTON FOR STORAGE

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ABSTRACT: This study describes the production of high quality fiber as a result of cleaning efficiency when the ginning process is carried out in a newly introduced device before ginning cotton in ginning plants.

KEYWORDS: Raw cotton, lint, quality, dirt, cleaning, fiber, seeds, damage, fungus, moisture.

INTRODUCTION

In the current technology, after ginning, the cotton is cleaned of small impurities and then of large impurities. Considering the fact that mechanical cleaning can damage the fiber and seeds, great attention is paid to the selection of the optimal number of seed cotton and fiber cleaning (the number of cleaning refers to the number of saw drums involved in cleaning the seed cotton).

This can be understood as follows. Experts obtained graphs of the dependence of fiber classes (varieties) on the number of cleaning drums when changing the appearance of fiber by hand and machine-picked cotton. The fiber class (type) increases significantly when the number of cleaning drums increases from 1 to 6; As it increases from 6 to 12, the cleaning intensity decreases. Further increase in the number of drums does not lead to an improvement in fiber quality Table 1. However, as the number of cleaning drums increases, the quality of the fiber deteriorates as a result of the negative impact of the mechanical processing of the fiber. If the number of cleaning drums is not increased too much when processing for machine-picked cotton, the deterioration of the fiber appearance will not be noticeable. As the number of cleaning drums increases, the appearance of the fiber deteriorates the micronaire performance.

It is necessary to minimize the mechanical impact on the process by maximizing the filling of the technological process of seed cotton processing with working bodies, as well as the rational placement of cleaners and reducing the number of transport devices.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Experiments were conducted to study the effect of fiber on quality indicators as a result of the increase in the number of drums for cleaning raw cotton in the coordinated technological process of the enterprise. The test used And-35, a variety of raw cotton, its initial quality indicators: III industrial grade, class 2, moisture 12.5%, impurity 11.9%, maturity 0.7%, the degree of mechanical damage to the seed 1.5%.

Table 1

The following table shows the interaction between fiber quality as a result of the increase in the number of cleaning drums.

Breeding Industry type	Mechanical damage to the seed, %			Short fiber content, %			Staple weight length of fiber, mm			Mass of defective and dity compounds, %		
	4	8	12	4	8	12	4	8	12	4	8	12
S-6524 II/2	1.9	1.9	2.1	7.7	7.7	7.9	32.4	32.2	32.2	2.3	2.3	2.4
And-35 III/2	3.7	3.8	3.9	9.5	9.0	9.8	31.3	31.2	31.1	3.9	3.9	3.9
And-35 IV/2	5.1	5.1	5.6	12.	12.5	12.2	30.4	30.4	30.0	8.5	8.6	8.7

In different selection varieties of raw cotton, the number of cleaning drums with a working capacity of 5 tons / hour is 6-8-12% mechanical damage to the seed%, short fiber content%, staple weight length of fiber mm, percentage of mass of defective and dirty mixtures, are shown in the graphs. (Figure 1)

The selected raw cotton in each selection and industrial varieties was carried out 3 times on experimental equipment, samples of raw cotton cleaned in the technological process were taken and laboratory analysis was carried out.

1. -picture. Mechanical damage to the seed, the amount of short fiber, the staple weight length of the fiber in mm, the mass fractions of defects and impurities are given.

The results of the analysis show that the graph shows the effect of cleaning frequency on cleaning performance at different work productivity, mechanical damage to the seed from 3.70% to 3.96% when the number of drums for cleaning raw cotton increases from 4 to 12 at 5 t / h; short fiber miklori, 9.51% to 9.82%; staple weight length of fiber from 31.35 mm to 31.15 mm; the mass of defective and contaminated compounds increased from 3.90% to 3.99%.

Subsequent experimental work used S-6524, grade II, grade 2 cotton raw material, its initial quality indicators: moisture 10.5%, contamination 9.6%, mechanical damage to the seed 1.90, from 1.98%; short fiber miklori, from 7.70% to 7.93%; staple weight length of fiber from 32.40 mm to 32.20 mm; the mass of defective and contaminated compounds increased from 2.30% to 2.47%.

And-35, IV-nav.2-class cotton raw material variety was used, its initial quality indicators: moisture 14.5%, contamination 15.5% mechanical damage of seeds from 5.10,% to 5.63%; short fiber miklori, from 12.50% to 12.72%; staple weight length of fiber from 30.45 mm to 30.05 mm; the mass of defective and contaminated compounds increased from 8.50% to 8.76%.

Analyzing the obtained results, we can see the decrease in quality indicators as a result of mechanical processing of raw cotton and its fiber products in the coordinated technological process of the ginnery. It is obvious that in the cleaning of low-grade and high-pollution cotton is the maintenance of quality and the introduction of its technology.

Flow 1-XP (RX-1), EN 177 saw sections, UXK cotton ginning units. The EN 177 saw section is the main part of the 1XP ginnery and 1RX regenerators, and the high-impurity cotton raw material is fully processed by this technological process. To clean the normal cleaning sections of cotton, the 3UXK unit with parallel-mounted cotton cleaning units is combined, the interchangeable UXK has 6 sections, 6 pile connections and 1 XK cleaner located in the last block.

The research and testing work was carried out on the basis of the "Coordinated Technology of Cotton Processing (PDQI-2016)", which has been used in the ginning industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan since 2016.

Table 2

Structural quality indicators of cotton fiber obtained from production according to the sequence scheme of the technological process

Technological process sequence diagram	Composite quality indicators of manufactured cotton fiber						
	Breeding and Industry type S-6524 II/2						
	Initial contamination, %	Sum of defects, %	Minor pollution%	waste %	Broken seed %	Roadside barrier %	Spun fiber %
SS-15A 2SB-10 UXK DPZ-180	9,60	4,42	1,14	0,93	0,69	1,01	0,07
MKO new SS-15A 2SB-10 UXK DPZ-180	4,50	2,85	0,96	0,91	0,65	0,98	0,05

The technological process of the ginning industry was carried out according to the sequence scheme, selection and industrial varieties S-6524 II / 2 according to the guidelines for determining the quality level of cotton fiber from production and was determined on the basis of the following tables and graphs. Selection variety S-6524, industrial grade second grade, initial contamination rate of second grade cotton raw material -9.6%; humidity level-10.5%. Before cleaning, the cleaning efficiency of the newly introduced device was 4.5%, ie the cleaning efficiency was 53.1%. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The results of the comparative research test are presented on the basis of the analytical graph

After cleaning of S-6524 II / 2 industrial grade cotton, the amount of fine defects is 4.42% to 2.85%, the amount of fine impurities is 1.14% to 0.96%, the amount of fiber is 0.93% to 0.91%, the amount of broken seeds is 0.69% to 0.65%, the amount of fiber seed husk is 1.01. The decrease in the amount of fiber from 0.07% to 0.05% and the increase in the quality of fiber products from 0.07% to 0.05% was determined on the basis of the analysis.

Table 3

Structural quality indicators of cotton fiber obtained from production according to the sequence scheme of the technological process

Technological process sequence diagram	Composite quality indicators of manufactured cotton fiber						
	Breeding and Industry type And-35 III/2						
	Initial contamination, %	Sum of defects, %	Minor pollution, %	waste %	Broken seed %	Roadside barrier %	Spun fiber %
SS-15A 2SB-10 UXK DPZ-180	11,90	5,19	1,19	1,16	0,83	1,28	0,12
MKO new SS-15A 2SB-10 UXK DPZ-180	5,40	3,46	1,05	0,98	0,76	1,06	0,09

Selection variety And-35, industrial grade third grade, initial contamination rate of second grade cotton raw material 11.9%; humidity level 13.5%; Before cleaning, the cleaning efficiency of the newly introduced device was 5.4%, ie the cleaning efficiency was 54.6%. The results of the comparative study show that after the cleaning process of And-35 III / 2 industrial grade cotton, the amount of fine defects is 5.19% to 3.46%, the total amount of fine impurities is 1.19% to 1.05%, the amount of fiber is 1.16% to 0.98%, the amount of broken seeds is 0.83. from 0.76 percent to 0.76 percent, fiber seed husk from 1.28 percent to 1.06 percent, and fiber content from 0.12 percent to 0.09 percent, which led to an increase in the quality of fiber products.

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TAJIKS OF JIZZAKH OASIS: TRADITIONAL WAY OF LIFE, CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS AND RITUALS

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ABSTRACT: In this article, the Tajiks are an Iranian people, speaking a variety of Persian, concentrated in the Oxus Basin, the Farḡāna valley (Tajikistan and parts of Uzbekistan) and on both banks of the upper Oxus, i.e., the Pamir mountains (Mountain Badaḡšān, in Tajikistan) and northeastern Afghanistan (Badaḡšān). Most Tajiks in the Pamirs (including about 34,000 in the Tašqorḡān district of the Xinjiang-Uighur Autonomous Region in southwestern China) are native speakers of several Eastern Iranian languages of the Pamir group (those in Tajikistan use Persian as an administrative and contact language, while those in China (speakers mainly of Sarikoli and Wakhi) generally do not know Persian, and use Uighur and Chinese in dealings with their neighbors. Emigrés from Tajikistan are to be found in Russia, Israel, Western Europe, and North America. The total population of Tajiks is estimated at about five million.

KEYWORDS: Navoi and Jizzakh regions, mind, manners, and beauty, Mountain of Religion.

INTRODUCTION

“Jizzakh region is located in the central part of Uzbekistan, and most of it consists of deserts and steppes. The relief of the region is unique and it includes mountains, foothills, steppes and plains (deserts). The earliest tribal communities in the region had favorable natural conditions and fertile lands for livestock and settled farmers, especially the availability of running water, which was the main reason for the mutual development of human activities and social processes in the oasis, It also laid the foundation for the formation of sacred shrines from ancient times, associated with the worldview and beliefs of the people,” wrote Akchayev F. The Nurata Mountains are located in the central part of Uzbekistan and are administratively part of

the Samarkand, Navoi and Jizzakh regions. The Nurata Mountains are described in Greek historical sources as part of the Soghdian Mountains, while in the Arabian geographical literature they are mentioned as part of the Qaf Mountains. Early medieval written sources refer to the mountains on the northern border of Samarkand as the “Mountain of Religion” – “the mountain of religion in which it originated”. The local people living in these mountains say that their voluntary conversion to Islam led them to call it by this name. Therefore, the local people considered their mountains sacred during the Mongol invasion and strictly protected them from non-Muslims.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The Ṭayyi’ _asher_ of northern central Najd, famous in Arab and later Islamic lore for the generosity of the fabled Ḥātem, were (on the evidence of Greek and Persian loanwords: Rabin, p. 201) in contact with Byzantium and Sasanian Iran from an early date. They came into prominence on the eve of Islam, when Ḳosrow II Parviz (r. 590-628, with interruptions) abolished the Arab Lakhmid dynasty and appointed a Ṭayyi’ chieftain as his governor of Ḥira, in effect march-warden of the Euphrates. It is not surprising, therefore, that their name was generalized in Syriac and Aramaic, from perhaps the fourth century, in the form Ṭayyāye (Segal, pp. 100-3) and Middle Persian, Armenian, Georgian (apparently directly from Middle Persian or Parthian: see Andronikashvili, p. 568), and Sanskrit (see below)—to denote Arabs as a whole. The Ṭayyi’ remained active in the Islamic conquests, and were still prestigious and in intimate contact with Iranians as recently as the 1950s, when the Kurdish villagers of Arpachi, northeast of Mosul, “claimed to be Arabs, belonging to the tribe of Ṭayy, their nearest neighbours across the Tigris” (MacKenzie, p. 419).

Examples of the complex semantic process of generalization and re-specialization: “Arab > (Arab) Muslim > Muslim > (Muslim) Persian/ Turk, etc.” are found in Armenian, where tačik ‘Arab’ came to mean ‘Turk’ from Seljuk times on (Schaefer, p. 18); and in English, an analogy to the second part of the process can be seen in the expression ‘to turn Turk,’ applied to a Christian convert to Islam (in the context of confrontation with the Ottoman empire). That this kind of transference was actually taking place in the minds of the local (Iranian) population in the year 728 is demonstrated in Ṭabari’s account of the Dehqāns of Bukhara reporting to the Arab governor Ašras on the success of the Muslim mission: “qad šāra al-nās kulluhum ‘araban” (‘All the people have become Arabs’: II, 1508, 13; Trans., Vol. 25, p. 47; quoted in Schaefer, p. 23).

Orthographically, we find the middle consonant as z in late Middle Persian, Qarakhanid Turkish (Yusof *Ḳāṣṣ-ḥājeb, tāžik and tājik*, loc. Cit.), recapitulating forms in the eighth-century Orkhon inscriptions, Old Chinese, and Tibetan (Schaeder, p. 19), and in New Persian until the late thirteenth century. From the fourteenth century the spelling *tāžik* also appears (see examples above); this may well reflect the pronunciation of previous centuries, when manuscripts did not consistently distinguish between written z and ž. From Timurid times (fifteenth century) the form is usually *tājik*, which has not been satisfactorily accounted for; perhaps it reflects a vernacular *Čağatāy* pronunciation, as continued in modern Uzbek, which substitutes j for Persian ž.

According to historical ethnographic literature, a mahalla is a large family or a community with a territorial unit that includes several families. The neighborhood is a historic community founded on the initiative of citizens. The neighborhood has a very ancient history its roots go back to the Bronze Age. Archaeological sources testify that it dates back to the Bronze Age. From the 3rd century BC to the beginning of the 5th century AD, all issues in the ancient state of Fergana (Parkana) were decided by a council of elders. The Uzbek mahalla is a cradle of goodness, a center of education, a place of national customs, traditions and traditions, and has played an important role in educating people in a mutually loving and generous manner, in the formation of a unique community and community traditions. In the nineteenth century, all vital problems in Uzbekistan were dealt with by mahallas in the city, rural and communities in the countryside. The mahalla and village community was led by an elder (in Khorezmold) elected at the community meeting.

Social life was concentrated in mosques, teahouses, and bazaars, which were mostly attended by men, and the community was made up of people living in a particular neighborhood, a village. Regardless of one's beliefs, nationality, or social status, the fact that one lived in the territory of a particular community was the only sign that belonged to that community. People in the community, regardless of their profession and position, had to participate in community work (*asher*) and ceremonies otherwise such a person would be left out of the public eye. The Tajik people are aware of the parties involved in the marriage tradition, in the selection of the bride or groom, and take into account their social background, their place in the community and their prestige. If the mind, manners, and beauty of the bride and groom are a part of it, then their relatives, the position of the generation in the community and public opinion in this regard are the second, and often the decisive factor.

CONCLUSION

In short, it is known that the custom of giving flour soup – “Atala” a new-born woman is widespread among all Uzbeks and has survived to this day, but the method of preparation of it differs depending on the ingredients added to it. For example, in some places it is fried in oil, in other places it is prepared without oil. In Surkhandarya, milky flour pour is made, and in Tashkent, it is made with minced meat. In Jizzakh, flour pour with a buttermilk or a sheep oil is prepared for a woman who gives birth [field records 6.]. Children are raised in cradles until they are one and a half to two years old.

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INTERNATIONAL LABOR STANDARDS AND THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING VACATION LEGISLATION

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ABSTRACT: This article examines the legislation that reflects the rights and interests of employees in the use of leave, analyzes the problematic aspects of the application of legislation in this area on the basis of the requirements of international standards and the experience of foreign countries and offers suggestions for their elimination.

KEYWORDS: Employee, leave, right to annual leave, employment contract, international standards.

INTRODUCTION

In order for each country to take its rightful place in the world community, it is necessary to pay special attention to the harmonization of its national legislation with the standards and norms established by international organizations for the protection of human rights and freedoms.

The right to rest and vacation, which is recognized as an integral part of human rights, is an integral part of the legal status of every employee. This right is recognized and guaranteed by many states. A universal international instrument adopted by the United Nations in accordance with Article 24 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights “Everyone has the right to rest and leisure, including reasonable restrictions on working hours and leave [1.188]” strengthened.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

According to Article 38 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, all employees have the right to rest. Working hours and duration of leave shall be determined by law. The fact that the right to rest and the right to leave is enshrined in the Constitution shows the importance of human rights in our country. As noted by President Sh. Mirziyoyev, our encyclopedia fully guarantees the personal rights and freedoms, political, economic and social

rights of citizens in full compliance with the requirements of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and other major international instruments [2.103].

Currently, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and foreign countries regulates a wide range of issues related to the conditions and procedure for granting annual leave to employees. In addition, there are a number of problems in the legal system of different countries related to the legal regulation of vacations and their application in practice. In particular, for many countries, the harmonization of national legislation on holidays with international standards remains one of the key issues.

The Republic of Uzbekistan continues to implement international norms in our national legislation. In particular, today 17 of the International Labor Organization ratified by the Convention and Protocol 1.

Article 16 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that leave provided by paid annual leave is the right of every employee. However, today there is a need to improve the norms determining the terms and conditions of leave on the basis of international standards and the experience of foreign legislation, based on existing problems in practice.

The current Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in 1995, and to date, several changes and additions have been made to the norms governing labor legislation. Also, the implementation of international labor standards and the introduction of new terms in the labor legislation, based on international experience, shows the need for the adoption of a new version of the Labor Code in our country. The new version of the draft Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, developed by the competent authorities and submitted for public discussion, includes a separate paragraph entitled “Annual leave” (§ 4), containing Articles 228-247. As a result of a comparative analysis of the norms governing the annual leave included in the draft of this document with the norms existing in the current Labor Code, as well as the study of existing problems in practice, the following recommendations are made:

The fact that the leave provided by the payment of paid annual leave is the right of every employee is also reflected in the current and draft Labor Code. However, in practice, there are many examples of complete and partial waiver of the right to leave, denial or restriction of this right by the employer. Therefore, it is proposed to include in the paragraph “Holidays” the norms prohibiting the right to leave and the restriction of this right. The strengthening of this right in this order is the experience of a number of foreign countries. In particular, the Moldovan Labor Code (Article 112) stipulates that the right to take leave may not be the subject of a

waiver, denial or restriction [3], In the Labor Code of Georgia (Article 31) the terms of the employment contract, which provide for the waiver or denial of the right to annual paid leave, are invalid [4] reinforced. Based on this experience and in order to ensure the use of leave for employees, it is proposed to supplement the draft Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the following provisions:

“The right to paid annual leave cannot be waived, denied or restricted. Any agreement to deny this right in whole or in part is not valid”.

One of the most pressing issues for Uzbekistan in terms of leisure time is the harmonization of the basic minimum leave with international labor standards. The current Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that employees are entitled to a basic annual leave of not less than fifteen working days. The new draft stipulates that the basic minimum leave is twenty-one calendar days. Article 3 of the ILO Convention № 132 of 1970 on Paid Labor Leave defines the period of leave in working weeks. The Lithuanian Labor Code (Article 126) and the Latvian Labor Code also stipulate that calendar days of work be granted [5] (A. 149.) also reinforced. Therefore, it is proposed to amend the rules on the duration of leave in accordance with ILO Convention № 132: **“The duration of the basic minimum leave is three calendar weeks (for a working week of five days or less) or four calendar weeks (for a working week of six days)”.**

The coronavirus pandemic, now known as COVID-19, which has complicated the economic, social and other sectors of the peoples of the world, has in practice created a number of problems in labor relations between employers and employees. “The coronavirus is not only a global health crisis, but also a serious crisis in the labor market and the economy,” said Gay Ryder, director-general of the International Labor Organization [6.403-407] Problems with the regulation of working hours, working hours, vacations and remuneration of employees in connection with the declaration of quarantine or state of emergency in many countries around the world have shown shortcomings in the existing regulations. In this situation, there was a need to create a legal basis for the procedure for granting annual leave to an employee by the employer, as an exception, without complying with the leave schedule. Therefore, it is proposed to include in the Labor Code of the new draft the following provision, which provides for the granting of leave by the employer in exceptional cases without complying with the leave schedule:

“The employer has the right to grant annual leave to all or certain categories of employees in the event of unforeseen circumstances and in the event of sudden suspension of work due to lack of raw materials, energy supply, natural disasters, losses”.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, today in the process of integration into the world community it is important to harmonize and improve the legal system of the world, in particular, the legal framework for the right of employees to work and leave in accordance with international labor standards.

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A BEGINNER'S GUIDE TO ART HISTORY

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ABSTRACT: When I first began learning about the history of art, I remember I wanted to understand one thing above all. I wanted to know the timeline. In other words, the grand story of one-style-followed-by-the next: Romanticism, Impressionism, Post-Impressionism, Cubism, and so on. I had the sense that art history was like a relay-race of artists, each passing the baton on from one to another, building up a cause-and-effect chain of history and development.

KEYWORDS: Baroque, contemporary art, Russian artist, Wassily Kandinsky, School of Art, discussion, Vasari identifies, W. J. Bouwsma.

INTRODUCTION

Beyond wanting to know about the -isms, I had other questions too: What was 'Baroque' and did it come before or after the Renaissance? Actually, come to think of it, what was the Renaissance? Did 'Classical' refer to classical music or something else altogether? What's the difference between 'modern art' and 'contemporary art'?

Where do you actually begin?

The truth is, nobody begins to think about the history of art without having first come across some art in the first place. Maybe it was a Jackson Pollock drip painting. Perhaps it was a visit to the Sistine Chapel in Rome. Maybe someone gave you a postcard with a Claude Monet painting on the front. Somehow, somewhere, an interest is kindled. I make this point because we all come to art history from some sort of perspective, and it is upon this perspective that we are likely to build up our mental map of how different styles of art, and ultimately individual artists, fit together. It is also how biases are able to sneak into our understanding even if we don't mean them to. But let's not worry about that for now...

For me, my interest was sparked one day when, aged 16, my art teacher at school took me aside and asked me if I'd ever heard of a painter called Wassily Kandinsky. I never had. Since my own paintings in class were beginning to move towards abstraction (without me really

intending it), my art teacher thought that I might find Kandinsky interesting. I took his advice and went to the school library where I found a book dedicated to the Russian artist. I had never seen anything quite like it. Kandinsky was a Russian who spent much of his adult life in Germany where he taught at The Bauhaus School of Art. As a painter, he is credited with making some of the very first purely abstract works in Western art. When I first looked at this painting, I especially liked the great ribbon of black that descends along the right-hand side, like a river or a pathway between hilltops. I also liked the way the different shades of colour overlap, intersecting and combining to form new shapes beneath. I really had no idea what the work 'meant'. I simply enjoyed looking at the explosion of colour and form appearing and disappearing with a strange, theatrical drama.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Next steps

If we wanted to place Kandinsky into the timeline of artistic movements as listed above, then he would sit inside the movement known as Expressionism (around 1905–1930). Expressionism originated in Germany at the beginning of the 20th century, mainly through poetry and painting. Artists like Kandinsky employed distorted forms and strong colors in order to evoke moods or anxieties. For Kandinsky, the subjectivity of art had a spiritual quality to it. Colours had the power to affect deep emotional responses in the viewer. Painting, he wrote, "can develop the same energies as music." For instance, the fact that he had a career arc of his own, where his work took on different forms as he associated with different artists in different European cities. Also, Expressionism itself is a umbrella term that encompasses many different artists with different styles, some abstract and some figurative.

I make this point to illustrate the fact that art is made in the midst of real circumstances, and that generalisations are useful only up until a point. Therefore, a useful next step for an art historian when looking at a work of art is to begin to build up a sense of time and place specific to the artwork and artist in question. There are all sorts of ways of doing this. For instance, one might begin by thinking about the following questions:

- Did the artist have friends or contemporaries that may have influenced the style of the work?
- Did the artist have a teacher or come from a tradition?
- Did the artist write about their own work?
- What were the materials available to the artist at the time?

- Was the artist a man or a woman, and could the answer have an bearing on the sort of art they might create?
- Might race or other specifics of the artist's identity play a role?
- Did the artwork get shown in public, and if so, what were the reactions of the first viewers?

These questions are by no means exhaustive, but they do perhaps point to the reality of any creative process: that all artists work within a context, with all the opportunities and constraints that this context might entail.

History is interpretation

I remember, long ago, having a discussion with someone about the nature of history. I remember saying that “History is a largely a matter of interpretation,” to which the other person replied something along the lines of, “Surely not. Isn't history about the facts of what actually happened?”

This idea — that history is about facts, not interpretation — seems especially pertinent in art history, since artworks are there in front of us even if the artist has long since died. But in reality, the way we interact and understand art is largely a matter of how the narrative of art history has been produced.

There are countless ways of exploring this, but I will keep to one well-known example. Thus, Vasari's historical design draws a correspondence between the passage of time and the ever increasing artistic achievement of Italian artists. The onward march of progress has a specified direction because Vasari identifies a model for its perfection. Today, the Renaissance stands as one of the cornerstones of art, which W. J. Bouwsma describes as “the traditional dramatic organisation of Western history.” In this organisation, the Renaissance is a historical turning point that brings the Middle Ages to a close and ushers in the modern era. It is “the inaugural chapter in the history that leads down to our own time.” In other words, the effect of Vasari's writing about his fellow countrymen was to help promote the Italian Renaissance to the elevated position of high-achievement in all of art history.

CONCLUSIONS

I described at the beginning of this article of my sense that art history was like a relay-race of artists, each passing the baton of creativity on from one to another. As the discussion about the Renaissance hopefully illustrates, it is Vasari that I ultimately have to thank for my relay-race picture of art history.

But is art always about progress?

The idea of progress is very appealing to historians because it gives a simple linear-narrative framework, that of history moving towards an idealised high-point.

The main problem with this way of looking at art history is that it tends to be exclusive, in that it takes the narrow view that Western art is the main story of art history. Where for instance could Buddhist art fit into the relay-race? What about Islamic art, Turkish art, Japanese art or the art of West Africa?

The truth is, many forms of art around the world have developed independently of each other or with some minimal overlap. Vasari was an Italian living in Florence, and as such was interested in how the wonderful art around him was made. That's understandable.

What we must do, however, is remember that all art history is tilted with a bias towards the storyteller. That's what makes it such as an interesting topic to learn about. And why, wherever we look, there is always more to understand about the history of art.

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HANDLING OF INTERPERSE AND CHANGED FONTS IN WORD RECOGNITION BY NATIVE AND NON-NATIVE SPEAKERS OF ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT: This examination explored the detectable quality of outwardly adjusted upgrades in word acknowledgment by English-and Korean-speaking adults. Forty four understudies from the U.S. what's more, South Korea partook in this examination. The orthographic profundity speculation and the psycholinguistic grainsized hypothesis guided this investigation. Three distinct text styles (and two lexical highlights were utilized in a lexical choice assignment. The outcomes showed that local English speakers were less touchy to the outwardly loud shapes i.e., exchanged and opposite text styles than the Korean members. It recommends that the psycholinguistic unit of the main language assumes a part in word acknowledgment past the language predominance i.e., first language versus unknown dialect .

KEYWORDS: English-and Korean-communicating in, language, scripts.

INTRODUCTION

Word distinguishing proof has since quite a while ago drawn analysts' attention, as word acknowledgment is the establishment of understanding cycles and fills in as an antecedent to understanding achievement (Adams, 1990). With the commitments of past examinations, the surviving group of information has been widened and extended as for the interaction among componential measures in perusing. Be that as it may, what actually stays hazy is the way lexical access is described by visual shapes and the degree to which lexical preparing is comparable or distinctive across speakers of various first dialects (L1s). Onaway to handle this request is to analyse lexical preparing without phonological and semantic controls in instruments with two gatherings of speakers whose L1s share a similar alphabetic rule however have various contents. English and Korean meet this condition well. This investigation analysed how local Korean speakers settle outwardly loud upgrades in English as an unknown dialect FL, in contrast with local English speakers. Since the two gatherings communicated in alphabetic dialects as L1s, the

reasoning for this investigation is three-overlap as far as the semantic properties of their L1s: shared traits divided among English and Korean as alphabetic dialects, contrasts in visual contents level direct course of action versus .

DISCUSSION

The aftereffects of this examination showed that the distinction in L1s was not influenced by the visual states of the upgrades. It appeared to be that a similar alphabetic standard shared by the two L1s assumed a part in visual handling. The local speakers beat the Korean partners in exactness. It was not amazing given the L1 and FL status for the two gatherings. In any case, the Korean members were quicker than the local partners in handling the visual stimuli paying little mind to the lexical element i.e., words or nonwords and recurrence i.e., high or low recurrence , with the exception of the great recurrence topsy turvy text styles. This could be clarified through the L1 impact on L2 word handling Akamatsu, 1999, 2003

CONCLUSION

This examination adds to the space of word acknowledgment by giving exact proof in English word acknowledgment by people whose L1s have comparative intralinguistic attributes yet have extraordinary contrasts by all accounts once more, English and Korean are alphabetic in nature however show revolutionary dissimilarities in composed structures . Notwithstanding the legitimacy this examination has, a few impediments should be noted comparable to future bearings. In the first place, this investigation didn't consider phonology on account of the point of convergence of visual goal. Since perusing is essentially making an interpretation of composed writings into phonological structures, further examinations that location phonology would widen the comprehension of word acknowledgment measures in cross-dialects. Besides, since the members are grown-ups, this investigation doesn't give a formative part of word acknowledgment. Relative investigations of youngsters' and grown-ups' handling of words would give bits of knowledge into formative directions. Then, since the Korean members were profoundly working understudies, it is muddled whether the aftereffects of this investigation can be summed up to average or lower entertainers in English as L2. More investigations with assorted English abilities are expected to support the discoveries of this examination. Ultimately, an incorporation of other L1 gatherings would add a fascinating picture to the cross-

phonetic L1 impact on L2 word ID. Resulting research is prescribed to incorporate gatherings that have distinctive L1 frameworks, like Japanese and Chinese.

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STUDY ON THE FEELING ANTAGONISM TYPES OF ALLIANCE FOR AS WELL AND VERY

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ABSTRACT: This investigation is a corpus-based methodology directed to analyze the two speakers as well and extremely as far as what feeling extremity types can be credited to the words in Alliance with these qualifiers. These qualifiers are for the most part known as strengthening a given significance of adjusted words, remarkably modifiers, action words or things. Notwithstanding, in light of the exact assessment of the British National Corpus (BNC), we accept that the noticeable feeling extremity sort of the words arranged with very is not at all like that of the words gathered with as well. For example, while the modifiers gathered with very communicates rather a positive conclusion extremity like in 'The soup is extremely delectable', those showed up with too generally express a negative estimation extremity like in 'This vehicle is excessively costly'. In many past works, it is attested that it is because of the specific semantic capacity of the verb modifier as well, since regardless of what semantic kinds of descriptors are, the arrangements like excessively little, too bright or too youthful express a negative assessment. By and by, we advocate that this understanding doesn't result from the unique capacity of as well, however from the semantic direction itself of the words gathered with these qualifiers.

KEYWORDS: British National Corpus (BNC), gathered, dialects.

INTRODUCTION

This study is a corpus-based methodology led to think about the two enhancers too and very in terms of what notion extremity types can be ascribed to the words in Alliance with these qualifiers. In human dialects, more can be found out about the contrasts between specific words through the words they assemble with. The last are alluded to, in the writing, as Alliance s. Firth (1957) underscored the significance of both phonetic and situational settings for the depiction of human dialects. "You will know a word by the organization it keeps." (ibid:195).The

plenitude of enormous assortments of spoken and composed corpora in electronic structure and the likelihood to examine those writings made by the improvement of innovations in corpus phonetics in the course of the most recent years laid the way towards better comprehension of how words are orchestrated in dialects. Subsequently, the idea of jargon and its commitment to the current semantics and sentence structure based hypotheses are re-examined now. Adverbs of degree and their alliance have been widely analysed in the writing. One of the primary examinations is Quirk et al(1985). The system utilized was basically a semantic one, by which speakers additionally called intensifiers, for example, totally, totally, really and very, were considered to communicate levels of expanding power, while downtoners, for example, rather, a digit, somewhat and very, were considered as scaling the feeling of a descriptor descending from an expected standard, regularly utilized as a conditioning gadget in situations where the modifier sounds excessively solid when left unmodified.

METHOD

The BNC Leech, Rayson and Wilson, 2001 is a 100-million-word organized assortment of verbally expressed and composed writings. The corpus was accumulated by a consortium of colleges, distributors, and the British government during the 1990s to be illustrative of the spoken and composed English utilized in Britain toward the finish of the 20th century. The BNC incorporates 90 million expressions of composed English from eight kinds and 10 million expressions of communicated in English from four social class groupings, gathered in 38 areas in the United Kingdom. In this manner, the BNC was picked in light of its impressive size and furthermore on the grounds that it joins a powerful linguistic tagger which works with the recovery and examination of words.

CONCLUSION

The qualifiers too and very are for the most part known as heightening a given importance of adjusted words, quite descriptors and verb modifiers. In any case, in view of the empirical assessment of the British National Corpus (BNC), we expected that the prominent assumption extremity kind of the words arranged with very is unlike that of the words assembled with as well. In many past works, it is stated that this is because of the specific semantic capacity of the verb modifier as well. In any case, we exhibited that this translation doesn't result from the unique capacity of as well, yet from the semantic direction itself of the words gathered with these qualifiers. The investigation we acted in this examination uncovers that the modifiers of negative extremity co-happen with too 7 times more regularly than those

of positive extremity. Actually, the modifiers of positive extremity co-happen with very 2.6 times more regularly than those of negative extremity. The conveyance of grammatical feature in the position gathered with these verb modifiers, the extent of words with positive/negative/unbiased extremity and the corpus types like formal/composed writings or casual/expressed messages unmistakably regret Biber's et al. (1999) declaration that qualifiers like very and too are utilized conversely.

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TRIANGULAR IRREGULAR NETWORKS FOR MODELING OF GEOMETRICAL STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT: The triangular irregular network (TIN) is used for modeling surfaces mainly due to effectiveness of surface representation. This property of TIN is result of flexibility of triangles vertices localization. However, there are restrictions and conditions for localization of points of input elevation point field to represent surface. We will discuss these issues in this article

KEYWORDS: The triangular irregular, vertices, The condition of correct configuration, is Lawson local optimization, polynomials, Lawson optimization, Input TIN with Delaunay triangles, georelief surface.

INTRODUCTION

The triangular irregular network (TIN) is used for modeling surfaces mainly due to effectiveness of surface representation. This property of TIN is result of flexibility of triangles vertices localization. However, there are restrictions and conditions for localization of points of input elevation point field to represent surface. The distribution of input points is according to [5] in relation to georelief surface curvature: the higher georelief curvature in given region the higher mutual points density must be so that with selected detailness there will be expressed the course of georelief. The condition of correct configuration of triangle toward georelief surface. There are geometrical properties of triangles with influence on origin of inaccuracy, for that reason is necessary to focus on relation between plane of triangle and georelief surface. Plane of triangle is defined by triplet of vertices

$$A_j(x_j, y_j, z_j), A_k(x_k, y_k, z_k), A_l(x_l, y_l, z_l) \quad (1)$$

located on georelief surface. The plane of triangle has the equation

$$\begin{vmatrix} x & y & z & 1 \\ x_j & y_j & z_j & 1 \\ x_k & y_k & z_k & 1 \\ x_l & y_l & z_l & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 0, \quad (2)$$

when adapted has form

$$\mathbf{Ax} + \mathbf{By} + \mathbf{Cz} + \mathbf{D} = 0 \quad (3)$$

where A, B, C, D are subdeterminants of determinant (2). And they are coordinates of the normal vector $N(A, B, C)$ of triangle plane [5].

Values of first partial derivatives (and from them calculated morphometric quantities) are given in triangle on basis of normal vector N , there are constants for whole plane of triangle. We assign values to the centre of triangle, its centroid T_s . In general, values on the georelief surface in point with same position like centroid T_s are different, there is different normal vector - N_{A_s} in point A_s than normal of triangle plane N_s (see fig. 1). For the difference of normal vectors ΔN is valid

$$N_{A_s} \neq N_s, N_{A_s} = N_s + \Delta N. \quad (4)$$

This difference creates deviation of calculated values of first partial derivatives and slope and aspect of georelief. Then is valid

$$(\gamma_N)_{A_s} = (\gamma_N)_{T_s} + \Delta \gamma_N, (A_N)_{A_s} = (A_N)_{T_s} + \Delta A_N, \quad (5)$$

where γ_N is slope in direction of slope curves, A_N is orientation of georelief to cardinal points, with sign A_s on the georelief surface and with sign T_s calculated from triangle. Sizes of values $\Delta \gamma_N$ and ΔA_N are numerical deviations [2, 5].

Important indicator of relation between plane of triangle and georelief surface is position of tangent point A_i of (tangent) plane, which is parallel to plane of triangle. Tangent point A_i will be the singular point of difference of altitude field ∇z , what are differences of altitudes belonging to certain point A_p in plane of triangle and on georelief surface. Tangent point A_i has the same normal vector like plane of triangle and so values derivated from it as well. Positional difference between point A_i and centroid T_s creates positional deviation.

Fig. 1 The deviation of normal calculated from plane of triangle

The condition of correct configuration of triangle toward georelief surface is fulfilled, if triangle vertices A_j, A_k, A_i are localized so that tangent point A_i of tangent plane parallel to plane of s -th triangle has the same coordinates x_i, y_i as coordinates x_{T_s}, y_{T_s} of triangle centroid T_s of s -th triangle. We can write this formulation according to [2, 5]

$$x_i \equiv x_{T_s}, y_i \equiv y_{T_s}, z_i = z_{T_s} + \Delta z; \Delta z = z_i - z_{T_s}. \quad (6)$$

The condition of correct configuration (6) is necessary condition for exact derivation of values of first partial derivatives and from them calculated morphometric quantities - slope in direction of slope curves γ_N , and orientation of georelief to cardinal points A_N .

Local optimization

As mentioned above TIN can be locally or globally optimized under some criterion. A triangulation is called globally optimal with respect to the given criterion provided that triangulation optimizes the given criterion among all possible triangulations of input set of points. A triangulation is called locally optimal with respect to a given criterion provided that every convex quadrilateral (consisting of two triangles sharing an interior edge) is optimal with respect to the given criterion [3].

1. {
2. while(triangulation is not locally optimal){
3. if(edge e is not locally optimal)
4. swap e with alternative diagonal;

5. }

6. }

The input is some initial triangulation and output is locally optimal triangulation under chosen criterion.

RESULTS OF LOCAL OPTIMIZATION

We have used mentioned principles on model surface typifying georelief surface. The model surface was given by analytical formula of two variables, which can be in general express

$$z = f(x, y). \quad (7)$$

This gives us possibilities to exactly calculate required values in every point. In real where there is only set of input points with elevation it is not know the formula (7). In that case we can approximate shape of surface in triangle and its neighbor by the second exact fit surface fitted through three triangle vertices and three other vertices of its neighbors [1].

The model surface was represented by TIN formed by Delaunay triangulation created from set of input points, including top points, saddle points, depression points, points located on ridge lines and valley lines. Subsidiary points were used outside investigated region to avoid long thin unnecessary triangles on the border of region. There were 626 triangles formed TIN on modeled surface. Input TIN with Delaunay triangles is shown on fig. 3.

CONCLUSION

The accuracy of the normal vector calculation is very important indicator of quality of TIN models and models of surfaces in general as well. The normal vector is very important parameter for visualization especially for computing illumination. Therefore a deviation of normal vectors produce none accurate model of georelief surface for visualization and also for processes modelling.

Reduction of deviation of normal vector has restrictions in case of using set of fixed elevation point as input for creating TIN. However despite of these restrictions local optimization of TIN (using Lawson algorithm) with value of deviation of normal vector as optimizing criterion provides not negligible results. This practice eliminates serious errors of normal vector calculations and better represents important shapes of georelief surface as well.

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RIEMANN-DARBOUX SUMS

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ABSTRACT: What is area? We are all familiar with determining the area of simple geometric figures such as rectangles and triangles. However, how do we determine the area of a region R whose boundary may consist of non rectilinear curves, such as a parabola? To see how this could be done let us consider the following process. Suppose that a function is continuous and non-negative on an interval $[a, b]$. We wish to know what it means to compute the area of the region R bounded above by the curve $y = f(x)$ below by the x -axis, and, on the sides, by the lines $x = a$ and $x = b$, in short, the area under the curve $y = f(x)$ as seen in the figure below.

KEYWORDS: a regular partition, function, Riemann integral, Lower Limit of Integration.

INTRODUCTION

The midpoints of each subinterval, maximum, Darboux.

Def: P is said to be a **partition** of the closed interval $[a, b]$ if P is a finite subset of $[a, b]$ which contains both a and b .

You may index the elements of P so that if $P = \{x_0 = a, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = b\} \subseteq [a, b]$, you may conclude that $x_0 = a < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{k-1} < x_k < \dots < x_{n-1} < x_n = b$.

Def: Let $P = \{x_0 = a, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = b\} \subseteq [a, b]$ be a partition of $[a, b]$. We define

- $\Delta x_k = x_k - x_{k-1}, 1 \leq k \leq n$, called the **width** of the subinterval $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$
- $\|P\| = \max_{1 \leq k \leq n} \Delta x_k$, called the **norm** or **mesh** of the partition P .

Def: A partition P is said to be a **regular** partition of $[a, b]$ if, for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\Delta x_k = \frac{(b-a)}{n}$, $1 \leq k \leq n$. In this case, $x_k = a + \frac{(b-a)}{n}k$, $0 \leq k \leq n$.

Def: Let f be a function bounded on $[a, b]$ and $P = \{x_0 = a, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = b\}$ a partition of $[a, b]$. By a **Riemann sum** of f over $[a, b]$, we mean the sum represented by $S_f^*(P)$ and defined by

$$S_f^*(P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{k=1}^n f(x_k^*) \Delta x_k, \text{ any choice of } x_k^* \in [x_{k-1}, x_k], 1 \leq k \leq n.$$

Remark: If $f \geq 0$ on $[a, b]$, then $S_f^*(P)$ can be thought of as an approximation to the area under the curve of f from $x = a$ to $x = b$.

Def: Let f be a function bounded on $[a, b]$. We say that f is **Riemann integrable** over $[a, b]$ if there exists a real number I such that $\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0 \exists$, for every partition $P = \{x_0 = a, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_{k-1}, x_k, \dots, x_{n-1}, x_n = b\}$ of $[a, b]$ and any choice of $x_k^* \in [x_{k-1}, x_k]$, $1 \leq k \leq n$, we have

$$\|P\| < \delta \Rightarrow |S_f^*(P) - I| < \varepsilon$$

In this case, we say $\lim_{\|P\| \rightarrow 0} S_f^*(P)$ exists, write $I = \lim_{\|P\| \rightarrow 0} S_f^*(P)$ and denote I by $\int_a^b f(x) dx$ or $\int_a^b f$,

called the **definite/Riemann integral** of f over $[a, b]$.

The components that make up the Definite/Riemann Integral are named as follows:

Remark: The limit $\lim_{\|P\| \rightarrow 0} S_f^*(P)$ satisfies all the usual properties of limits.

Remark: For $x_k^* \in [x_{k-1}, x_k]$, it is convenient sometimes to use one of the following:

1. $x_k^* = a + \frac{(b-a)}{n}(k-1)$, $1 \leq k \leq n$. The left end points of the subintervals corresponding to the regular partition P_n .

2. $x_k^* = a + \frac{(b-a)}{n}k$, $1 \leq k \leq n$. The right end points of the subintervals corresponding the regular partition P_n .

3. $x_k^* = \frac{x_k + x_{k-1}}{2}$, $1 \leq k \leq n$. The midpoints of each subinterval $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$, $1 \leq k \leq n$.

4. $x_k^* \in [x_{k-1}, x_k]$, $1 \leq k \leq n$, $\exists f(x_k^*)$ is a maximum in $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$, assuming f is continuous on $[a, b]$.

The corresponding Riemann sum is then denoted by $U_f(P)$, called the **upper Darboux sum** of f over $[a, b]$.

5. $x_k^* \in [x_{k-1}, x_k]$, $1 \leq k \leq n$, $\exists f(x_k^*)$ is a minimum in $[x_{k-1}, x_k]$, assuming f is continuous on $[a, b]$.

The corresponding Riemann sum is then denoted by $L_f(P)$, called the **lower Darboux sum** of f over $[a, b]$.

Note that we always have $L_f(P) \leq S_f^*(P) \leq U_f(P)$.

There is an alternative but logically equivalent definition of the integral that is conceptually easier to understand and that uses Darboux sums.

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SELF-EFFACING IN COMMUNITY SERVICE: EVOLUTION AND BASIC ACCEPTANCE OF THE SELF-EFFACING SCOPE FOR COMMUNITY SERVICEERS

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ABSTRACT: Self-viability convictions don't mirror a conventional feeling of capability, however are rather setting explicit. In this way, self-adequacy ought to be evaluated by utilizing a promotion hocscope estimating singular practices that permits social laborers to practice impact over occasions that influence their work life. The current investigation depicts the turn of events and starting approval of the self-viability scope for social specialists (SVSSS). Things were produced through the Critical Incident Technique. Sixteen social specialists with at any rate 10 years of administration took part in two center gatherings; they were approached to review basic occurrences in their work and to show the best practices to deal with the episodes. Content examination of the center gathering records gave 13 key self-adequacy convictions. The 13-thing scope was approved with an example of 805 social laborers.

KEYWORDS: Self-viability; community service; scope approval; exploratory factor examination; corroborative factor investigation .

INTRODUCTION

Bandura offered a proper meaning of self-viability: "Self-adequacy is characterized as individuals' decisions of their abilities to arrange and execute approaches needed to achieve assigned sorts of execution". Seen self-viability is subsequently a conviction about one's abilities to prevail in explicit circumstances . It is an individual appraisal of one's capacity to execute explicit abilities under specific conditions, and subsequently to accomplish a fruitful result. Assumptions for individual viability are recognized from result anticipations, since people can accept that a game-plan will create a specific result, however on the off chance that they trust themselves to be not able to play out the necessary conduct, it is far-fetched that the conduct will be begun or will continue even with impediments or aversive encounters. It is essential to take note of that apparent self-viability is a conviction about what an individual can do instead of an assessment of one's physical and character ascribes . This implies that self-viability is a setting

explicit build as opposed to an overall characteristic , that is, it doesn't show consistently across movement areas and situational conditions, yet shifts across errands and settings. Individual self-adequacy is a result of the collaborations among individual components , practices, social and natural conditions .

METHODS

We fostered a scope explicit for social laborers (SVSSS), following Bandura's rules for the improvement of self-viability scales. As per the hypothetical references, SESSW surveys singular practices that permit social laborers to practice impact over occasions that influence their work life. To recognize the action space and the troubles that social laborers experience each day in their work, we embraced the Critical Incident Technique . By an occurrence it is implied that any occasion or circumstance that is later, adequately complete and delegate of one's work. An occurrence is basic when it makes a huge commitment to work and difficulties one's capacities. This strategy has been effectively applied to various spaces ; for surveys see . CIT was completed into two center gatherings, each including eight social laborers, chosen based on the accompanying models: a. they worked in the region of Verona Italy; b. had at any rate 10 years of administration; c. were exceptionally energetic to give an individual commitment to exercises identified with lasting schooling; d. had given composed educated agree to take part in the investigation. Every meeting was separated into two phases, the two of which embraced semi-organized meetings.

CONCLUSION

This investigation is the basic phase in fostering the SVSSS, so it is on the whole correct to perceive a few impediments, including the way that we depended only on self-reports, and that people may not really know about their insights and contemplations or may react in socially alluring manners. A subsequent limit is that we didn't test the discriminant and focalized legitimacy of SVSSS. Future examinations should address this point and furthermore confirm the test-retest dependability of this action. To test the prescient legitimacy of SVSSS, further exploration ought to likewise contemplate and investigate the connection between scores on this scope and other significant factors in friendly work, like obligation to the calling, burnout and prosperity.

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COLLABORATIONS IN CONCLUDE CRAMPED DUPLICATE: LOGICAL AFFAIR AND AN APPLICATION TO PERSONAL VOTE-EARNING ATTRIBUTES

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ABSTRACT: There is some disarray in political theory, and the sociologies in general, about the significance and translation of connection impacts in duplicate with non-interval, non-ordinary result factors. Frequently these terms are nonchalantly tossed into a duplicate specification without seeing that their essence in a general sense changes the interpretation of the subsequent coefficients. This article clarifies the restrictive idea of reported coefficients in duplicate with associations, characterizing the essentially extraordinary interpretation required by summed up direct duplicate.

KEYWORDS: Conclude straight duplicate; association impacts; first contrasts; personal vote-procuring credits

INTRODUCTION

Conclude straight duplicate, restricted ward variable duplicate specifically, are presently very normal in empirical concentrates in the sociologies. Multiplicative connection terms have been regularly incorporated in direct model applications, and are surely known. As of late, there has been expanding attention paid to the job of these communication terms in such cramped structures in sociology written works, including Berry et al., Berry and Berry, Berry, Frant, King, Bramboret al., and Kamand Franzese. In any case, a couple of creators have noticed the extra intricacy forced by the conditional nature of interaction particulars throughout their investigations. A focal issue is that the translation of communications is more intricate in summed up straight duplicate than in the basic cramped develop, and it isn't generally realized that connection impacts are essentially brought into all conclude direct duplicate by the connection work.

METHODS

The treatment of collaboration terms in summed up straight duplicate is at the center of a conversation between rant and Berry and Berry concerning the determination of dichotomous duplicate with a logitlink work applied to state-level lottery information. Berry and Berry state that intentionally specifying multiplicative connection segments is suitable for testing speculations when the left-hand side specification is a log-chances structure like Equation , however when a normal likelihood is demonstrated, the automatically produced collaboration impacts in the minimal first contrasts for singular coefficients are sufficient for such tests.

CONCLUSIONS

To an incredible degree, the mission here has been to expand on the phenomenal, however maybe neglected, exposition ofFriedrich . This article goes past Friedrich in that he doesn't consider the summed up direct modeland centers rather rigorously around the understanding of associations in the straight model. Friedrich addressesa clothing rundown of reactions of the overall utilization of collaboration terms, shows why they are exaggerated, and afterward goes on to painstakingly build up the correctconditionalnature of association coefficients and their standard blunders. His work is stretched out here by building a system for deciphering and understanding higher-request association impacts and the more confounded proportions of unwavering quality of communication effects imposed by the summed up straight model.

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FARMERS' SCHOOL IS THE FIRST PROJECT IN UZBEKISTAN!

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ABSTRACT: This project, organized under the auspices of JSCB “Agrobank” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, has created another benefit for rural youth, especially for the effective use of their free time. The project is very well thought out and opens the doors of opportunity for our current youth.

KEYWORDS: Innovative, livestock, poultry, vegetables, melons, credit, expert, business, finance, law, vitamins, agrobank, competition, certificate

INTRODUCTION

The first project in Uzbekistan that will teach young people the use of the latest innovative technologies in agricultural production, cultivate educated and skilled young farmers and reveal the secrets of improving entrepreneurial skills in agriculture.

This project, organized under the auspices of JSCB “Agrobank” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, has created another benefit for rural youth, especially for the effective use of their free time. The project is very well thought out and opens the doors of opportunity for our current youth.

Absolutely free participation in the project means a greater opportunity for rural youth. It is no secret that many rural youth today are spending their most prosperous, innovative years in idleness. How to use this opportunity, to determine the path to the future depends on each unemployed youth.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The sectors selected in the project mean that it is possible to run their own business in rural areas.

Livestock sector - The rapid development of the livestock sector plays an important role in providing our people with cheap and quality meat and other food products, especially in increasing employment and increasing incomes of citizens living in rural areas.

In order to fully support the entrepreneurial initiatives of our people in the development of animal husbandry, the widespread introduction of scientific approaches and advanced modern technologies in this area, to further stimulate the production and processing of import-substituting and export-oriented livestock products, It will be another impetus for our youth to take advantage of the benefits set out in the resolution of March 18, 2019.

It is well known that the **poultry industry** is one of the seven treasures. Today, the industry has truly become a treasure. At a time when the state pays great attention to private entrepreneurship, this sector is developing. In particular, entrepreneurs engaged in poultry farming make up the majority.

In the past, poultry products were imported, but now they are grown in our country by entrepreneurs. Poultry products, in particular, chicken and eggs, can be purchased at any time in the markets. This collection is about poultry and poultry, their cultivation, care, eggs and their usefulness.

Vegetable and Horticultural Network - We eat a variety of vegetables every day. We don't think much about the fact that vegetables, which are a good source of vitamins and nutrients, also have a history of origin. Some of our vegetables were cultivated by our ancestors in ancient times, while others were introduced to humans only three or four centuries ago. Below we want to tell you a brief story about the history of our vegetables, which are well known to us and added to our dishes as a source of nutrients.

Historians say that people have mastered the cultivation and cultivation of vegetables since the Stone Age. At first, primitive people simply ate fruits and vegetables that grew wild. They later gradually learned to farm by preserving and planting their seeds and pods. Over time, the best, most productive, sweetest and most medicinal plants were selected and the selection process took place. Thus, for many centuries, people have brought vegetables to the appearance we know today.

In addition, it promotes the formation of qualified business representatives in the field of "Greenhouse", "Business, Finance and Law".

The advantages of the project are the opportunity to receive training from highly qualified, internationally experienced teachers in the field for 2 months in a short training

course, combined with theoretical and practical training, master classes of leading business owners in each field, business partners to expand their cooperation in the network. This project is truly the first project in Uzbekistan, which includes such benefits as obtaining a certificate of eligibility for a loan.

Areas of study - animal husbandry, poultry, vegetables and melons, greenhouses and business, finance and legal literacy. The curriculum focuses on developing both theoretical and practical skills. Practical classes are held on experimental plots and in large agricultural enterprises.

The project will be organized in 5 regions on the basis of agricultural universities:

- Tashkent (Tashkent region, Syrdarya, Jizzakh regions);
- Andijan (in Andijan, Namangan and Fergana regions);
- Samarkand (Samarkand, Navoi, Bukhara regions);
- Termez (in Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions);
- Nukus (in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm regions).

Candidates are required to:

- The applicant must be at least 18 years of age but not older than 35 years of age;
- have at least secondary education;
- Must be interested in animal husbandry, poultry, greenhouses and vegetables and melons.

All training costs are covered by Agrobank.

The competition for admission to the Farmers' School course is held in 2 stages. First, the documents of the candidates will be studied by the "Competition" commission, and a preliminary list will be formed. Candidates will then be interviewed directly or online.

Candidates will be required to submit the following documents through the school's official website:

- online survey (questionnaire);
- a copy of the document on education (certificate or diploma);
- 4x6 color photo;
- copy of passport.

Young people wishing to participate in the project should submit an essay, presentation or video electronically in the field of their choice.

The project will be implemented in constant cooperation with universities, research institutes, large producers, clusters and farmers with many years of experience in the regions.

As part of investing in the agricultural sector with social projects, JSCB “Agrobank” has prepared a set of manuals consisting of 100 books. The collection covers a wide range of scientific and practical information on the best practices of the agricultural sector, including fruit and vegetables and melons, grain, livestock, fisheries, beekeeping, developed countries and our country. The collection is the first edition in this direction, and in the future it is planned to further enrich it on the basis of feedback and suggestions for the continuation of this project. The guide is intended for industry professionals, farmers, and the general public, and all of these guides are equally accessible.

CONCLUSION

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stressed that the most effective factor in reducing poverty and increasing the income of the rural population is a sharp increase in productivity and efficiency in agriculture. In this process, the priority was to increase the yield per hectare from the current average of \$ 2,000 to at least \$ 5,000, and it was determined that we should widely introduce the most advanced technologies in agriculture, water-saving and biotechnology, seed, science and innovation.

This can be achieved with the created opportunity, only if there is passion.

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CLASSIFICATION OF MODERN TOURIST SERVICES BY TYPE OF ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the ways of development of modern tourism and methods of its promotion in Uzbekistan. Such activities are carried out by various enterprises of the tourism industry and their affiliates. Tourism activities are mainly carried out in leisure time.

KEYWORDS: Phenomenon of the XX century, tourism, domestic, inbound, outbound tourism, recreational tourism, ecotourism, religious tourism, sports tourism, shop-tours.

INTRODUCTION

Today, tourism is one of the main sectors of the world economy, and its share in world GDP is growing every year. The development of the tourism industry involves a large number of employees, fixed assets and large capital investments. It's big business, big money, and serious politics on a global scale.

Although tourism is a type of travel, it has a specific description in terms of its specifics, and the person involved is called a tourist. Importantly, we can call a tourist a traveler, but we cannot always call a traveler a tourist. Unlike travel, tourism is an area that is strongly influenced by the economy and politics. Tourism is a type of public travel that is carried out by tourists with a clearly defined tourist purpose, i. e. the activities of the tourist and the organizations that provide services for the organization and conduct of such travel. Such activities are carried out by various enterprises of the tourism industry and their affiliates. Tourism activities are mainly carried out in leisure time. For this to happen, there must be two conditions: the time spent on vacation and the appropriate amount of money.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

For a long time, only the rich were engaged in tourism. Currently, different segments of the population spend their free time and savings on various tourist trips. Although tourism, as it

is now understood, took shape at the end of the 19th century, it was not until the 20th century that it developed rapidly and became known as the “20th Century Phenomenon” as a result of advances in technology and social relations.

In order to determine the specifics of modern tourism, it is necessary to identify its important classification features. In particular, it is expedient to classify the organizational and legal forms in terms of geographical features, direction of tourist flow, purpose of travel, mode of movement, means of accommodation of tourists and the number of participants.

Domestic tourism is the travel of citizens permanently residing within the borders of their country to the place of temporary visit (without paid activity) for tourist purposes. Domestic tourism is not about crossing state borders and tourist formalities. The national currency, language and documents will remain the same. Domestic tourism accounts for 80-90% of the world’s travel. It is especially popular in the United States. International tourism is the travel of a temporary destination outside the country of residence for unpaid, permanent purposes. Foreign tourists include anyone who has temporarily visited a country for at least 24 hours. In recent years, there has been a trend of convergence of domestic and international tourism, which is explained by the simplification of tourism formalities (for example, the Schengen Agreement in the United Europe).

Inbound tourism - visits, travel to another country by persons who do not live permanently for unpaid tourist purposes.

Outbound tourism is an unpaid trip to another country by a person permanently residing in one country.

Recreational tourism is a form of tourism for a number of countries. Visits of foreign tourists to Spain, Italy, France and Austria are primarily aimed at this goal. Leisure trips are diverse and include interesting entertainment programs (theater, cinema, festivals, etc.), hobbies (hunting, fishing, music, art, etc.). may include ethnic travel related to the study of the national culture of the country. Healthy recreational tourism is a very personal experience. Depending on the means of exposure to the human body, recreation for treatment is divided into climatic, marine, mud therapy, and so on. Excursion tourism - includes visits and trips for the purpose of acquaintance (knowing, seeing and hearing). Excursion is a form of cognition that serves to broaden one's intellect and worldview. Qualified business tourism includes business travel. In today’s advanced society, life makes it necessary to connect international relations. In recent years, the visits of business representatives and entrepreneurs have become more

popular. A number of travel agencies specialize in organizing business trips of groups of businessmen for various purposes. The peculiarity of this type of tourism is that the participants of the meeting, which takes place in a business environment, spend more money when traveling around the country than the average tourist. That is why many countries try to host international forums and similar events.

Scientific tourism is a relatively new type of international tourism, which is carried out for the purpose of study, education, training. Studying abroad is one of the established segments of the tour business in Uzbekistan. The most popular type of travel is to learn the language, especially in the UK and other English-speaking countries.

The main purpose of sports tourism is to provide tourists with the opportunity to practice their chosen sport. Sports tourism requires the availability of the necessary base: various inventory, special tracks, roads, sports grounds, equipment. One of the main requirements for sports travel is to ensure the safety of vacationers.

Shop tours are typical for Russia and CIS countries. The main purpose of the visit is to buy consumer goods from abroad and resell them at home (shoes, knitwear and other goods from Turkey, Italy, Portugal, Syria; summer knitwear from Indonesia; postage from Greece and Argentina; furniture from Poland and Italy; electronics products from the UAE; buy cars from Germany, Sweden, Finland, Holland).

Religious tourism - pilgrimage, pilgrimage is now very popular and popular. Every year, hundreds of our compatriots go on pilgrimages to Mecca and Medina. Missing tourism is based on the need to visit relatives, places of birth and loved ones and plays an important role in international tourism exchange. An obvious example of longing tourism is the Crimean Tatar, Transcaucasian, Jewish, German and other ethnic groups that lived in Uzbekistan during the former Soviet Union and whose relatives still operate in various cities of the country.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, ecotourism - today eco-tourism is more in demand than ever. This applies to all countries of the world and is a form of active recreation. According to it, a person not only recovers his health, but also receives a number of aesthetic feelings. Today, eco-tourism is the most developed form of recreation, which is also a sport, and it is becoming the most developed field of tourism. The goal of ecotourism is to use nature wisely for tourism purposes to ensure the ecological security and sustainable development of present and future generations.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF 3D PRINTER IN SMALL BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT: The article explores the types of products that can be printed on 3D printers and their role in small business development.

KEYWORDS: 3D printer, small business, pixel, raw material, plastic, accessory, exclusive

INTRODUCTION

3D printers can print a variety of products for consumers. The 3D printer is designed for small businesses only. It gives people new opportunities at low prices to make good money and do their favorite job. How can I print products for sale on a 3D printer to start a small business? 3D printers used in small businesses are equipped with simple features, but if you analyze them in detail, you can see that exclusive small-scale products meet the needs of a wide range of consumers. From toys to printed shoes [1].

Those who start a business on a 3D printer can set up an online store of exclusive goods and sell printed products to order. Also, volumetric printing technology allows many people to realize their innovative ideas. Useful inventions can now be tested at home and work effectively

without large monetary costs. We analyze in detail all areas of application of 3D printer in small or home business at home.

You can print a variety of products on 3D printers.

Exclusive accessories:

- modern design coatings for smartphones and tablets;
- key accessories (emblems, pets, etc.);
- folders for documents;
- souvenir boxes.
- Souvenir products:
 - miniatures of famous architectural structures;
 - statues and sculptures of engineering structures;
 - mini-copies of people created from photographs;
 - jewelry (beautiful rings, bracelets).

A 3D printer is a revolutionary device for small businesses. Now there is an opportunity for small industrial enterprises to implement good industrial ideas. More creative people are able to independently implement and develop their ideas, make money, and do what they love at the same time. It is necessary to predict the growth of competition. In the near future, the 3D printer will become a home appliance. This means that a very big new change is taking place in the modern world. The number of consumers of 3D models created in three-dimensional modeling programs will increase.

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VIRTUAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT - AS THE FUTURE OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: Virtuality is increasingly attracting the attention of e-learning professionals. Distance learning has been successfully used in organizations and educational institutions for more than ten years. A learning environment has been created for the audience, where not only face-to-face meetings are organized, but also various tools for joint activities are provided. Learning portals are designed for informal and subject-specific learning. Such environments are now referred to as “virtual environments”. The main task facing organizations today is to create the necessary conditions for permanent learning centers that will integrate students into such a virtual environment.

KEYWORDS: Virtual, E-lear, portal, Adobe Connect, Unsatisfactory, Health Financial Management, Notre Dame, Generate.

INTRODUCTION

A study by E-lear’s Media Group found that 64% of corporate respondents already use virtual education and 18% plan to implement it in the near future. The use of virtual worlds in teaching will increase by 250 percent in 20 percent of organizations next year. The same study found that collaboration and social education were also developing rapidly - 77 per cent of organizations were planning or using such approaches to staff training.

Classification of virtual tools. Today, 4 types of training solutions are most commonly used:

1. Web meetings. This tool includes audio podcasts, recordings, archiving, desktop collaboration, drawing and sketching software and chat from WebEx Meeting Center and Citrix GoToMeeting, for example.

2. Virtual classes. Allows you to organize content libraries, thematic archives, tests on materials, student surveys and assessment tools. Virtual classes include WebEx Learning Center and Adobe Connect.
3. Virtual learning environment. This is a live environment on the browser platform. This provides easy access to real-time data, subject matter experts, and peers. Such tools are used to combine non-formal and formal education into a single learning space based on the simultaneous use of video and audio podcasts, virtual classes, network resources and social networks. Unsatisfactory and Virtual Activities 365 products have good reviews.
4. Virtual worlds. The most modern and promising tools of e-learning. They use very sophisticated software and as a result place high demands on teachers and service staff. Allows the implementation of the most complex scenarios of non-formal and formal education.

According to experts from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and the University of Notre Dame, virtual worlds are the most economical and effective solution for organizing distance learning. Here, Second Life is out of competition and is being adopted by organizations because the virtual learning environment is economical, interactive and easy to implement. This e-learning novel will appeal to both teachers and students. It is much harder for adult students to adapt in a real classroom - they are afraid of making the mistake in front of their peers. In a virtual environment, they feel more confident. This explains the liking of the virtual environment, as well as the fact that they are thematically content-oriented and constantly evolving technologically.

Advantages of a virtual learning environment. Leading global companies such as the Association for Health Financial Management, Intuit, ADP, Medco, IBM, CA and others regularly use virtual learning environments in their practices. They organize courses in almost all types of modern business activities: production and sales, management, marketing, personnel management, etc.:

- reduce training costs and increase learning efficiency;
- reduction of time for launching a service or product;
- increase ROI (investment profitability) for training;
- creation of an optimal learning environment / simulator;
- Achieving the maximum audience for the sessions;

- have permanent access to content and specialists.

In addition to organizing the training, the virtual environment provides detailed reports on all formalized accounting criteria and provides direct access to the content at any time convenient for the employee.

Recommendations for the implementation of virtual learning environments in the company.

The company's plan to integrate the virtual learning environment consists of six steps in a row:

1. Strategy and planning. You need to start by setting goals and making a plan. Find a qualified salesperson with an experienced and knowledgeable team. A trial period is required to access and correct the program - at least three months. The most optimal option is to create a single business model and to attract specialists from all areas of the enterprise. The wider the professional coverage, the more effective the learning process.
2. Gain experience. To implement a virtual learning environment, a leader is needed who will be the engine and soul of the project, around whom a team of like-minded people will crystallize. Due to his authority, over time, the work on the organization of training will continue on the basis of a strictly planned plan and within the agreed timeframe.
3. Make the event attractive. Advertise your event in each section a month or a month and a half before it starts. It is important that every employee knows their goals, objectives, and capabilities.
4. Training and education. During the preparation phase, make sure that the technical staff is properly trained and that potential visitors will have no problem accessing the claimed resources for training and escort purposes.

Connect a virtual environment or virtual event on the day the event starts.

Maintenance and analysis.

Even after the end of the next training cycle, it is necessary to advertise the event and constantly involve employees in the use of virtual environment content. Generate feedback from the learning process, periodically analyze the learning process and student behavior, and quickly adjust the learning environment if necessary.

CONCLUSION

Creating a virtual learning environment in the enterprise is a powerful tool for solving learning and professional development tasks. At the same time, they are constantly evolving and improving, bringing corporate education to a new, higher quality level. Now you can create your own virtual learning scenarios that cover narrowly focused topics and at the same time are cost-effective for the enterprise.

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THE ROLE OF LOCALIZATION IN INCREASING THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION OF THE ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT: The article discusses that there are no significant differences, as modernization is understood as reforms and improvement of equipment and technologies that advance society along the path of innovation. Initially, “modernization” did not have a semantic content in the part of the formation of any specific business institutions, and state’s achievement of certain social and economic indicators.

KEYWORDS: Significant differences, modernization, improvement of equipment, technologies, advance society, path of innovation, semantic content.

INTRODUCTION

A hypothesis is that modernization is a universal historical and institutional phenomenon representing a special complex of modernization – a system of economic, social, state, legal, scientific and technological institutions of a country or a geo-economic region into a more modern concrete-historical form. At the level of public administration, business, large public institutions there is an understanding of the need for innovative development and modernization transformations. In the Joint Communiqué following the 14th meeting of the Council of Heads of Government of the member states of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) (2015), the importance of cooperation was stressed, including through "the construction of new and modernization of existing international transport corridors".

There are no significant differences, as modernization is understood as reforms and improvement of equipment and technologies that advance society along the path of innovation. Initially, "modernization" did not have a semantic content in the part of the formation of any specific business institutions, and state's achievement of certain social and economic indicators.

The most widely used classification of modernization is that by dominant idea and intellectual organization of the implementation mechanism. Here, the following types of modernization are singled out: traditional modernization as transformations of traditional societies based on the development of equipment and industrial technology – industrialization (Lerner, 1965); convergence, put forward in the 1950s with the success of the scientific and technical revolution (Rostow, 1971; Black, 1976, p. 8); neo-modernization – Turkey, the countries of Latin America (Kaypak & Akin, 2017; Sakwa, 2012); postmodernization and comparative democratization (Sakwa, 2012; Capistrano et al., 2008, pp. 71-72). There are always links between belief systems and political and socio-economic variables (Table 1) The post-Second World War world order.

The events leading up to the Second World War and the war itself had a profound impact on political and economic structures. The main impact was the emergence of a bi-polar world order, with the rise of a communist power, the USSR, on the one side and the United States as leader of the liberal capitalist system on the other. The US had emerged from the war as the strongest economy, enjoying rapid growth and capital accumulation and saw itself as leader of the emerging monetary and economic system in the capitalist world.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

A major early objective of the US was to assist Europe's recovery and lay the foundations of a new economic and political order, while containing the spread of communism in Western Europe. It was felt that institutions were needed that were able to create functioning, liberal market economies and order the economic, social, and political development in a post-war world.

Amongst other things, the Bretton Woods conference of 1944 saw the establishment of the International Monetary Fund, and the International Bank (IMF) for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD or World Bank). Initially, these institutions were tasked with providing the loans, credits, and investment necessary for Europe's post-war reconstruction and preventing a backlash into depression. As former colonies of European powers achieved independence from the 1950s onwards, these two institutions started to get more involved in broader international development. Meanwhile, the United Nations (UN) came into existence in October 1945 with the goal of creating a wider and more permanent system of global security. In addition to maintaining peace and security, other important objectives included developing friendly relations among countries based on respect for the principles of equal rights and self-

determination of peoples; achieving worldwide co-operation to solve international economic, social, cultural, and humanitarian problems; respecting and promoting human rights; and serving as a centre where countries could co-ordinate their actions and activities toward these various ends. To help it carry out its mandate, the UN established a number of specialised agencies, including the World Health Organization (WHO), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and the International Atomic Energy Authority (IAEA). Most of these were established around the end of the Second World War, for example, the ILO and UNESCO in 1944, WHO in 1946, and IAEA in 1957.

CONCLUSION

For much of the past half century, the World Bank and IMF on the one hand and the UN system (led by UNDP) on the other, have stood as the two main poles of the international development system. At times, the relationship between them has been principally one of tension, with the Washington institutions emphasising market-led economic growth and the UN system championing human and social development. Arguably, however, the Millennium Development Goals represent an attempt at a consensus between them.

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IMPACT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH

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ABSTRACT: The article analyzes the concept of foreign investment as an important source of overcoming the backwardness in the socio-economic development of Pakistan. This is because foreign investment is only a source of funding to improve the structure of the economy and to diversify and diversify the country's exports. Due to foreign investments, technical, technological and innovative achievements are transferred to the industry, thereby introducing new technologies, new knowledge, better management and marketing methods in production, which contributes to an increase in the income of the population, their consumption of high-quality goods and products, in addition, there is a positive impact on social and economic development and increasing the level of well-being of the country's population.

KEYWORDS: Foreign investment, source, backwardness, socio-economic development, funding, structure of the economy, diversify, country's exports, technical achievements, technological achievements, innovative achievements.

INTRODUCTION

Many domestic economists point to foreign direct investment (FDI) as one of the most important sources of modernization of the Russian economy. Meanwhile, the practice of many foreign countries shows that even a large-scale inflow of foreign capital does not guarantee stable and high rates of economic growth. This is clearly confirmed by the experience of such large developing countries as Brazil, Mexico and Argentina.

Over the past decades, they have been among the main recipients of foreign direct investment in the developing world (see table). However, despite the attraction of significant volumes of foreign capital, their economic development over the past 25 years has remained extremely unstable. After an economic recovery, each time there is a new drop in the volume of GDP or a decrease in its growth rates to a minimum level. During the period from 1980 to 2004, the GDP of Mexico and Brazil decreased by 5 times, while that of Argentina - 9 times.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Historically, foreign investments in the development of Latin American states have played a special role. From the moment they gained political independence, foreign capital influenced the formation of the structure of their economy and socio-political climate. Largely under the influence of foreign capital, an extensive type of development based on the export of resources was formed (2). Therefore, despite the rich source of raw materials, the level of economic development of most states in the region remained low.

In the 1980s-1990s. the influence of foreign capital in the Latin American economy has increased significantly. After insufficiently successful attempts to create their own competitive processing industry, many countries in the region experienced debt crises, as a result of which they embarked on a course of liberal reforms. Under pressure from creditors, the access of foreign capital to the national economy was expanded and large-scale privatizations were carried out with the active participation of foreign investors. As a result, a significant part of the economy of many Latin American countries came under the control of foreign corporations, which have a serious impact on the situation in their economy and political sphere. Decreased controllability of the national economy, high dependence on uncontrolled flows of foreign capital and the interests of transnational companies have become one of the most important reasons for the periodic crises occurring here. The situation is especially difficult in Argentina, where in the 1990s. was realized, perhaps, one of the most radical scenarios of neoliberal reforms.

In the late 1980s. After currency crises, hyperinflation and bankruptcy of debt policy in the country, a rigid pegging of the national currency - the peso - to the US dollar was introduced, which effectively deprived it of the opportunity to conduct an independent monetary policy and regulate the exchange rate. The government cut government spending and attracted loans from the IMF. The measures taken helped to stop hyperinflation and even triggered some economic growth. However, in the late 1990s, Argentina's economy fell into a new recession, and in December 2001, Argentina defaulted. To keep the economy from collapse and prevent social explosions, the government was forced to ask the IMF again for financial assistance, in return for which it went to an unprecedented opening of the economy, not stopping at the loss of national control over it. The result of the reforms was the impoverishment of a significant part of the population and the actual loss of the country's economic sovereignty. Today, even to

solve problems in the housing and communal sector, the President of Argentina has to fly to France to ask concessions from French investors.

Another pole of the large inflow of foreign direct investment in the 1970-1990s. became the countries of East and Southeast Asia. However, unlike Latin America, Asian economic growth was more stable and higher.

Over the past 25 years, the economies of the countries of this region have experienced a decline only 1-2 times (see Fig. 2). If from 1980 to 2004 the economy of Argentina grew by 36%, Brazil - by 79, Mexico - by 96%, then the economy of Malaysia over the same period grew 4.5 times, South Korea - 4.8, China - 9.5 times. Malaysia also relies on a model of centralized strategic planning based on five-year development plans. Over the past 30 years, her government has successfully implemented a new economic strategy (1971-1990) and a national development policy (1991-2000), transforming an agricultural and mining country into a modern industrial state with a dynamic economy.

In contrast to the neoliberal scenario implemented in Latin America, in Asia the state did not withdraw from the economy, but assumed the main role in carrying out reforms. Economic transformations and attraction of investments were carried out in accordance with national plans for economic development. For example, the Chinese government made extensive use of a centralized industrial policy in the framework of five-year plans, carried out according to the so-called long-term program of four modernizations. Each plan identified the sectors that need to be upgraded first. Initial plans focused on agricultural reform, food processing, and the consumer goods sector. Later, plans were developed to diversify and modernize key industries such as mechanical engineering, building materials industry, chemical and automotive sectors.

CONCLUSION

Based on the experience of foreign countries, we can conclude that the inflow of foreign investment will have the most positive impact on the development of the country if its authorities have their own strong economic policy and attract foreign investment in accordance with its priorities. Where the state withdraws from the management of its economic development, yielding it to transnational corporations, the inflow of foreign investment does not ensure high and stable growth and often leads to a decrease in national sovereignty.

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WAYS TO IMPROVE THE SYSTEM OF REMUNERATION OF LABOR IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the relevance of the research topic, which is determined by the presence of a whole set of unresolved issues in the field of labor and social-labor relations in connection with the transition from the command-administrative system of public administration to a market economy. In the years of reforms in Russia, the total number of unemployed exceeded about 4 million. In 1992, it reached 6.5 million people in 2002.

KEYWORDS: Research topic, unresolved issues, field of labor, social-labor relations, connection, transition, command-administrative system, public administration, market economy, unemployed exceeded, functions, principles.

INTRODUCTION

In theoretical terms, there is still no consensus among economists and practitioners not only about the scientific definition of the economic category “wages”, but also about the functions and principles of its organization. Their ordering, systematization of the categorical apparatus are of particular relevance at the present stage of development. They will allow scientists and specialists to identify shortcomings in the organization of wage systems used at enterprises, to outline ways to improve them, to create an effective wage system at industrial enterprises of the Russian Federation.

The relevance of the chosen topic is also determined by the need to adapt the existing wage system to the conditions of a market economy. Thus, the main issues of the organization of wages at industrial enterprises in the conditions of a command-administrative economy were regulated exclusively by the state. At the same time, at modern enterprises, most of the problems of the previous wage system have remained.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

They still dominate the role of wages as an indicator of the employee's contribution to the overall product, its stimulating effect on the employee is weakly expressed. During the transition to the market, other requirements arose for the organization of remuneration. The main influence on its size began to be exerted by the financial and economic situation and the industry of the enterprise where the person works. In view of the insignificant experience and weak scientifically-based approach in solving the problems of remuneration in the state and at enterprises, an urgent need arose to improve the market levers of its functioning, to develop appropriate methods for introducing a new remuneration system that fully meet the requirements, functions, and principles of a market economy.

In the current conditions, it is necessary to solve other problems as well: to create a mechanism for managing the motivation of labor activity, to overcome the tendency to reduce the standard of living of workers, to reduce the differentiation in the levels of remuneration of managers and ordinary workers; to reduce the unreasonable difference in pay for work of the same complexity, to outline ways to improve the tariff system of remuneration for labor at a particular enterprise. All this makes the development of practical, scientifically grounded methods and recommendations for reforming the existing remuneration system urgent.

Currently, the management of industrial enterprises does not have strategic prospects for the development of the wage system. Their development, taking into account the analysis of world and domestic experience, is important and relevant for the economy of the Russian Federation.

Thus, based on the crisis situation, the need to adapt enterprises to new economic conditions, to develop their own wage system and its implementation at Russian industrial enterprises, the study of the topic we have chosen is especially important and relevant.

The biggest, in our opinion, the lack of scientific research in the sphere of the functioning of the remuneration system is that practical recommendations for eliminating the unreasonable difference in remuneration of the same complexity and intensity of work, stimulating creative work and education of workers in modern literature have not received sufficient coverage.

Based on this, it is necessary to continue the search towards the formation of a generalized foreign model of wages and its adaptation to modern Russian conditions.

Thus, currently in the scientific literature there are extensive studies devoted to the process of analyzing and improving wages in a market economy. At the same time, it is necessary to further develop the directions outlined by Russian and foreign scientists to

improve the mechanism for the functioning of the wage system at Russian industrial enterprises.

The goals and objectives of the dissertation research follow from the relevance of the chosen topic, the degree of its elaboration. The main goal is to substantiate the concept of functioning of the improved remuneration system, develop a system of measures, regulations and scientific and practical recommendations for the creation and implementation of an optimization mechanism for the remuneration system at industrial enterprises of the Bryansk region.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set and solved:

1. general principles, functions, tasks of wages are systematized, their interrelationships are determined; 2. a conceptual model of labor remuneration at industrial enterprises in countries with developed market economies has been created; 3. the actual model of management of the remuneration system used at industrial enterprises of the Russian Federation has been developed; 4. proposed methods for assessing the value of a workplace, determining priorities in remuneration for all categories of workers; 5. a model for the formation and distribution of the wage fund at an industrial enterprise has been developed, which meets the requirements of a market economy; 6. the mechanism of stimulation of productive and creative labor is revealed.

The theoretical basis of the dissertation is the works of the classics of economic theory, the objective laws of the functioning of the market economy, the work of domestic and foreign scientists - economists on the organization of the remuneration system, materials of the legislative and regulatory order in the field of remuneration.

The methodological basis of the dissertation is the following methods: general scientific (analysis, synthesis, induction, deduction, comparisons, generalizations, ascent from the abstract to the concrete); specific (statistical analysis, questionnaires, expert assessments, modeling, groupings, exceptions).

The developed concepts and substantiated conclusions were verified using the methods of logical analysis, building classifications, expert assessments, questionnaires, economic and mathematical methods, as well as by summarizing the practical experience of transformations and identifying the effectiveness of introducing a new remuneration system at industrial enterprises of the Bryansk region.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, approbation of the work results. The main results of the dissertation research were used in the development of regulations on remuneration at industrial enterprises of the Bryansk region: JSC “Thermotron - Factory”, JSC NII “Izotherm”, JSC “Thermotron”. The results of the thesis were reported and discussed at scientific and practical conferences: International Seminar “Economic education of students and students v as an important factor in the development of a market economy in the region” (Bryansk-2002); IV scientific-practical conference “Bridge to the Future” - International Youth Forum (Moscow-2002). On the topic of the dissertation, 7 articles were published with a total volume of 1.1 printed sheets.

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SOCIO-ECONOMIC ISSUES OF WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT IN RURAL AREAS AND WAYS TO INCREASE IT

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ABSTRACT: In this article, modern processes in the field of employment are associated with the emergence of various forms of ownership, which include the restructuring of employment, the formation of new areas of employment, the creation of surplus personnel from existing industries, the cause of the shattering is analyzed.

KEYWORDS: Modern processes, field of employment, emergence, various forms of ownership, restructuring of employment, formation of new areas, creation of surplus, shattering.

INTRODUCTION

Employment is a key factor in human development. Labor activity allows you to independently receive the income necessary for a decent existence, ensuring individual human development: including investments in education, health improves the quality of life, and allows everyone to realize the accumulated human potential. High employment also provides an increase in the aggregate income of society, creates an opportunity for the production of more public goods that contribute to human development.

The relevance of the topic is reinforced by the fact that in the context of a general socio-economic crisis that has engulfed all aspects of the life of Russian society, the agrarian sector of the economy is in a worse position. One-on-one with its problems is such an important administrative-territorial unit as a village. The quality of life in rural areas has lagged behind urban conditions by ten years, and by more than half a century - from rural areas in civilized countries. All this leads to a sharp decrease in the level and an increase in the cost of living of a peasant, to a decrease in the birth rate and an increase in mortality, and ultimately to a decrease in the share of the rural population and a decrease in the reproduction of the labor force in the countryside.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Research on the issues of women's labor and employment in rural areas is especially relevant due to the fact that women's employment is one of the determining factors in the conduct of demographic family policy in the context of the demographic crisis.

The problem of changing the socio-economic status of women in the context of market reforms is becoming an increasingly popular topic of research in society, which is explained by the depth and drama of the changes experienced. At present, the participation of women in production, the problems of combining their family and production functions are being studied quite actively. Such concepts as “gender inequality”, “occupational segregation”, discrimination in the labor market are emerging.

The position of women in the labor market largely depends on their competitiveness. But women, as a rule, turn out to be the least competitive category of citizens; they first of all, for example, suffer from mass layoffs of workers. The situation in the rural labor market of the republic is aggravated by the significant amount of hidden unemployment, especially female, the potential level of which is three times higher than officially registered.

The new opportunities associated with economic liberalization have been successfully exploited by only a few women, while the situation of the majority has deteriorated significantly.

A sharp deterioration in the situation of rural women, an increase in female unemployment, the feminization of poverty, the collapse of the social protection system in rural areas, the displacement of women into the informal sector of the economy, at the same time an increase in the educational level determined the choice of the topic of dissertation work.

The employment of socio-economic groups of the population in the period of growth of market relations is becoming increasingly important. The works of foreign and domestic scientists and economists are devoted to individual problems of women's employment. But the specificity of the problem, on the one hand, and the complexity, on the other, necessitate a more complete and detailed study of women's employment. Among foreign scientists, the works of G. Becker, J.M. Keynes, K. Marx and F. Hayek should be highlighted.

The issues of the theory of the formation of employment relations have received much attention in the works of domestic and foreign scientists-economists. The theoretical basis in the field of employment was laid by the founders of the so-called classical theory of employment, D. Riccardo, J. Mil, A. Marshall and others. Subsequently, their concepts were developed by neoclassical economists D. Giller. A. Laffer and others, whose views continued to

develop within the framework of the “monetarist school” by M. Friedman, E. Phelps and others. A significant contribution was made by K. Marx (study of the methodological foundations of employment) and J. Keynes (substantiation of the need for state regulation of the labor market as an inert system).

At the same time, the issues of the harmonious combination of professional labor and motherhood by women, especially in rural areas, in the context of the curtailment of agricultural production and the deteriorating demographic situation, remain insufficiently studied. The increased theoretical and practical significance of the problem determined the choice of the research topic.

The purpose and objectives of the study. The purpose of the dissertation research is to identify socio-economic factors affecting the level of employment of rural women in the Republic of Mari El and, on this basis, to build a promising model of employment for rural women and develop conceptual approaches to increasing the level of employment of women in rural areas, taking into account the socio-gender characteristics of the regional labor market.

The purpose of the study determined the formulation and solution of the following main tasks:

- to study the theoretical and methodological aspects of employment of the population and to give the author’s interpretation of the essence of the economic category “employment”, to determine the economic forms of female employment;
- to reveal the economic content of concepts related to women's employment and to determine their features in rural areas;
- to determine the reasons for the decline in employment in rural areas of the region (RME);
- to identify trends in the female labor market in rural areas of the region (RME); substantiate the need for a differentiated approach to professional training of women in rural areas of the region;
- to propose a model for the employment of women in rural areas, taking into account the demographic forecast and the state program to promote the employment of women in rural areas;
- to assess the factors that determine the level and dynamics of employment of rural women using mathematical calculations.

CONCLUSION

The results and conclusions obtained significantly expand the understanding of the position of women in the labor market in rural areas, and on the socio-gender characteristics of the labor market in the countryside. The proposed system of indicators for measuring the territorial disproportionality in the labor market in rural areas can be used by the Federal State Statistics Service and the Federal State Statistics Service Office for the RME to assess the state and determine the prospects for the development of the regional labor market. It can also be used by state authorities of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation, local governments for analyzing and forecasting the labor market in rural areas, taking into account the gender aspect, in developing measures for social protection and state regulation of female employment in rural areas, taking into account territorial characteristics.

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THE ROLE OF INDIRECT TAXES IN INCREASING STATE BUDGET REVENUES

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ABSTRACT: This article analyzes the study of VAT as an indirect tax that shapes the budget. The article also discusses the essence of the tax system, the essence of direct and indirect taxes, the role of indirect taxes in the tax system of the state is determined. The history of VAT, its peculiarities and advantages were studied. It describes the main changes in the tax legislation regarding VAT and their impact on the structure of budget revenues. This article gives the recommendations for state agencies and individuals solutions in the field of fiscal policy of the host to minimize fiscal risks associated with the collection of taxes in particular VAT.

KEYWORDS: VAT, indirect tax, shapes the budget, essence of the tax system, the essence of direct tax, history of VAT, peculiarities, advantages, tax legislation, structure of budget revenues.

INTRODUCTION

The tax system, being the most important part of the financial and economic system of the state, is a set of taxes, principles, forms and methods of their establishment, change and cancellation, payment and application of measures for their payment, implementation of tax control, as well as bringing to responsibility and measures liability for violation of tax legislation.

Indirect taxes play the main role in the Russian system of fiscal payments.

Indirect taxes are levied on goods and services that are levied through the price goods, and arise from economic acts and turnovers, financial transactions and are related to the economic potential of the taxpayer only indirectly.

VAT is an indirect tax. For the first time, VAT was theoretically justified and began to be introduced into taxation practice in the mid-1950s. in France. Years of experience have shown that VAT is an effective fiscal tool for harmonizing and integrating tax systems in different countries.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

So, at present, for a country to enter the European Union, it is necessary to have a VAT presence in the tax system.

In world practice, at the end of the 20th century, there was a tendency to expand the use of VAT in individual countries. Suffice it to note that out of 24 countries participating in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, only 4 countries do not use this tax: USA, Canada, Australia, Switzerland.

I would like to note that in Russia until 1992, a turnover tax was applied, the essence of which was to attract more than 80% of the difference between fixed state retail and wholesale prices.

The development of market relations in Russia led to the need to reorganize the calculation and collection of turnover tax, which predetermined the establishment of

in Russia, from January 1, 1992, the value added tax, which was supposed to prevent unjustified price increases. This tax practically replaced the previously existing tax on turnover and sales, not only replaced, but also significantly surpassed both the tool for generating budget revenues and regulating the economy (especially pricing).

In Russia, the VAT rate was 28%. The high tax rates caused criticism. For this reason, it was planned to reduce the tax rate to 14% already in 1994, but this would mean a sharp reduction in funds received by the budget, which would require either a reduction in budget expenditures, worsening the situation of the poor, or inflationary financing of expenditures, and in this case the situation that was characteristic of the first half of the 1990s would have worsened.

Since January 1, 2001, the procedure for calculating and paying VAT is governed by the provisions of Chapter 21 of Part Two of the Tax Code of the Russian Federation. The development of this tax in Russia proceeded along the line of unification of the method of its calculation. The leading role of VAT in the formation of tax revenues of the budget can be traced from the very beginning of its introduction. From 01.01.2004, the basic tax rate was reduced to 18%.

Value Added Tax is a federal tax that is levied throughout the Russian Federation. It is mandatory for all market participants, with the exception of beneficiaries and those who are exempt, allocated to special groups.

The main advantage of this tax in comparison with others is that value added tax is levied on income that goes to final consumption, which subsequently goes to investment savings, is exempt from tax, which indirectly stimulates these processes.

This tax results in an increase in government revenues from income earmarked for consumption, since they have a tax base that is broader than other taxes. Unlike other taxes, the state receives part of the income at each stage of production. Thus, the state revenue from this tax does not depend on the number of intermediate producers.

However, despite all the positive qualities of VAT, there are also disputes with tax authorities, which occur mainly on the calculation of VAT, registration of primary documents (refund, offset) of VAT, the application of tax deductions for VAT, the conscientiousness of counterparties to the chain of VAT payers.

The experience of foreign countries shows that indirect taxes have a different place in budget revenues. For example, for France the main source of budget revenues is VAT, which has been in effect since 1954.

In the practice of applying VAT in France, one can single out such positive features as VAT incentives, according to which the following are exempt from VAT: small businesses; all operations related to export; banking and finance; services of private doctors and teachers, etc.

VAT in Belgium also plays an important role in the formation of budget revenues. There are standard (21%) and reduced (12% for construction of residential buildings and 7% for agricultural raw materials, medicines, books, etc.) VAT rates. The lowest VAT rate in Europe is in Switzerland, where the fixed VAT rate is 8% of turnover, there are also reduced rates of 3.5% in the field of hotel services and 2.5% - for goods first need.

Thus, the positive factors of using VAT in foreign countries can be taken into account to improve the mechanism of an effective tax system in Russia.

In order to determine the place and economic role of VAT, it is necessary to analyze the dynamics and structure of all tax payments according to the data of tax authorities.

In order to minimize budgetary risks associated with the collection of taxes, in particular VAT, the following recommendations can be made to state bodies and decision-makers in the field of fiscal policy:

- if the macroeconomic forecast predicts a crisis or recession;
- when forming budget forecasts, avoid optimistic assumptions about the expected increase in the level of tax collection or increase the quality of tax administration;
- during a crisis, do not make radical decisions to change tax legislation;
- when drawing up long-term budget forecasts and budget strategy one should take into account the presence of negative trends in the dynamics of the collection rate,

since even insignificant annual decline in collection in the long term can lead to significant loss of income.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, VAT is an important source of replenishment of the state budget. In recent years, there has been a positive trend in the collection of this tax, which is associated not only with changes in tax legislation, but also with positive factors that influenced the growth of production and, consequently, an increase in tax revenues to the budget. However, despite the positive dynamics of VAT collection, there are a number of problems in the field of this tax, which require careful study and adoption of measures by the state to their solutions. This is, first of all, the improvement of the mechanism for collecting this tax, taking into account the positive factors of foreign experience. As well as solving the problems of optimizing VAT tax rates by reducing VAT rates and improving benefits for this tax. Implementation of all the proposed measures will not solve all problems, but will help to improve the efficiency of this tax and preservation of the positive dynamics of VAT revenues to the budget.

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ENHANCING THE ROLE OF ANTI-CORRUPTION IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT (AFGHANISTAN)

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the role of anti-corruption in economic development. After examining these data, the authors found that the number of violations correlates with the value of the Corruption Perceptions Index in the diplomat's country. The corruption perception index of the participant's country had a positive effect on the likelihood that he would offer or accept a bribe as a "citizen" or as a "bureaucrat".

KEYWORDS: Anti-corruption, economic development, violations correlates, Corruption Perceptions, Index, diplomat's country, perception index, participant's country.

INTRODUCTION

At the present time, the problem of corruption can be found in almost every country in the world. Corruption has been widely discussed as a transnational crime internationally in recent years.

It should be noted that the damage caused by corruption is equal for all countries, and it affects the country's political, economic, social and cultural reforms, as well as the country's image and investment attractiveness in the international arena.

Corruption is a big problem in many countries. The UN estimates the total amount of bribes in the world at \$ 1 trillion per year, and the amount of money stolen as a result of corruption at \$ 2.6 trillion per year, or more than 5% of world GDP, and calls corruption one of the main obstacles to development.

Because corruption is difficult to observe, most empirical research attempts to gather data to measure it and test simple economic hypotheses.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

One of the most famous measures of corruption is the Corruption Perceptions Index, which is published by Transparency International. It covers 180 countries and has been compiled

since 1995 based on surveys of experts and entrepreneurs - hence the “perception” in the name. In a famous article, Raymond Fisman (Boston University) and Edward Miguel (Berkeley) analyzed the behavior of UN diplomats working at the organization's New York headquarters: until 2002, diplomatic immunity allowed them not to pay fines for incorrect parking, but violations were still recorded in the police databases. After examining these data, the authors found that the number of violations correlates with the value of the Corruption Perceptions Index in the diplomat's country.

Abigail Barr (Oxford) and Danila Serra (University of Florida) in a laboratory experiment also find that corrupt behavior is correlated with the Corruption Perceptions Index of the participant's country.

In the experiment, participants in the role of “citizens” decided whether to offer a bribe, and participants in the role of “bureaucrat” decided whether to accept it. With a successful bribe, “citizens” received a certain bonus, but at the same time the remuneration of other - passive - participants was reduced by an even greater amount: this was done to illustrate the negative effect of corruption from the point of view of the whole society. The corruption perception index of the participant's country had a positive effect on the likelihood that he would offer or accept a bribe as a “citizen” or as a “bureaucrat”.

At the same time, survey-based indices have methodological problems: first, such indices do not distinguish between different types of corruption, which is important for an effective anti-corruption policy; secondly, survey participants may follow stereotypes when answering; Finally, when surveys are used, differences in coverage and comparative quality are inevitable. Therefore, studies do not always find a correlation between manifestations of corruption and the values of the index.

Jorgen Andersen of the Norwegian Business School and co-authors, including Elena Paltseva (NES and Stockholm School of Economics), who studied how much of the oil rent ends up in offshore accounts after the accumulation of money by the elites of oil-rich countries, find no connection between the amount of funds hosted offshore and the International Country Risk Guide used to calculate the Corruption Perceptions Index. They found that 15% of countries' revenues from oil exports end up offshore, but only when these countries have an autocratic regime that allows them to turn oil rents into political ones.

The work of Andersen et al. is one of the few examples of high-level corruption analysis. It is more difficult to study, but at the same time it involves much larger amounts and causes the greatest damage to society.

The overwhelming majority of research studies household corruption or corruption at the level of small firms and local authorities. For example, Benjamin Olken (MIT) and Patrick Barron (World Bank) for their work agreed that assistants will accompany truck drivers in Indonesia and observe what bribes drivers pay at checkpoints and weight control stations. The researchers, in particular, found that the amounts of bribes correspond to the basic hypotheses of microeconomics: when there are more checkpoints, there is less bribe for each; when the cargo is more valuable and the truck is newer, the bribes are higher. Towards the end of the route, the size of the bribe also increases: if the driver knows that this is the last bribe on the way, then he is ready to pay more.

Marianne Bertrand (University of Chicago) and Simeon Dyankov (Peterson Institute for International Economics) and co-authors conducted a field experiment in India, where participants were interested in obtaining a driver's license. It was found that Indian inspectors randomly give applicants low scores, thereby encouraging applicants to obtain the right to resort to corrupt practices. Passing the license exam is independent of driving skills - the system is not aimed at checking quality, but at extorting money.

There is a concept that corruption can be beneficial: it happens when, as shown in his famous 1964 article by Columbia University professor Nathaniel Leff, when government intervention in the economy either has the wrong goals or uses the wrong methods (see sidebar). But as economic policy in the world improves and the quality of institutions increases, the opportunities for "useful" corruption diminish.

Therefore, economists consider corruption to be one of the main obstacles to development. In addition, under a corrupt bureaucracy, "wrong" intervention in the form of, say, excessive regulation can arise endogenously - just to increase corruption payments. However, overcoming corruption remains a daunting task. Why? Several theoretical ideas help answer this question. They not only explain the complexity of the fight against corruption, but also allow you to analyze its features and economic consequences.

Corruption, while harmful to society as a whole, can be beneficial to both parties directly involved in a corrupt transaction. Economists distinguish two types of corruption: extortion and collusion. In the first case, an official extorts a bribe in order to do what he should already do.

Extortion is easier to fight because one side is interested in stopping it. In the case of collusion, an official takes a bribe for some of his illegal actions in the interests of the other side, and society becomes the victim, but it may not know about the collusion.

Ideally, the state should only intervene in the economy in situations where there are market failures, that is, where markets are ineffective - for example, due to externalities or information asymmetries. In such situations, creating the right incentives for officials, that is, incentives to work for the result that society needs, is a rather difficult and not always solvable task. And corruption is only one side of this problem.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, if the majority of officials are corrupt, then there is no or almost no censure and, accordingly, the costs of corruption are lower, that is, it becomes profitable to be corrupt. As a consequence, the task of anti-corruption policy is to “push” the system from a bad balance into a good one, which is possible only with systemic impact, that is, with a complex of large and decisive measures. This is exactly what happened, for example, in Singapore and Georgia - two success stories in the fight against corruption. But these and other examples are examples of small countries, often in special conditions: for example, in Singapore, the fight against corruption began after independence from Great Britain under an autocratic regime.

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TUNNEL NEUROPATHIES IN PRIMARY HYPOTHYROIDISM

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ABSTRACT: In the Department of Endocrinology and Neurology of Andijan State Medical Institute, 78 patients with primary hypothyroidism aged 18 to 59 years were examined for tunnel neuropathies depending on gender. It was found that tunnel neuropathies were a frequent syndrome of lesions of the peripheral nervous system in primary hypothyroidism. They were multiple in nature with the involvements of the upper limb nerves in the pathological process. The clinical picture was dominated by sensory disturbances. The severity and frequency of occurrence of tunnel syndromes in female patients were significantly more frequent and more pronounced than in male patients.

KEYWORDS: Tunnel syndromes, primary hypothyroidism, gender.

INTRODUCTION

According to the literature, the most common causes of the development of tunnel neuropathies are chronic long-term compression of the nerve trunk in the area of the tunnel (2). The most common places of compression of the peripheral nerves of the hands is the lesion of the median nerve in the carpal tunnel, and among the nerves of the legs - the lesion of the common peroneal nerve in the area of the fibular head (2,3). To assess the pathogenetic features in the areas of the most frequent lesions of the nerves of the extremities, it is important to timely identify the possible presence of anatomical prerequisites for the development of nerve damage in the tunnel. With hypofunction of the thyroid gland due to the accumulation of mucinous fluid in the nerve sheaths, the nerves swell. Tunnel neuropathies develop as a result of infringement of peripheral nerves in the osteo-ligamentous canals and under the muscle tendons against the background of the existing soft tissue edema (1).

The purpose of scientific research: to reveal the clinical features of tunnel neuropathies in primary hypothyroidism, depending on gender.

Material and methods: Examined 78 patients with primary hypothyroidism aged 18 to 59 years, mean age 38.2 ± 7.6 years.

The patients were observed in the Department of Endocrinology and Neurology of AndMI. AIT was the cause of hypothyroidism in all patients. All patients signed informed consent to participate in the study. Thus, the criteria for inclusion in the study were: age from 18 to 59 years, the presence of subclinical hypothyroidism (SH) and overt hypothyroidism (OG). The study excluded patients with mental and severe somatic diseases and diseases of the thyroid gland (thyroid gland), accompanied by thyrotoxicosis syndrome, in anamnesis; climacteric syndrome requiring hormone replacement therapy with estrogens; diabetes mellitus; autoimmune polyendocrine syndrome; pregnant and lactating.

According to gender, the patients were divided into 2 groups according to gender. The first group I included 55 (70.51%) female patients, the second group - 23 (29.49%) male patients.

The assessment of the severity of tunnel neuropathies (TN) was carried out according to the developed three-point scale intended for the overall assessment of tunnel neuropathies (T_o), as well as for assessing the severity of each tunnel syndrome separately. On this scale, T_o was assessed taking into account the number of affected nerves and the time of onset of symptoms during provocative tests. The assessment of the severity of an individual tunnel syndrome was based on the timing of the tests.

Statistical processing and visualization of the obtained results were carried out using the software package for statistical analysis STATISTICA v. 10 and built-in functions of Microsoft Office Excel. When conducting statistical analysis, the critical level of significance of the null statistical hypothesis was taken to be 0.05.

Research results. The clinical picture of this pathology included the patients' complaints of transient morning and nocturnal paresthesias, as well as positive tests for tunnel neuropathies, depending on the nerve being examined. In some cases, a decrease in sensitivity in the area of the affected nerve was determined. No movement disorders associated with tunnel neuropathy were identified. One of the features of tunnel neuropathies in primary hypothyroidism was their multiple natures.

Among female patients, tunnel neuropathies were detected in 72.7% of cases (40 people). The average T_o index in the examined patients was 2.31 ± 0.70 points. In men, clinical signs of this pathology were detected less often and amounted to 56.5% (13 people), ($p < 0.05$).

The average T_o index in women was 2.51 ± 0.68 points, and in male patients - 1.63 ± 0.81 points ($p < 0.05$).

In patients with primary hypothyroidism, in general, carpal tunnel syndrome was more common. Its clinical manifestations were observed in 53.8% of cases (42 people). The second most frequent occurrence was Guyon's canal syndrome. In all examined patients, this syndrome was observed in 44.8% of cases (45 people). In terms of frequency of occurrence, cubital canal syndrome ranked third among tunnel neuropathies in patients with primary hypothyroidism. Of the 78 patients examined, this syndrome was observed in 39.7% of patients (31 people). Tarsal canal syndrome was the rarest and occurred in about a quarter of patients with primary hypothyroidism (24.3%, 19 people).

Carpal tunnel and Guyon's canal syndromes were significantly more frequent and more pronounced in female patients with hypothyroidism than in men. Some predominance of the cubital canal syndrome was found among women - 47.2% (26 people), compared with the group of male patients, in whom this syndrome was observed in 34.8% of cases (8 people). However, there was no significant difference ($p < 0.09$). Tarsal canal syndrome occurred with almost equal frequency in the groups. Nevertheless, the severity of the last two tunnel syndromes prevailed in female patients (Table 1).

Table 1

The severity of clinical manifestations of tunnel neuropathies (compare T_0) in patients with primary, depending on gender, points ($M + \sigma$).

Tunnel Syndrome	Women		Men	
	Right limb	Left limb	Right limb	Left limb
Carpal tunnel syndrome	2,52±0,85 [^]	2,58±0,79 [^]	2,0±1,0	2,00±1,00
Guyon's canal syndrome	2,57±0,93 [^]	2,57±0,84 [^]	1,30±1,49	1,90±0,99
Cubital canal syndrome	2,56±0,56 [^]	2,44±0,81 [^]	2,00±1,16	1,80±1,23
Tarsal canal syndrome	2,40±0,70 [^]	2,20±1,10 [^]	1,70±1,01	1,70±1,10

Note - [^] - differences are statistically significant with a significance level of $p < 0.05$,

CONCLUSION

Thus, tunnel neuropathies were a common syndrome of damage to the peripheral nervous system in primary hypothyroidism. They were multiple in nature with the involvement of the upper limb nerves in the pathological process. The clinical picture was dominated by sensory disturbances. The severity and frequency of occurrence of tunnel syndromes in female patients were significantly more frequent and more pronounced than in male patients.

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THE SEVERITY OF PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS, DEPENDING ON THE BODY MASS INDEX

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ABSTRACT: On the basis of the clinic of the Andijan State Medical Institute and the Regional Endocrinological Dispensary, 110 patients were examined, of which 42 (33.2%) were men, 68 (61.8%) were women; the average age of patients is 52.3 ± 12.9 years; It was found that the group of patients with normal weight had a significantly lower severity of peripheral neuropathy in comparison with the group, the mean BMI of which was higher than normal, according to the scales by 29% on the NSS scale.

KEYWORDS: Diabetic polyneuropathy, Type 2 diabetes mellitus, overweight.

INTRODUCTION

Peripheral neuropathy is observed in almost half (47%) of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM-2) (1,2,3). Neuropathy is detected in 7.5% of patients at the time of diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. More than half of cases are distal symmetric polyneuropathy, in other cases focal lesions are recorded (6,4,5).

There is evidence that diabetic polyneuropathy (DN) may develop earlier in men with type 2 diabetes than in women and neuropathic pain is more common in women. However, not all researchers find this confirmation (5,7).

Purpose of the study: To compare the severity of peripheral neuropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus depending on the body mass index.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After signing a voluntary informed consent, 110 patients took part in the study, of which 42 (33.2%) were men, 68 (61.8%) were women; the average age of patients is 52.3 ± 12.9 years; the average duration of type II diabetes mellitus is 9.1 ± 6.4 years, divided into 2 groups. The first group consisted of 25 (22.7%) patients with normal body weight, for this group the average HbA1C level was $8.8 \pm 0.4\%$. The second group included 85 (77.3%) obese patients. In this group, the average HbA1C level was $9.2 \pm 0.8\%$.

The study was carried out on the basis of the clinic of the Andijan State Medical Institute (I, II, III neurological departments) and the Regional Endocrinological Dispensary. The criteria for the inclusion of patients in the study were the presence of verified type II diabetes (DM-2); the length of the disease is at least 5 years; age from 45 to 65 years; absence of focal brain damage according to MRI data; signing a voluntary informed consent to participate in the study.

The study of disorders of the peripheral nervous system was carried out using a standardized scale - the scale of neuropathic symptomatic score (Neuropathy Symptomatic Score - NSS) (1).

Statistical processing and visualization of the obtained results were carried out using the software package for statistical analysis STATISTICA v. 10 and built-in functions of Microsoft Office Excel. When conducting statistical analysis, the critical level of significance of the null statistical hypothesis was taken to be 0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Damage to the peripheral nervous system in the examined patients was represented by diffuse distal nerves of the extremities, focal forms were not found. Symptoms and signs of peripheral diabetic neuropathy in patients with type 2 diabetes were studied clinically by collecting complaints and targeted questioning and assessed on the neuropathic symptomatic score (NSS) scale, which assesses the subjective symptoms of neuropathy. The test results are shown in Table 1.

The NSS scale revealed a statistically significant difference between the indicators of groups 1 and 2 ($p < 0.05$). According to the NSS scale, patients in group 1 demonstrated a statistically significantly lower severity of symptoms of peripheral neuropathy compared with group 2 ($p < 0.05$). Most often (60% of the examined) patients of both groups stated that they had positive symptoms of neuropathy (burning, tingling). More rarely - the presence of negative

neuropathic symptoms - a feeling of numbness in the distal parts of the lower extremities (15%), the presence of pain in the distal extremities at the time of examination was actively reported by 7% of patients. The results of testing patients on the NSS scale are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Comparative results of the study of symptoms and signs of peripheral diabetic neuropathy in groups (points)

Scale	Group 1 [n=25]	Group 2 [n=85]
NSS		
Me (Q25; Q75)	5 (0; 6)	7 (6; 8)
M±m	4±3	7±2
Min-Max	0-8	1-10

*Note - n is the number of patients; * - statistically significant differences between groups (p < 0.05).*

The median of indicators of the 1st group was within the limits of moderate violations, of the 2nd group - within the limits of pronounced disorders. In group 1 (5 (0; 6) points), the median of indicators was 29% lower than in group 2 (7 (6; 8) points). The lower quartile of group 1 values showed that 25% of patients in this group had no symptoms of neuropathy. All patients of group 2 had symptoms of neuropathy, not less than moderate severity.

The minimum and maximum scores used by patients to assess their condition were also different: in group 1, based on the data of quartile analysis, 25% had no symptoms of neuropathy, in group 1, 100% of patients had symptoms of neuropathy. The maximum number of points scored between groups differed by 20% (8 points in group 1, 10 points in group 2) and, in group 1, was on the border of moderate and severe neuropathy, in group 2 - at the level of severe neuropathy.

The severity of symptoms of diabetic peripheral neuropathy, assessed by the NSS scale, differed between groups by 29%, in group 1 it corresponded to a moderate degree, in group 2 - a high degree. The differences between the groups are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

Thus, in the group of patients with normal weight, a significantly lower severity of peripheral neuropathy was revealed in comparison with the group, the mean BMI of which was higher than normal, according to the scales by 29% on the NSS scale.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT: This article about the importance of information technology in learning a foreign language.

KEYWORDS: Language, communication, teaching, foreign..

INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of information and communication technologies, which is one of the distinctive features of our time, special attention is paid to the organization and approach to the educational process, using its potential. The XXI century is the age of high technologies, and our modern youth is not only in line with the spirit of the times, but also in line with the development of the electronic world. Therefore, it requires a different approach to the process of educating the younger generation. The role of the teacher in the classroom is also changing. The teacher is now mainly a facilitator. It is time for teachers who want to keep pace with the times to be ready to revive any part of the lesson through ICT.

Resolution of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" "Introduction of advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies By radically improving the system of training the younger generation in foreign languages, training specialists who are fluent in these languages, and on this basis, their achievements in world development and the wider use of world information resources, international cooperation and dialogue. Creating conditions and opportunities for the development of the country "and the need to implement a number of important tasks for this purpose.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The document states that from the 2013-2014 academic year, foreign languages will be taught before the first grades of secondary schools. defining teaching using ICT tools as a basic educational subject given. In accordance with this important resolution, today, in particular, foreign language lessons have been given a deeper look. In order to properly defend the honor of the country on the world stage, our youth must first compete with their foreign peers conducted in English, which is an international business language.

Indeed, the role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and effectiveness of education, the targeted organization of lessons in the form of games that interest students is very large. The scope of their application is expanding day by day. In order to teach English to young people through computers, first of all, the teacher must be able to use computer technology at a professional level. To use this level not only to fully use the existing capabilities of the computer, but also it also includes the ability to create new curricula. To become a teacher at this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work harder on themselves in the field of modern technology. There are several advantages to teaching English with a computer over traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English learner is taught four areas of language (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will have the opportunity to test their skills. This is now possible with the help of advanced software. You just have to be more discriminating with the help you render toward other pupil.

In addition, every rule, every word, every unit of understanding taught in a foreign language with the help of a computer is better stored in the memory of the student. Naturally, the rich graphic capabilities of the computer The ability to deliver video in visual form makes it one of the most effective ways to teach foreign languages through the computer. In general, it is better to use Word and Power Point to explain current issues. Because I think it's much easier for students to understand when they're spreadsheets using Word. In Power Point, students can be more involved in the topic by presenting them in audio, visual, and video formats.

As the first head of our state I.Karimov noted in his book “High spirituality is an invincible force”: “We need to educate great writers, great poets, great artists. Recommendations for the reading process are one of the most pressing problems facing scientists. experts. For our talented young people to become experts in their areas of interest, they must first be fluent in all foreign languages, including English.

The main goal of natural learning is to teach students to speak a foreign language. Representatives of this method proceeded from the premise that, having learned to speak, students will be able to read and write in this language. M. Walter is considered one of the most orthodox representatives of the natural method. In questions of the place and role of the native language, on the teaching of grammar and other theoretical provisions, he almost completely adheres to the rest of the supporters of the natural method. In our opinion, M. Walter offers a unique way of working on vocabulary.

The direct method appeared on the basis of natural. It received this name because its representatives sought to correlate the words of a foreign language and its grammatical forms precisely with their meaning, without using the native language of the students.

The goal of the direct method advocates is to teach students the practical knowledge of a foreign language. Practical knowledge of a foreign language at the beginning was designated by the task of teaching students to speak, and this designation has survived to this day. This one-sided view of practical language proficiency played a specific role in the awareness of learning objectives. Based on the linguistic concepts that any language reflects the culture and spirit of the people who create this language, and that any language has its own system of opinions, the representatives of this method believed that the content embodied in one language cannot be adequately conveyed in another language. The result of this awareness of the language is the weighty state of the direct method - the need to eliminate the native language from teaching a foreign one.

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